

**Mechanistic model of pDNA production through
*Escherichia coli***

Maria Leonor Mouro Ferreira Gundersen Marques

Thesis to obtain the Master of Science Degree in

Biological Engineering

Supervisors: Dr. Carina Loureiro da Costa Lira Gargalo
Prof. Ana Margarida Nunes da Mata Pires de Azevedo

Examination Committee

Chairperson: Prof. Ana Margarida Pires Fernandes Platzgummer
Supervisor: Dr. Carina Loureiro da Costa Lira Gargalo
Members of the Committee: Prof. Krist V. Gernaey
Dr. Sofia de Oliveira Dias Duarte

May 2025

Declaration

I declare that this document is an original work of my own authorship and that it fulfills all the requirements of the Code of Conduct and Good Practices of the Universidade de Lisboa.

Acknowledgments

I would first like to thank Dr. Carina Gargalo for her guidance, clarity, and unwavering drive. Her determination to push boundaries and explore new directions inspired in me a deeper curiosity and ambition that carried throughout the entirety of this work.

A warm thank you to Professor Ana Azevedo, who not only introduced me to this project but also supported me through its many phases. Her encouragement and shared learning spirit made tackling new challenges a collaborative and memorable experience.

I would like to thank Professor Krist Gernaey, whose leadership shaped the research environment I was fortunate to be part of. His perspective, guidance and sense of humour were always appreciated.

A special thanks to Dr. Sofia Duarte for her patience and steady support in the lab. I'm grateful for her expertise, calm persistence, and kindness.

To my lab mates, Diogo and Iris, who were so generous with their knowledge and jumped into the lab trenches with me, and made the experience fun and memorable. To my office mates, Irene, Cristian, and Ingrid, for always being there to share laughter, doubts and small victories.

To Nick and Tony, whose friendships made a world of difference during my time in Denmark. A heartfelt thank you to Nick, our prolonged hangouts at the climbing gym were some of the best moments during my time there, made even better by the presence of the lafiest dog. To Tony, for sharing not just his house and daily life with me, but also his great taste in movies and food.

To Torga, for his enthusiastic and unwavering support, and for never once asking about my thesis.

I'm incredibly grateful for Miguel, whose humour and insight brought me perspective, inspiration, and distraction in equally important measures.

To Nailya, whose guidance, academic rigour and blind faith in me made this significantly less impossible, with steady and tender support in every moment. You were in every moment of this journey.

To my parents, who patiently supported me through the ups and downs of this process, bravely offered solutions to any issue I faced, and encouraged me to grow both personally and professionally.

And finally, to any college, friend, or stranger who knowingly or not helped me and put me on this path, through guidance or inspiration.

Abstract

Plasmid production is the bottleneck preventing the full exploration of plasmids towards vaccine production, manufacturing bioproducts, and gene and cell therapies, mainly due to a lack of process reproducibility and scale-up challenges. To address this, mechanistic models can be developed and implemented to improve process prediction and control. In this work, a kinetic model was developed to describe the production of plasmid in three strains of *E. coli*: two common laboratory strains, DH5 α and MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA (MG1655), and a novel engineered strain, GALG20. An identifiability, sensitivity and uncertainty analyses framework, implemented in Python, was built to analyse the model and its robustness. The parameters were estimated using batch data from the three strains and tested with batch data and shake flask data, which were produced over the course of this work.

The fitting obtained as a result of parameter estimation showed some predictive capability, having obtained R^2 values of ≥ 0.80 for plasmid and biomass for the three strains. The DH5 α model was not considered reliable due to overconfidence. Batch testing retained minimal predictability, with Coefficient of Determination (R^2) values for plasmid of ≥ 0.50 for both strains. Biomass and plasmid estimations differed from experimental values at a range between 6 and 51% for strain MG1655 and GALG20, respectively. The shake flask cultures obtained large errors for these variables, and in both batch and shake flask testing, the acetate production was underestimated. The poor fitting results were attributed to differences in behaviour and subsequent results between the datasets tested, which were more significant for shake flask experiments. The shake flask cultures resulted in low biomass concentrations and high acetate accumulation, due mainly to undergoing an adaptation period and the use of a chemically defined medium. While GALG20 noticeably underperformed, DH5 α and MG1655 obtained comparable or higher plasmid yields to those reported in literature. Although its effectiveness as a tool for experimentalists in early stages of research was limited, it established a pipeline for model formulation, parameter identification, estimate, and global sensitivity evaluation.

Throughout this work, a methodology for comprehensive model analysis was implemented and applied to a kinetic model of plasmid production using *E. coli* for plasmid production. By fitting and testing different datasets, insights on the structure of the model and relationships between parameters and

outputs were obtained.

Keywords

Mechanistic Model; Plasmid production; *Escherichia coli*; Identifiability analysis;

Resumo

A produção de plasmídeos é atualmente o principal entrave na exploração do seu potencial na produção de vacinas, bioproductos e em terapias génicas e celulares, devido sobretudo à falta de reprodutibilidade dos processos e dificuldade no escalamento do processo. Para ultrapassar esta limitação, podem ser desenvolvidos e implementados modelos mecanísticos que melhorem a previsão e o controlo do processo. Neste trabalho, foi desenvolvido um modelo cinético para descrever a produção de plasmídeo em três estirpes de *E. coli*: duas estirpes comuns de laboratório, DH5 α e MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA (MG1655), e uma estirpe geneticamente modificada, GALG20. Foi criada uma estrutura de análise de identificabilidade, sensibilidade e incerteza, implementada em Python, para estudar o modelo. Os parâmetros foram estimados utilizando dados de fermentações em batch para as três estirpes, e testados com dados de fermentações em batch e em shake flask, produzidos ao longo deste trabalho.

O fitting obtido durante a estimativa de parâmetros revelou alguma capacidade preditiva, com valores de $R^2 \geq 0.80$ para plasmídeo e biomassa nas três estirpes. O modelo da estirpe DH5 α não foi considerado fiável devido a uma confiança excessiva nas estimativas por resultar de dados pouco completos. Os testes com dados de batch mantiveram alguma capacidade preditiva, com valores de R^2 para plasmídeo ≥ 0.50 nas duas estirpes testadas. As estimativas de biomassa e plasmídeo diferiram dos valores experimentais entre 6 e 51%. As culturas em shake flask apresentaram erros elevados nestas variáveis, e tanto nos testes em batch como em shake flask, a produção de acetato foi subestimada. Os fracos resultados de fitting foram atribuídos a diferenças nos dados, mais significativas nas experiências em shake flask. As culturas em shake flask resultaram em baixas concentrações de biomassa e elevada acumulação de acetato, consequência principalmente de um período de adaptação e da utilização de um meio quimicamente definido. Embora a estirpe GALG20 tenha apresentado um desempenho bastante baixo, as estirpes DH5 α e MG1655 obtiveram rendimentos de plasmídeo comparáveis ou superiores aos reportados na literatura. Apesar da limitada aplicabilidade como ferramenta de apoio ao desenvolvimento experimental em fases iniciais, este estudo estabeleceu um processo para a formulação de modelos, análise de identificabilidade de parâmetros, estimação e avaliação de sensibilidade global

Ao longo deste trabalho, foi implementada e aplicada uma metodologia compreensiva de análise

a um modelo cinético de produção de plasmídeo utilizando *E. coli*. Através de fittings e testes com diferentes conjuntos de dados, foi possível obter conclusões sobre a estrutura do modelo e as relações entre os parâmetros e as variáveis.

Palavras Chave

Modelo mecanístico; Produção de plasmídeo; *Escherichia coli*; Análise de identificabilidade;

Contents

1	Literature Review	1
1.1	Plasmid DNA	3
1.1.1	Historical context	3
1.1.2	Characteristics	4
1.1.3	Applications	4
1.1.4	Production and purification	6
1.1.5	Market analysis	8
1.2	Plasmid Manufacturing	9
1.2.1	<i>E. coli</i> as host	9
1.2.2	Influence of Strain and Culture Conditions on pDNA Production	10
1.2.2.1	Shake flask	12
1.2.2.2	Batch bioreactors	13
1.2.2.3	Fed-batch	14
1.3	Modelling Approaches	15
1.3.1	Digital Twins in biotechnology	15
1.3.2	Mathematical models	18
1.3.3	Mechanistic models	19
1.3.3.1	Introduction	19
1.3.3.2	Kinetic models	20
1.3.3.3	Constraint-based models	21
1.3.3.4	Mechanistic modelling in plasmid production	22
1.3.4	Data and Model Analysis	23
1.4	Aim of the Study	25
2	Material and Methods	27
2.1	Experimental Data	29
2.1.1	Host strains and plasmid	29
2.1.2	Media composition and preparation	29

2.1.3	Inoculum and cultivation	30
2.1.4	Data collection and analysis	30
2.2	Kinetic Model	31
2.2.1	Datasets	31
2.2.2	Model formulation	31
2.2.3	Identifiability analysis	33
2.2.4	Parameter estimation	35
2.2.5	Uncertainty analysis	36
2.2.6	Global sensitivity analysis	36
3	Results and Discussion	39
3.1	Shake Flask Fermentations	41
3.1.1	Overview	41
3.1.2	Acetate accumulation	44
3.1.3	Biomass and plasmid	44
3.2	Kinetic Model	46
3.2.1	Batch bioreactors datasets	46
3.2.2	Analysis	48
3.2.3	Model testing	65
3.2.3.1	Batch bioreactors	65
3.2.3.2	Shake Flask	69
3.2.4	Impact of initial conditions	73
4	Conclusions and Future Work	79
4.1	Final Conclusions	81
4.2	Limitations and Future Work	84
	Bibliography	87
A	Experimental data	101
B	Model Analysis	105

List of Figures

1.1	Applications of plasmid DNA in the context of gene and cell therapies.	5
1.2	Schematic of the main operations for Plasmid DNA (pDNA) manufacturing.	7
1.3	Apollo 13 crew after landing, from left to right: Fred Haise, James Lovell and John Swigert (17.04.1970).	15
1.4	Data flow between Digital Model, Digital Shadow and Digital Twin (adapted from Fuller et al. (2020)	16
1.5	Sectors of application of Digital Twin technology (adapted from Qi et al. (2021)).	17
3.1	Experimental results from shake flask cultures with 20g/L of glucose for DH5α	41
3.2	Experimental results from shake flask cultures with 20g/L of glucose for MG1655	42
3.3	Experimental results from shake flask cultures with 20g/L of glucose for GALG20	43
3.4	Representation of estimation datasets for batch bioreactors experiments using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right).	47
3.5	Ranked importance of parameters (δ_j) using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right).	49
3.6	Collinearity indexes (γ_K) according to subset size using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right).	50
3.7	Model simulation vs experimental data for DH5α	52
3.8	Model simulation vs experimental data for MG1655	53
3.9	Model simulation vs experimental data for GALG20	54
3.10	Uncertainty analysis according to output, with corresponding mean and 10th and 90th percentiles, for DH5α	56
3.11	Uncertainty analysis according to output, with corresponding mean and 10th and 90th percentiles, for MG1655	57
3.12	Uncertainty analysis according to output, with corresponding mean and 10th and 90th percentiles, for GALG20	58

3.13 Sensitivity analysis using the Morris screening method, with mean and 10th and 90th percentiles, for each output in cultures for DH5α	59
3.14 Sensitivity analysis using Morris screening, with mean and 10th and 90th percentiles, for each output in cultures for MG1655	60
3.15 Sensitivity analysis using Morris screening, with mean and 10th and 90th percentiles, for each output in cultures for GALG20	61
3.16 Morris screening for each output in cultivations for DH5α	62
3.17 Morris screening for each output in cultivations for MG1655	63
3.18 Morris screening for each output in cultivations for GALG20	64
3.19 Comparison of data used for estimation and respective simulation with data used for batch bioreactors testing and respective simulation for MG1655	66
3.20 Comparison of data used for estimation and respective simulation with data used for batch bioreactors testing and respective simulation for GALG20	67
3.21 Comparison of data used for estimation and respective simulation with data used for shake flask testing and respective simulation for DH5α	70
3.22 Comparison of data used for estimation and respective simulation with data used for shake flask testing and respective simulation for MG1655	71
3.23 Comparison of data used for estimation and respective simulation with data used for shake flask testing and respective simulation for GALG20	72
3.24 Simulations of MG1655 model using different initial values.	75
3.25 Simulations of GALG20 model using different initial values.	76
A.1 Experimental values of plasmid (P), biomass (X), glucose (S), and acetate (A), and respective standard deviations (SD) for each time point, for shake flask culture of DH5α . . .	102
A.2 Experimental values of plasmid (P), biomass (X), glucose (S), and acetate (A), and respective standard deviations (SD) for each time point, for shake flask culture of MG1655 . . .	103
A.3 Experimental values of plasmid (P), biomass (X), glucose (S), and acetate (A), and respective standard deviations (SD) for each time point, for shake flask culture of GALG20 . . .	103
B.1 Ranked importance of parameters (δ_j) according to output using DH5α (top), MG1655 (middle), and GALG20 (bottom).	107
B.2 Fitting of estimation data to the simulation according to output using DH5α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right).	108
B.3 Correlation between estimated parameters using DH5α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right).	109

B.4	Simulation vs experimental results according to output for testing model using batch cultures using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right).	109
B.5	Simulation vs experimental results according to output for testing model using shale flask cultures using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right).	110

List of Tables

1.1	Summary of reported results for pDNA production using <i>E. coli</i> across different operation modes, strains, and carbon sources.	11
1.2	Classification of cell population models based on structure and segregation.	20
2.1	Strains used and their respective genotypes.	29
2.2	Summary of the datasets used in this work.	31
2.3	Nominal values and units of parameters used in simulations, taken from apparent experimental values from glucose cultures (α) or estimated values from mixed cultures (β), described by Lopes et al. (2014).	34
3.1	Maximum biomass and plasmid (specific and volumetric) yield and maximum acetate detected for DH5 α , MG1655, and GALG20 in shake flask cultures.	43
3.2	Final parameter set for the three strains (DH5 α , MG1655, GALG20), with estimated parameter values highlighted in blue.	51
3.3	Values for the Coefficient of Determination (R^2) of each output, the final Weighted Residual Sum of Squares (WRSS), and the average Normalized Root Mean Squared Error (nRMSE) of each output, for the three strains (DH5 α , MG1655, GALG20). $R^2 \geq \sim 80$ are highlighted.	52
3.4	Estimated parameter values, respective 95% Interval of Confidence (IC), for the three strains (DH5 α , MG1655, GALG20).	55
3.5	Morris ranking of the top 5 parameters, θ , according to absolute mean value, μ^* , for cultures using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (middle), and GALG20 (bottom).	65
3.6	Comparison of maximum values (g/L) for the batch bioreactors testing dataset and the corresponding simulation for each output, and respective error (%).	68
3.7	Comparison of maximum values (g/L) for the shake flask testing dataset and the corresponding simulation for each output, and respective error (%).	73

3.8	Initial concentrations of biomass (X), plasmid (P), glucose (S), and acetate (A) for each estimation and testing in batch (B) and shake flask (SF). Highlighted in blue are the values that were assumed.	74
B.1	Sensitivity matrix for DH5 α according to the outputs biomass (X), glucose (S), plasmid (P), and acetate (A).	106
B.2	Sensitivity matrix for MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA (MG1655) according to the outputs biomass (X), glucose (S), plasmid (P), and acetate (A).	106
B.3	Sensitivity matrix for GALG20 according to the outputs biomass (X), glucose (S), plasmid (P), and acetate (A).	106

List of Symbols and Abbreviations

Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence	HPLC	High-performance Liquid Chromatography
bp	base pairs	IVT	<i>in vitro</i> Transcription
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate	kb	kilobase
CAR-T	Chimeric Antigen Receptor-T	MIR	Mid-Infrared
CBM	Constraint-Based Modelling	MFA	Metabolic Flux Analysis
IC	Interval of Confidence	ML	Machine Learning
CPPs	Critical Process Parameters	MLR	Multi-Linear Regression
CQAs	Critical Quality Attributes	mRNA	messenger RNA
CRISPR	Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats	NIR	Near-Infrared
CS	Carbon Source	NN	Neural Network
DCW	Dry Cell Weight	nRMSE	Normalized Root Mean Squared Error
DoE	Design of Experiments	OD	Optical density
DM	Digital Model	ODEs	Ordinary Differential Equations
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid	OR	Origin of Replication
DS	Digital Shadow	PAT	Process Analytical Technologies
DT	Digital Twin	PLS	Partial Least Squares
EE	Elementary Effects	PSS	Production supplement solution
EFP	Exponential-Fed Perfusion	pDNA	Plasmid DNA
FBA	Flux Balance Analysis	QbD	Quality by Design
dFVA	Dynamic Flux Variability Analysis	R^2	Coefficient of Determination
GMP	Good Manufacturing Practices	RI	Refractive Index
HGT	Horizontal Gene Transfer	R&D	Research and Development
		RNA	Ribonucleic acid

shRNA	short hairpin RNA	VGT	Vertical Gene Transfer
SSS	Seed supplement solution	XR	Extended Reality
TES	Trace element solution	WLS	Weighted Least Squares
TFF	Tangential Flow Filtration	WRSS	Weighted Residual Sum of Squares
USD	United States Dollars		

Nomenclature

X	biomass concentration (g/L)	$Y_{P/A/S}$	acetate yield on glucose (g/g)
S	glucose concentration (g/L)	$Y_{X/S}$	biomass yield on glucose (g/g)
A	acetate concentration (g/L)	$Y_{X/A}$	biomass yield on acetate (g/g)
P	plasmid concentration (g/L)	Y_{P/X_S}	plasmid yield on biomass growth on glucose (g/g)
μ_S	specific growth rate on glucose (h^{-1})	Y_{P/X_A}	plasmid yield on biomass growth on acetate (g/g)
μ_A	specific growth rate on acetate (h^{-1})	K_S	affinity constant for glucose (g/L)
μ_T	total specific growth rate (h^{-1})	K_A	affinity constant for acetate (g/L)
μ_{maxS}	maximum specific growth rate on glucose (h^{-1})	K_{iX-A}	inhibition constant of biomass growth by acetate (g/L)
μ_{maxA}	maximum specific growth rate on acetate (h^{-1})		

1

Literature Review

Contents

1.1 Plasmid DNA	3
1.2 Plasmid Manufacturing	9
1.3 Modelling Approaches	15
1.4 Aim of the Study	25

This chapter focuses on the main theoretical concepts involved in this project. It contains a section regarding plasmid Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA), complete with a summarised historical context, an overview of plasmids, their applications and production methods, as well as a market analysis. Regarding modelling, it begins with an overview of Digital Twins within bio-manufacturing, followed by an explanation of mechanistic models, their governing principles, and applications. It finalises with a description of the aim of this work.

1.1 Plasmid DNA

1.1.1 Historical context

The term plasmid was first used by J. Lederberg in 1952 [1], in reference to extranuclear molecules that he had observed, which were able to reproduce autonomously. At that time, the term plasmid was used distinctively from the term episome, which was defined as a transmissible genetic component that could exist as an extranuclear element or integrated into the chromosome [2]. This distinction remained until the late 1960s when it was concluded that these terms were redundant, and so the term episome was subsequently abandoned [3].

Several seminal studies were performed during the 1960s, notably by T. Watanabe [4], which explained the transmission of antibiotic resistance in enterobacteria through extrachromosomal factors (R plasmids). These studies proved both the extrachromosomal nature of R plasmids and the need for physical contact between cells for resistance acquisition. T. Watanabe also introduced the notion that plasmids had distinct genetic components responsible for replication and antibiotic resistance [2]. In the late 1960s, it was shown that plasmid elements generally have a circular structure [5], and about a decade later, it was concluded that bacterial plasmids had a circular form [2].

In 1972, S. Cohen and H. Boyer formed a partnership aimed at using plasmids as tools to clone genes [2]. This resulted in significant advances in key components of gene cloning, namely in the stable transformation of plasmids into *Escherichia coli*, and the cleavage of plasmid factors and subsequent connection with DNA fragments through restriction endonuclease (EcoRI) [6]. These advancements led to the development of new high-copy-number vectors, most importantly the pUC and pBR families in *E. coli* [7], paving the way for the beginning of *in vitro* recombinant DNA technology in the following years [2].

After successfully cutting a plasmid, inserting a foreign gene, re-closing the plasmid, and transferring it into bacteria, this method was used to transfer a frog gene into bacteria [8]. This process was officially patented [9] by S. Cohen and H. Boyer on December 2, 1980, marking a significant contribution to the biotechnology industry [10].

1.1.2 Characteristics

Plasmids are typically circular molecules that occur naturally in bacterial cells, as well as in some eukaryotes and archaea. They are composed of double-stranded DNA, and their size can range from below 10 kilobase (kb) to over 400 kb. The DNA present in plasmids is extrachromosomal, meaning it is distinct from the DNA in the chromosomes of the organism [11]. Combined with the ability for autonomous replication, plasmids can provide organisms with several genetic advantages, such as antibiotic resistance, virulence, and enhanced metabolic capacities [12].

One way in which some organisms can pass on the advantages encoded in plasmids is through conjugation, the process by which conjugative plasmids are exchanged between cells. This is particularly advantageous for survival when it comes to transferring antibiotic resistance genes between bacteria. During the conjugation process, a donor organism transfers the plasmid unidirectionally to a recipient organism, and this transfer can occur even between different strains of bacteria [11]. Horizontal Gene Transfer (HGT), or lateral gene transfer, is the process by which genetic material is exchanged between strains. This contrasts with Vertical Gene Transfer (VGT), where DNA is transferred from parent to progeny through reproduction [13]. Conjugation is one of the three main pathways for HGT, the other two being bacterial transformation and transduction. Conjugation is the only one requiring cell-to-cell contact [14]. In transformation, bacteria take up DNA from the environment, while in transduction, a phage vector is used to transfer DNA between cells [11].

The biological importance of plasmids as carriers of exogenous DNA also translates into significant biotechnological relevance. This makes plasmid vectors a highly valuable tool for the delivery of therapeutic and prophylactic transgenes aimed at disease management and control [15].

Regardless of their intended application, most plasmid vectors have a fixed structure, containing an Origin of Replication (OR), a selection marker, and a cloning site. The OR has a length of approximately 1000 base pairs (bp), and is where DNA replication is initiated, and the number of copies in cells is maximised. The selection marker is an antibiotic-resistance gene that ensures the selection of the plasmid-carrying clones by exposing them to a medium containing the corresponding antibiotic. Finally, the cloning site is where the restriction enzyme cleavage occurs, and where exogenous DNA is inserted [16].

1.1.3 Applications

Plasmids can serve several purposes as biopharmaceuticals. They can be used directly by being injected into patients, or indirectly by being used as a starting or raw material to produce other biomolecules (summarised in Figure 1.1) [17]. These applications rely on the expression of a transgene, encoded in the plasmid, which is designed to target a specific condition or disease [15].

Figure 1.1: Applications of plasmid DNA in the context of gene and cell therapies [18].

When used directly as a biological drug ([A] in Figure 1.1), pDNA delivers therapeutic molecules or antigens to target cells by encoding them within its genetic sequence. It also provides DNA templates for the transcription of Ribonucleic acid (RNA) molecules within the cell [18]. This can boost the expression of proteins already present in the body, particularly if they play a role in the organism's response to a specific disease. Boosting can also be applied in cases where the protein is systematically produced in a defective manner due to a hereditary defect in the corresponding gene (e.g., cystic fibrosis, hemophilia), or when the protein is rapidly degraded (e.g., growth factors) [15]. Plasmids can also deliver gene editing machinery, namely DNA sequences from Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats (CRISPR) [19].

Plasmids are often encapsulated in lipid-based delivery vehicles (e.g., liposomes or lipid nanoparticles), to form stable complexes that can be administered to the patients [18]. *In vivo* gene therapies or gene editing use pDNA directly, as do DNA vaccines, which stimulate the immune system by transferring a gene. This can serve both prophylactic purposes, preventing episodes of the disease in question [15], and therapeutic purposes, such as directing the immune system to combat cancer or other diseases [20]. Additionally, plasmids can also carry genes that aid in the destruction of malignant cells by producing proteins that stimulate or enhance the immune responses against tumours. They can also suppress the expression of target genes related to a disease by coding for short hairpin RNA (shRNA) molecules [15].

Plasmids can also be used as indirect starting materials for complex bioproduct manufacturing and cell engineering processes ([B] in Figure 1.1). This is the case when plasmid vectors are used to alter patient/donor cells *ex vivo* [18] ([Bi] in Figure 1.1), for example in Chimeric Antigen Receptor-T (CAR-T) cell [21] or mesenchymal stem cell [22] therapies, as well as in genome editing [19]. Plasmids are also used in the manufacturing of messenger RNA (mRNA) and viral vectors, which are used in numerous therapies ([Bii] in Figure 1.1) [18]. mRNA vaccines have recently emerged as a new technology using plasmids as a template for the manufacturing platform of mRNA by *in vitro* Transcription (IVT) [23]. These products can also be used in *ex vivo* cell and gene editing [18] ([C] in Figure 1.1).

All direct uses of pDNA require full compliance with Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP), since the plasmid will be delivered to patients, subjecting them to any possible contamination. However, when plasmids are used indirectly, for example, to modify cells to produce therapeutic biomolecules, only the biomolecules themselves must be produced under GMP conditions [18]. Nonetheless, the plasmids must still adhere to rigorous quality and process regulations and verification protocols [17].

1.1.4 Production and purification

The manufacturing of pDNA starts with the selection of an *E. coli* strain capable of overcoming the typical challenges associated with upstream and downstream processing. The chosen strain must also ensure high plasmid quantity and quality, which is achieved by maximising plasmid volumetric and specific productivity, minimising insertion sequences and deletions, and promoting the prevalence of supercoiled pDNA [24].

Several strategies can be employed to achieve this, namely rational strain engineering and the intentional manipulation of operational parameters, such as cultivation strategy, Carbon Source (CS) concentration, bioreactor settings, and growth medium composition [15]. However, significant challenges still hinder the scale-up of plasmid DNA production, particularly due to the difficulty in meeting GMP production standards, which in turn delay regulatory approval [23].

Medium design optimisation can be a complex task, particularly when working with chemically defined media, but it offers significant long-term advantages, particularly when combined with statistical analysis tools [25]. Chemically defined media eliminate possible uncertainties and variability associated with the components of raw complex media and enable better positioning towards regulatory agents with respect to safety and reproducibility [26].

The pre-culture inoculated into the bioreactor of choice is prepared from a cell bank, which is established by transformation of the host cells with the plasmid DNA, followed by rigorous verification and characterisation [17]. The culture is grown through fermentation, after which the cells are harvested and lysed. Downstream processing then involves several purification steps, primarily chromatography, to ensure that the final product meets the required safety and quality standards [15]. The bulk pDNA is

then formulated by combining it with the proper excipients, bringing all components to their final concentrations. Figure 1.2 represents an overview of this process [27].

Figure 1.2: Schematic of the main operations for pDNA manufacturing [27].

Various fermentations modes, namely batch fermentation [28] [29], fed-batch fermentation [30] [31] and continuous fermentation [32], can be used to support cell growth. Batch fermentation is the most straightforward and widely used. In this mode, all nutrients are supplied at the beginning of the culture, and no further additions are made during growth. While simple to operate, batch processes often result in lower biomass and plasmid yields due to nutrient depletion and by-product accumulation [28] [29]. Moreover, batch fermentation conditions can vary significantly depending on the scale and equipment used, particularly between shake flasks and bioreactors [24].

Fed-batch fermentation, by contrast, allows for the controlled addition of nutrients throughout the culture, enabling extended growth phases and higher cell densities. This results in significantly improved volumetric and specific plasmid yields. Different feeding strategies are available, such as exponential feeding [33] [34] or constant feeding [35].

Continuous fermentation, in which fresh medium is continuously added while culture broth is simultaneously removed to maintain steady-state conditions, has also been explored for plasmid production [32]. However, its use remains limited due to concerns related to genetic stability, process complexity, and scale-up challenges.

An alternative method to conventional batch mode, also used in plasmid production, is high-cell density cultivation, which can be implemented in both batch and fed-batch formats. This approach involves optimising growth conditions (i.e., nutrient feeding, oxygen supply, and pH control) to achieve extremely high biomass concentrations. This approach enhances plasmid yield and improves the overall productivity of the bioprocess [36]. It is important to note that high-cell-density cultivation is not a fermentation mode per se, but rather a process intensification strategy that can be applied across different modes to enhance performance.

After cultivation, the cells are typically harvested through Tangential Flow Filtration (TFF) or centrifugation and then lysed. Cell debris are then separated using, again, TFF or centrifugation, followed by precipitation and one or more adsorption steps. Before the final product is sterile filtered, another TFF, or alternately an alcohol-based precipitation, is performed for buffer exchange and concentration. Although these purification steps may vary or be adapted, they are largely applicable for large-scale purification

of pDNA. Nevertheless, scale-up introduces challenges, mostly derived from inconsistent mixing, membrane fouling and constraints related to equipment design and cleaning [25]. Flocculation-related issues can also arise in large-scale processes, such as reduced product yield due to flocculant agents used during cell harvest, or floc breakdown caused by shear stress, which lowers the recovery efficiency of flocculant precipitates [37].

At small scales (e.g., shake flasks, small bench-top bioreactors), the production and purification process is considered to be relatively stable and accessible. However, such small-scale setups cannot meet the demands for the large quantities of pDNA for effective large-scale vaccination [25]. Furthermore, the limited number of manufacturers capable of producing and purifying pDNA under GMP conditions has led to production bottlenecks and delays in Research and Development (R&D) timelines [23].

The main bottleneck to the implementation of large-scale manufacturing and therefore full exploration of the potential of pDNA lies in scaling-up issues, at both production and purification stages. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated efforts to overcome these challenges to support vaccine development, leading to significant progress in the field [23]. Despite this, many issues remain with the scaling up and optimisation of the plasmid manufacturing process [38] [39].

1.1.5 Market analysis

The global market size for pDNA manufacturing stood at around 2.13 billion United States Dollars (USD) in 2024. The projected Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) value between the years 2025 and 2030 corresponds to 21.44%, with the market size expected to reach 6.70 billion USD in 2030 [40]. Additionally, this value is expected to further increase to 11.33 billion USD by 2034 [41].

The majority of market share was held by the North American region at around 44%, followed by Europe at 27% and the Pacific Asian region at 22% [41]. The North America's dominance of the market is explained by the presence of significant players in the biopharmaceutical industry and higher levels of infrastructure development, disposable income, and consumer awareness of gene-based therapies. The manufacturing market for pDNA in the Asia Pacific region is the fastest-growing, with a CAGR value of 22.99% between 2025 and 2030. This will result from economic development, an upgraded healthcare structure, and the exploration of formerly untapped opportunities, facilitated by government incentives and private investment [40].

The increase in reliable and approved pDNA products in the context of cell and gene therapies has led to increased investment and funding, particularly in the GMP-grade sector, which held 84.29% of the 2024 market share, with the remaining part deriving from R&D-grade. These factors also lead to cell and gene therapies holding over half of the market share by application (54.4%). Other main contributors to the GMP sector growth are the strict regulations surrounding manufacturing, the growth of the usage of therapeutic modalities of an advanced grade (e.g., therapies based on CAR-T cells [21]), and the

rise of outsourcing practices to facilities specialized in GMP-grade production by biopharmaceutical companies [40].

The increasing number of new cancer cases every year [42] and the success of some gene therapies, particularly those based on vaccination, against different cancer types [20] explain the dominance of cancer segment over the pDNA manufacturing market in 2024, with a 40% share, closely followed by infectious diseases and then genetic disorders [40].

Overall, the global demand for pDNA manufacturing is driven by an increased demand for cell and gene therapies, leading to higher investment in technology and infrastructure. However, this is hindered by scalability issues, as maintaining consistent quality and purity of the product remains a significant challenge and decreases the cost-effectiveness of the production process. Additionally, the strict regulations that these products are subjected to imply detailed research and proof of the safety and benefits of the therapeutic. Nevertheless, increasing collaboration between biopharmaceutical companies aiming to bring new products into the market and academic institutions seeking to advance scientific knowledge could help to overcome these challenges while simultaneously encouraging the discovery of therapeutic applications for pDNA [41].

1.2 Plasmid Manufacturing

1.2.1 *E. coli* as host

Escherichia coli is the host of choice for plasmid manufacturing, although the specific strain utilised can vary greatly depending on the growth conditions. The strains DH5 α , BL21, and JM101 are often employed for pDNA production, even though they were initially engineered for recombinant protein production. Due to their highly mutagenic genetic background and the strict nature of pDNA production, wild-type strains are often used as a starting point and then genetically engineered to enhance plasmid yields and cell densities [27].

Among commonly used strains for plasmid production, DH5 α is particularly reliable, as it is known to deliver reproducible results [26]. This strain can be used in various fermentation strategies with positive and stable outcomes, making it also useful as a comparison strain when testing engineered ones [24].

Another frequent strain employed in pDNA production is the *E. coli* K-12 MG1655 [43]. This strain can be engineered through gene knockouts, most frequently on the *endA* and *recA* gene (MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$), allowing for a higher structural stability [26], and a reduction in non-specific pDNA recombination and digestion when compared to the wild-type strain [27].

The strain GALG20 can be constructed from the engineered strain MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$, by adding an additional knockout on the *pgi* gene [44]. This knockout redirects the flux of carbon towards the pentose phosphate pathway, increasing nucleotide production. This occurs because the gene encodes

a phosphoglucose isomerase, which catalyses the conversion of glucose-6-phosphate to fructose-6-phosphate. In the absence of this enzyme, glucose-6-phosphate is instead channelled into the pentose phosphate pathway, enhancing the synthesis of nucleotides that are subsequently incorporated into the pDNA molecule [27].

Furthermore, this strain is also better equipped to overcome the effects of acetate inhibition on biomass growth [24], a well-documented phenomenon that often poses a challenge in plasmid production [45]. In aerobic conditions, high concentrations of the CS are responsible for the production of acetate by inhibiting respiration [27]. This process occurs as a result of an uptake of carbon greater than a critical limit, resulting in a metabolic overflow [26]. Acetate accumulates in the medium, causing acidification, as it is typically only consumed once other CSs (such as glucose and glycerol) have been depleted. Knocking out the *pgi* gene reduces the flux of carbon towards glycolysis and the tri-carboxylic acid cycle [46], the main processes responsible for acetate production, thus leading to lower accumulation of acetate by GALG20 [24].

The performance of a strain in a given growth medium is greatly affected by the selected fermentation method. Shake flask cultures can be useful for strain screening and evaluating genetically modified strains, but they are typically poor predictors of strain behaviour at larger scales [26]. Batch fermentation generally results in lower biomass and plasmid yields than fed-batch fermentation. Additionally, the use of rich media accelerates bacterial growth, which can exceed the bioreactor's oxygen transfer rate and lead to oxygen-limited conditions. When the oxygen demand surpasses the bioreactor's capacity to supply it, cells shift to anaerobic metabolism, resulting in the accumulation of inhibitory by-products, such as acetate. In fed-batch mode, nutrient availability is more tightly controlled, helping to regulate growth rates and minimise acetate accumulation, thereby improving the overall culture performance [25].

Both glycerol and glucose are commonly used as CSs in plasmid production. Glycerol is associated with lower rates of both acetate production and specific growth in *E. coli*, as well as higher plasmid yields on biomass, while the opposite is observed using glucose [26]. This issue can be addressed by, for example, engineering strains for optimal glucose uptake (and minimal acetate production), as in the case with GALG20 [44], or by using both CSs during fermentation [26].

1.2.2 Influence of Strain and Culture Conditions on pDNA Production

The following subsections are dedicated to the comparison of reported results for the three strains of interest: DH5 α , MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$, and GALG20 under different conditions.

In Table 1.1 the main results addressed are summarized and organized according to operation mode (Shake flask, Batch, and Fed-batch), strain (DH5 α , MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ (MG1655), and GALG20), and carbon source (Glucose (Glu) and/or Glycerol (Gly)), followed by the maximum values obtained for biomass and plasmid yields, as well as the amount of acetate accumulated at the end of the experiment.

Table 1.1: Summary of reported results for pDNA production using *E. coli* across different operation modes, strains, and carbon sources.

Operation mode	Strain	Carbon source (g/L)	Biomass (g/L)	Plasmid (mg/L)	Plasmid (mg/gDCW)	Acetate (g/L)	Ref.
Shake Flask	GALG20	20 (Glu)	10.9	140.8	19.1	0	[44]
				90.1	10.3	0	[24]
		20 (Gly)	8.5			0	[44]
	MG1655	20 (Glu)	3.5	1.5	0.8	5.74	[44]
				8.8	2.9	3.1	[24]
		20 (Gly)	7.7	79.3	11.5	3.86	[44]
	DH5 α	20 (Glu)	3.8	1.3	0.8	4.72	[44]
				8.2	2.4	2.2	[24]
		20 (Gly)	11.3	34.7	4.4	0.05	[44]
Batch bioreactor	GALG20	20 (Glu)	27.2	108	4.0	0	[47]
				87.3	8.2	0	[24]
	MG1655	20 (Glu)	32.7	116	3.5	0	[47]
				94.9	8.1	0	[24]
	DH5 α	6.0 (Glu)	6.7	14	2.1		[28]
		7.0 (Glu)	5.6	14	1.8	0	[48]
		20 (Glu)		72.2	8.0	3.9	[24]
		4.1 (Glu) and 5.4 (Gly)	9.4	51	5.4		[28]
		6.8 (Glu) and 5.4 (Gly)	12.8	95	7.4		[28]
		8.8 (Glu) and 3.9 (Gly)	10.3	11	1.1		[28]
		8.0 (Glu) and 6 (Gly)	9.4	42	7.2	5.4	[48]
		5.1 (Gly)	8.2	32	3.9		[28]
		6.0 (Gly)	5.3	28	5.3	0	[47]
7.0 (Gly)	5.9	34	4.8	0	[48]		
Fed-Batch	GALG20	20 (Glu) + 175 (Glu)	$\sim 10^*$	140.6	9.8	~ 7	[24]
		10 (Glu) + 500 (Glu)	$\sim 40^*$	1479	$\sim 6^*$	< 1.5	[24]
		6 (Gly) + 600 (Gly)	$\sim 48^*$	2177	$\sim 8^*$	< 1.5	[24]
	MG1655	20 (Glu) + 175 (Glu)	$\sim 10^*$	48.2	7.2	~ 15	[24]
		10 (Gly) + 600 (Gly)	$\sim 52^*$	2123	$\sim 6^*$	< 1.5	[24]
	DH5 α	6 (Glu) + 150 (Glu)	8.6	66	7.7	~ 10	[47]
		7 (Glu) + 150 (Glu)	8.6	66	8.7	~ 4	[48]
		20 (Glu) + 175 (Glu)	$\sim 14^*$	40.1	4.3	~ 16	[24]
		5 (Glu) and 6 (Gly) + 150 (Glu)	13	142	10.9	~ 20	[47]
		8 (Glu) and 6 (Gly) + 150 (Glu)	12.1	142	12.4	~ 8	[48]
	80 (Gly) + Gly	35.2^*	2200	$\sim 10^*$	~ 30	[49]	

* Values converted from OD₆₀₀ to g using OD₆₀₀ = 0.4g [24].

1.2.2.1 Shake flask

As summarised in Table 1.1, the *E. coli* strains DH5 α and MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ behave similarly regarding plasmid yields under shake flask cultures with complex medium containing 20g/L of glucose [44] [24]. Although the results differed slightly, partially due to the differences in culture volume (50 mL [44] and 100 mL [24]), both studies showed that MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ had a slightly larger volumetric yield, but also accumulated more acetate when compared to DH5 α . On the other hand, the GALG20 strain exhibited a plasmid volumetric yield approximately ten times higher ($\sim 90\text{-}140\text{ mg/L}$), and showed no detectable acetate accumulation. Additionally, the biomass produced and the specific yield were similar between DH5 α and MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$. GALG20 reached values over three times higher for biomass ($\sim 11\text{ g/L}$ [44]) and specific yield ($\sim 10\text{-}19\text{ mg/gDryCellWeight(DCW)}$), compared to the previous strains.

Differences in biomass and acetate accumulation between GALG20 and MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ were also analysed by Prazeres et al. (2016) [27], using shake flask culture (50 mL of medium) containing 20 g/L of glucose. It was observed that the pH dropped significantly more for MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ than for GALG20, despite similar Optical density (OD) values. GALG20 also achieved a final OD ($\sim 12\text{ mg/L}$) approximately three times higher than that of MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$, likely due to a reduced acetate inhibition.

These studies highlighted the beneficial effects of the *pgi* gene knockout present in the GALG20 strain, which allowed for significantly higher plasmid yields and lower production and accumulation of plasmid [44] [24] [27].

Additional studies by Gonçalves et al. (2013) [44] using shake flasks with 20 g/L of glycerol showed that GALG20 continued to outperformed MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ in terms of biomass production, but DH5 α achieved the highest biomass concentration ($\sim 11\text{ g/L}$), showcasing its increased suitability for glycerol-based cultivations. These studies also compared acetate accumulation according to the CS used. It was observed that all strains accumulated more acetate in glucose-containing medium, with MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ showing the highest amounts in both glucose ($\sim 5.7\text{ g/L}$) and glycerol ($\sim 3.9\text{ g/L}$) mediums. Notably, GALG20 showed no detectable levels of acetate after 24 hours [44].

Gonçalves et al. (2013) [44] also studied the growth rates under the different CSs. GALG20 and MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ showed lower growth rates in glycerol (0.49 and 0.60 h^{-1} , respectively) than in glucose (0.77 and 0.65 h^{-1} , respectively), whereas for DH5 α the opposite was reported (0.55 h^{-1} in glycerol and 0.49 h^{-1} in glucose).

It is worth noting that the studies by Gonçalves et al. (2013) [44], Gonçalves et al. (2014) [24], and Prazeres et al. (2016) [27] consistently used strains producing the pVAX1GFP plasmid.

1.2.2.2 Batch bioreactors

The best performers in shake flask conditions were typically not the best in batch bioreactor conditions, as observed by Gonçalves et al. (2014) [24] and Lopes et al. (2015) [47] (Table 1.1). Both used glucose at 20 g/L, with the first studying GALG20, MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$, and DH5 α and the second only GALG20 and MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$.

Consistent with shake flask results, GALG20 outperformed MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ in batch operation in terms of volumetric plasmid yield (~ 95 - 116 mg/L for GALG20 and ~ 87 - 108 mg/L for MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$) [24] [47]. The same consistency was not verified for the specific yields, where the studies obtained opposite results, with one of the strains having double the specific yield of the other. The results by Gonçalves et al. (2014) [24] showed that DH5 α obtained the lowest volumetric yield, but a similar specific yield to GALG20 (~ 8.0 mg/gDCW) [24]. According to Lopes et al. (2015) [47], GALG20 produced slightly more biomass (~ 33 g/L) than MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$. Regarding acetate production, while neither of the previous strains accumulated acetate, DH5 α accumulated almost 4 g/L by the end of the experiment [24].

Several studies addressed the effects of using unique or mixtures of glycerol and glucose at different concentrations in batch mode, typically only using common laboratory strains, such as DH5 α [28] [26]. As previously established, this strain behaves differently than GALG20 and MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ in glycerol compared to glucose in shake flask conditions [44], so a similar disparity is expected in batch bioreactors conditions. Nevertheless, these results can provide important insights into the effect of the CS on the cultures.

Scholz et al. (2012) [28] and Lopes et al. (2014) [26] report the same data [28], obtained by cultivating DH5 α using glucose, glycerol, or both. The results showed that DH5 α produced twice as much plasmid when grown in glycerol (32 g/L) compared to glucose, but the opposite was observed for the specific yield, which was higher in glucose. The highest specific and volumetric yield (7.4 mg/gDCW and 95 g/L, respectively) were obtained in a mixed CS culture containing the highest glucose concentration and lowest glycerol concentration among the tested mixed. This condition also yielded the highest amount of biomass (~ 13 g/L), while in single CS cultures, glycerol led to a higher production of biomass [28].

Similarly, Sales et al. (2015) [48] also observed higher volumetric yields in glycerol, but higher specific yields in glucose. A slightly lower biomass concentration was also reported in glucose. Additionally, the mixed culture also produced the highest biomass (9.4 g/L) and plasmid levels (42 g/L and 7.2 mg/gDCW), while simultaneously accumulating the highest amount of acetate [48].

In all experiments discussed, the bioreactor used held a working volume between 1.1 and 1.8 L. In addition to the previously mentioned conditions, Scholz et al. (2012) [28] and Sales et al. (2015) [48] conducted their experiments using the pVAX-LacZ plasmid. Lopes et al. (2015) [47] used the pVAX-LacZ plasmid for DH5 α and the pVAX1GFP plasmid for GALG20 and MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$.

1.2.2.3 Fed-batch

Fed-batch fermentation offers multiple variations according to the feeding strategy, and can additionally involve temperature shift strategies designed to maximise volumetric plasmid yield in high-cell-density cultures [24].

Gonçalves et al. (2014) [24] studied the effect of glucose in batch mode (mentioned previously) and fed-batch conditions, comparing GALG20 with MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ and DH5 α . GALG20 was initially tested under fed-batch conditions, starting with an initial batch phase using 20 g/L of glucose. followed by exponential feeding of glucose solution of different concentrations. A temperature shift was applied at 24 hours (from 30 °C to

42

°C). It was observed that biomass accumulation occurred primarily during the batch phase, while pDNA production occurred mostly after the temperature shift. The actual growth rate was lower than the set one, likely due to carbon flux being redirected towards plasmid production rather than biomass formation. The feeding strategy utilising less glucose (175 g/L) was selected as it produced similar amounts of plasmid (140 mg/L) and biomass (~10 g/L), while accumulating significantly less acetate and glucose [24].

This optimised strategy was then applied to the other two strains, MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ and DH5 α . Similarly to shake flask conditions, GALG20 produced nearly three times more pDNA than MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ and DH5 α , which performed similarly. GALG20 also achieved the highest specific yields (9.8 mg/gDCW), followed by MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ and DH5 α . Acetate accumulation was less pronounced in GALG20, with the other two strains accumulating more than twice the amount of acetate [24].

Additional studies by Sales et al. (2015) [48] and Lopes et al. (2015) [47] examined DH5 α under fed-batch conditions, beginning with a batch phase containing either glucose or a mixture of glucose and glycerol. In these studies, the single CS culture yielded lower biomass and plasmid levels, but also accumulated lower amounts of acetate. In contrast, mixed-carbon-source cultures produced significantly higher volumetric (~140mg/L) and specific (~11-12mg/gDCW) yields, in accordance with batch cultivation, demonstrating again the potential of using mixed CS cultures.

Gonçalves et al. (2014) further explored scale-up by evaluating GALG20 and MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ in a 6L batch mode followed by fed-batch mode until 14 L, using glucose as a CS and a temperature shift. GALG20 was also tested using glycerol in fed-batch [24]. Using glycerol, GALG20 and MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ reached similar volumetric plasmid yields (2177mg/L and 2123mg/L, respectively) with minimal acetate accumulation (less than 1.5 g/L) and high biomass levels (~50 g/L [24]. Under similar conditions, Carnes et al. (2011) [49] obtained a higher plasmid yield (2200mg/L) with DH5 α , but accumulated about 30 g/L of acetate and produced less biomass [49].

By contrast, under glucose-feeding conditions at large scale, GALG20 yielded less plasmid (1479mg/L) but also accumulated reduced amounts of acetate [24]. Other studies also report the inability of glucose cultures to produce high plasmid yields in larger scales [31].

These experiments demonstrate that even when applying similar strategies to the same strains, the outcomes can vary significantly across different production scales. This highlights the critical importance of developing robust and predictable scale-up methodologies tailored to specific strain and process characteristics.

1.3 Modelling Approaches

1.3.1 Digital Twins in biotechnology

The concept of a Digital Twin (DT) was presented first in 2003 by M. Grieves [50], who described it as a virtual and digital analogue to a physical product, connected through a continuous flow of information and data. Despite being the first formal definition of a DT, the concept had already been applied decades earlier, with one of the earliest and most significant applications occurring during the Apollo 13 mission in 1970, when an oxygen tank of an aircraft exploded, causing the main engine to sustain damage [51]. The engineers used simulators and twin models of the command module and electrical system to provide the appropriate guidance, leading to the safe landing on the South Pacific Ocean of the three astronauts on board, Fred Haise, James Lovell and John Swigert (Figure 1.3) [52].

Figure 1.3: Apollo 13 crew after landing (left to right): Fred Haise, James Lovell and John Swigert (17.04.1970) [53].

The study and implementation of DT has been growing exponentially, facilitated by the increasing evolution of infrastructure and software that allow for real-time data collection and analysis. In academic settings, this growth can be observed by the number of publications related to Digital Twins [54]. On the Scopus database, the number of publications that mentioned DT in the title, abstract, or keywords was just 136 in 2016, and grew to 1978 in just 4 years, in 2020. In 2024, about 10200 publications related to DT were made on the platform [55].

DT technology can bring enormous value to any sector to which it is applied, allowing companies to increase their competitiveness by becoming more productive and effective [54]. In 2024, it was estimated that over 60% of companies planned to incorporate some form of DT technology by 2029 [56]. This also translates to an increased market size, from 24.97 billion USD in 2024 to a prospective 155.84 billion USD in 2030, with a CAGR of 35.7% over this period. Regarding end-use applications, the automotive and transport sector was responsible for about 21.0% of the revenue share in 2023, followed by the manufacturing sector, and the aerospace sector [57].

The foundations of a DT are data acquisition, storage, processing, and representation, each of these relying on different technologies to perform their tasks. Data collection and transmission are assured through the Internet of Things (IoT), a framework in which e objects and technologies are connected and share information, being therefore the primary technology of any DT [58]. The storage and access of the data obtained can be done by Cloud computing, circumventing issues related to computing and storing large amounts of data, and allowing remote access to data by virtual Cloud storage [59]. The analytical, predictive, or automatic components of a DT can be provided through the employment of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and its many tools, such as Neural Network (NN) and Machine Learning (ML). This allows not only for the processing of data and the extraction of desired insights but also for outcome prediction and the generation of suggestions [60]. Finally, to connect the virtual and physical spaces and permit user interaction with the digital model, Extended Reality (XR) can be used. This area includes several immersive technologies, such as augmented, mixed, and virtual reality [59].

A Digital Model (DM) corresponds to a digital version of a physical object with no automatic data exchange, while a Digital Shadow (DS) corresponds to a digital version with a unidirectional flow of information from the physical to digital object. Unlike a DT, these models do not have an integrated data flow between the physical and virtual space (Figure 1.4). In a DT, changes in physical product lead to changes in the virtual model, and vice-versa, achieving full integration in both directions [61]. Compositing the types of models in terms of levels of integration, a DM has the lowest level while a DT has the highest level of integration [62].

Figure 1.4: Data flow between Digital Model, Digital Shadow and Digital Twin (adapted from Fuller et al. (2020) [61]).

DTs can be applied to several sectors, particularly in the context of Industry 4.0, by increasing the complexity and independence of industrial systems, which form intricate networks with different virtual and physical objects [54]. DT technologies are being developed and implemented in several sectors (Figure 1.5) such as automotive and transport, manufacturing, agriculture, healthcare, and retail [59].

Figure 1.5: Sectors of application of Digital Twin technology (adapted from Qi et al. (2021) [63]).

The biopharmaceutical manufacturing sector shares many of the applications, advantages, and challenges with the manufacturing and healthcare sectors. In the manufacturing sector, DTs can decrease costs by optimising process and product design, increasing supply chain management effectiveness [64], and changing maintenance from a reactive to predictive nature [65]. An important component of this, particularly in the manufacturing of biopharmaceuticals, is the implementation of Process Analytical Technologies (PAT), which corresponds to a system that ensures the quality of the products and the safety of the process through standardised design, analysis, and control [66]. The healthcare sector, like many others, underwent a rapid digitalisation process due to the COVID-19 pandemic. A digital transformation was particularly necessary in this sector to effectively manage the disease and its consequences effectively, namely supply chain issues [67]. When applied to healthcare, DTs can be used to replicate patients, healthcare facilities, and biomedical devices. This allows for personalised and predictive care to be provided more safely, faster, and more effectively for patients, as well as being less expensive for companies [59]. These models can also improve diagnosis capacity, preventive care, hospital resource management, and the education of healthcare professionals [61].

In bio-manufacturing, the expected advantages are an increase in quality and yield, and a decrease in costs and waste generated, as a result of the automation of systems and operations. Additionally, a

transparent and well-informed process can lead to increased flexibility and adaptability, while minimising the intervention required in the event of schedule or product variations [68]. Industry 4.0 aims to establish smart factories, in which the units within it exchange information and adapt accordingly, monitoring and controlling the process without the intervention of operators [69]. Dr. Joseph M. Juran [70] presented the concept of prioritising building quality into the product by using tools such as prior knowledge, quality risk management, PAT, mechanistic models, data analysis, collectively known as Quality by Design (QbD). Another important tool in QbD, which seeks to uncover the correlations between inputs and outputs by performing multiple experiments with planned input differences and assessing the interaction between variables, is called Design of Experiments (DoE). Ultimately, this allows for a systemic minimisation and maximisation of resources and information gain, respectively [71].

Although Industry 4.0 is under development in several industries, most of the biopharmaceutical industry largely fails to comply with Industry 3.0 standards, due to its continued reliance on manual systems. This occurs due to the complexity of the operation units, as well as the high cost of operation and difficulty in extracting and analysing the large collections of data required for process understanding [68]. Therefore, to achieve Industry 4.0, it is crucial to establish a solid base of process knowledge and model structure on which to build digitalisation and automation [69]. The implementation of digitalised monitoring and control approaches requires a comprehensive understanding of the process and its variability. In turn, this requires the existence of proper sensors and technologies that permit full control and monitoring of the Critical Process Parameters (CPPs) related to the bioproduct in question [68]. To this end, an emphasis on mathematical models that accurately reflect bioprocesses, combined with real-time monitoring and control, can play a crucial role in the integration of DT technology in the bio-manufacturing and (bio)pharmaceutical industry [72].

1.3.2 Mathematical models

To develop and characterise a process, it is necessary to understand it. This is done by uncovering relationships among CPPs and Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs). A key method to achieve this is mathematical modelling, accompanied by strategic experimentation and efficient data management and treatment [73].

Mathematical models can be mechanistic models, also known as knowledge-based models, data-driven statistical models, or a combination of the two, which are hybrid models. Mechanistic models are white-box models, meaning it is possible to understand how they work internally, and they rely on first principles derived from physical laws to describe the behaviour of the system mathematically. On the other hand, data-driven models are black-box models, named so because they lack transparency regarding the underlying mechanisms that govern them [74]. The coefficients in these models do not have biological meaning, aiming merely to reflect the relationships between the data through methods

like Multi-Linear Regression (MLR), NN, and deep learning [73].

Hybrid modelling combines the two previous types of model, incorporating both knowledge-based and data-based techniques. These models aim to explore the advantages of white and black box models and minimise their respective disadvantages [74].

Biological processes, due to their inherent complexity, are often unable to be described solely by mechanistic models, but statistical models lack interpretability and hinder process understanding. Hybrid models can overcome these issues by combining both approaches, particularly when physical models are unavailable or costly. This combined approach enables process understanding to be gained through deterministic mechanistic modelling, and more accurate predictability is achieved through statistical modelling [74].

1.3.3 Mechanistic models

1.3.3.1 Introduction

Mechanistic models can play an important role in the development and optimisation of bioprocesses. They are an essential tool in PAT-centred approaches, since they depict the intricacies of a process through mathematical and biological expressions [72].

In line with PAT guidelines, the biopharmaceutical industry has been shifting from a batch-to-batch consistency approach, relying on off-line samples, to on- or at-line monitoring and control approaches, ensuring consistent final product safety and quality requirements [72].

Particularly in cell cultivation at a large scale, mechanistic models are used in soft sensors, which allow for indirect monitoring of process variables in real-time, reducing the need for complex hardware. This can be integrated to also control process variables and adjust inputs to improve the outcomes of the process [73]. Additionally, *in silico* mechanistic models can aid in process design in terms of time and cost by assessing the behaviour of the process when variations are induced, increasing its safety without the need for physical testing [72].

Mechanistic approaches employed towards modelling metabolism and microbial growth can have two main methods: a kinetic approach, and a Constraint-Based Modelling (CBM) approach. These approaches reflect some of the mechanisms within the biological system and allow for the measurement or estimation of model parameters. However, kinetic models only translate underlying phenomena through the kinetic parameters and therefore require prior knowledge of the metabolic behaviour. On the other hand, CBM analyses the relationships between the phenotype, genotype, and environmental conditions [75].

1.3.3.2 Kinetic models

Kinetic models are deterministic by nature and disregard the stochastic nature that biological systems are subjected to [76]. They are developed by taking the mathematical expressions that describe biochemical reactions within a system and forming mass balance equations, and are also referred to as dynamic models [77].

Cell population kinetic models are classified based on assumptions about the reactor environment and how cell populations are described and characterised (summarised in Table 1.2). An initial distinction is whether the environment within the bioreactor can be considered homogeneous or not, in which case the model must be a distributed one and have space as an independent variable [72].

If the model assumes an average cell for biomass quantification, it does not consider cell heterogeneity and is considered an unsegregated model. Segregated models typically use population balance models to describe the differences between cells within a population [34], or use randomly generated parameters in a single-cell model to create a cell population, called cell ensemble models [78]. Biomass can also be represented as one variable, if the model is unstructured [79], or as a series of variables (biomass, precursors, ATP, metabolites) if the model is structured [80].

The models can be combined in different ways. For example, they can be unsegregated structured models, with multiple variables describing the biomass, but relying on an average description of a cell. Alternatively, they can be segregated but unstructured, in which case the biomass is described by a single but distributed variable, that considers cell-to-cell variability but not intracellular composition [72]. The characteristics of the different classes of cell population models are presented below, in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2: Classification of cell population models based on structure and segregation [72].

Model Type	Structure	Segregation	Definition	Ref.
Unstructured, Unsegregated	Single variable	Average cell description	Used for simple systems; Does not consider heterogeneity or internal structure of biomass.	[81]
Structured, Unsegregated	Multiple variables	Homogeneous population	Considers internal cell structure; Can model complex processes (intracellular metabolism).	[34]
Unstructured, Segregated	Single variable	Distributed biomass	Biomass is a single distributed component; Does not consider intracellular composition.	[80]
Structured, Segregated	Multiple variables	Distributed cells	Considers internal cell structure and population-wide variability; Computationally expensive but highly detailed.	[82]

Unsegregated unstructured models are the simplest ones, but they can be very useful towards process design, particularly in the study of growth kinetics [83]. They are typically based on rate expressions for nutrient uptake, cell growth, and metabolite production [84]. The balance between the objective of the model and its complexity is evaluated through a "fitness-for-purpose" criteria, allowing an appropriate model type to be selected [72].

1.3.3.3 Constraint-based models

Metabolic analysis and modelling of cellular behaviour form the foundation of CBM and has risen as an area of focus within biotechnology due to its potential for the engineering of customisable bioproducts and pharmaceuticals [85]. Biochemical reactions operate within a coordinated network of pathways, transforming substrates into metabolites at a quantifiable rate. The two main methods for quantifying these metabolic fluxes are Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) and Metabolic Flux Analysis (MFA) [75].

FBA is a genome-scale analysis that studies the metabolite flux. Through this approach, maximum theoretical yields of target metabolites can be estimated [86], as well as the prediction of biomass production rates [87] and medium optimisation [88] [89]. FBA models use a stoichiometric matrix to represent metabolic reactions and their corresponding coefficients, hence imposing flow constraints on the metabolic network. These constraints can either balance the reactions, imposing that the amount consumed and produced are equal, or input system bounds, establishing maximum and minimum values for the reaction fluxes [87].

In contrast, MFA uses experimentally derived metabolite mass balances to calculate intracellular fluxes and obtain an overview of the metabolic state of the cell under particular conditions [85]. Unlike FBA, MFA does not aim to optimise metabolic fluxes, but rather to study the influence of different conditions on those fluxes. It can be used to investigate the effect of pH [90] or temperature control strategy [91] to improve metabolite yield [75].

MFAs perform significantly better than FBAs, especially when applied to engineered strains [92], and are, therefore, more indicated for selecting strategies for metabolic engineering [93] [94]. However, because MFAs often make simplifications on the metabolic network, optimisation algorithms have been developed [95] [96], to augment their scope and to increase their accuracy [75].

To assess the impact of the dynamic nature of the external environment, as well as the relationship between physiological metabolic parameters and macro-state parameters, Dynamic Flux Variability Analysis (dFVA) was created [75]. This method can integrate macro kinetics, such as the Monod equation [97], and can be utilised in hybrid modelling through the use of ML [75]. Such hybrid modelling approaches can be promising for biological process modelling and will be part of future work.

1.3.3.4 Mechanistic modelling in plasmid production

There are several approaches to mechanistic models for pDNA production in *E. coli*, ranging from simple unsegregated kinetics to more complex structured and segregated frameworks.

Bohle and Ross [98] proposed a model linking the specific growth rate to increased plasmid production, identifying the specific plasmid production rate as a crucial parameter [98]. This work also utilised a defined medium for batch and fed-batch cultures with exponential feeding, which was later adopted in several publications, such as by Munguia-Soto et al. (2015) [34], García-Rendón et al. (2016) [99], and García-Rendón et al. (2019) [100].

These follow-up studies addressed plasmid production under Exponential-Fed Perfusion (EFP) cultures using DH5 α and plasmid pVAX1-NH36, with applications directed at a Leishmaniasis vaccine. They used the same segregated kinetic model developed by Munguia-Soto et al. (2015) [34]. The authors used glycerol as a main CS and employed flow cytometry to monitor *E. coli* cultures. The model was able to accurately predict cell growth and substrate consumption, providing insights on bioreactor cell dynamics and showcasing its potential for process prediction and control [34].

Building on these insights, García-Rendón et al. (2016) [99] used the model to simulate different operation parameters and determined that the initial cell and substrate concentration were the most influential. Later, García-Rendón et al. (2019) [100] investigated the impact of using glycerol or glucose in both batch and EFP fermentation. Higher productivities were observed in EFP than in batch mode, with glycerol yielding higher plasmid productivities. Given the elevated operation cost of glycerol compared to glucose, it was suggested that glycerol should be utilised during the batch phase of the process, and glucose during the EFP stage. These studies highlighted the potential of EFP cultures in plasmid production and demonstrated that the process can be flexible and cost-effective [99] [100].

In another approach, Lopes et al (2014) developed an unstructured and unsegregated kinetic model for batch cultures [26]. This model described plasmid production kinetics in the DH5 α strain under different media compositions, using either a single main CS, glycerol or glucose, or a mixture of the two. In contrast to the previous model, it also considered acetate as an additional CS available for biomass and plasmid production. Biomass growth rate was defined by Monod kinetics, incorporating all three substrates. The model was based on a system of Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs) translating mass balance equations and was subsequently simplified after a sensitivity analysis revealed that several inhibition-related parameters were negligible. The final model retained key parameters such as maximum specific growth rates on each CS, including acetate, biomass yields on glycerol and glucose, and plasmid yields on acetate and glycerol. These parameters were identified as primary contributors to the differences observed between cultures [26].

Grijalva-Hernández et al. (2018) [101] extended the kinetic model developed by Lopes et al (2014) [26] to build a state estimator with output feedback injector, using biomass concentration measurements

to estimate plasmid concentration. This approach allowed for accurate estimations and demonstrated the ability of this methodology for reliable online measurement of plasmid and possible application towards process control, coming at significantly lower cost than traditional methodologies [101].

More recently, advances in genome-scale metabolic modelling have been applied to plasmid production. Gotsmy et al. (2023) [88] applied a constraint-based modelling approach using a genome-scale metabolic model of *E. coli* to optimise fed-batch plasmid production. Using FBA and dynamic simulations, nutrient limitations capable of decoupling biomass from plasmid production were identified. Based on this, they proposed a novel three-stage fed-batch, containing an initial batch phase, followed by a growth phase fed-batch, and then a nutrient-starved production phase induced by sulfate limitation. Implementing this strategy in DH5 α cultures led to an increase in both specific and volumetric yields of supercoiled plasmid DNA, illustrating the potential of metabolic network models for bioprocess optimisation [88].

In summary, mechanistic modelling provides a powerful framework for understanding and predicting plasmid production in *E. coli*, and gain valuable insights on the biological dynamics that govern this process. Despite the limited number of mechanistic studies available, existing models have successfully contributed to rational process design, control, and scale-up strategies in plasmid DNA manufacturing.

1.3.4 Data and Model Analysis

Growth kinetics can be a useful tool in mechanistic models aimed at describing biological systems, but this can be hindered by the non-linear nature of their intrinsic mechanisms [102]. Even equations like the Monod expression are simplified approximations of complex biological processes, which rely on empirical data for parameter estimation rather than of capturing the underlying intricacies of the system in their entirety [72].

Identifying parameters experimentally can require laborious and specific laboratory work, and these parameters cannot always be identified [102]. Additionally, even with an optimised experimental design, the time-course datasets required are often deficient due to the high number of metabolites involved, time points needed, and unavoidable noise in the data [103]. Given this, developing and employing robust and accurate methods for parameter estimation for the effective development of models, particularly in the biotechnology industry, is extremely important [102]. Proper parameter estimation is crucial, as poor estimations lead to poor model performance during validation. The wide variability of model types and datasets results in an absence of fixed guidelines for model validation. As a result, establishing a detailed workflow that addresses this can be challenging [104].

Parameter estimation and model validation methods should be chosen according to several factors, such as model type and purpose, and the nature and size of the dataset used. Data is often used to fine-tune and validate kinetic models, typically by optimising methods that minimise errors between

the measured and simulated data to improve parameter estimation [105]. While data-driven models, which translate relationships between input and outputs, are validated through statistical methods such as variance analysis and cross validation, mechanistic models must evaluate both the structure of the model and the parameter values [106].

Overall, the analysis and validation of a mechanistic model generally follows this following schematic: formulation of the model; identifiability analysis; estimation of parameters and corresponding intervals of confidence; uncertainty analysis; and finally, global sensitivity analysis [107].

For a rigorous estimation, optimisation, and validation of model parameters, it is necessary to investigate their structural and practical identifiability [108]. Structural identifiability reflects the amount of information that can be extracted from a given experiment, in theory, considering the structure and studied outputs. On the other hand, practical identifiability relates to the conditions of the experiments, the structure of the model, and the quantity and quality of the data extracted [109]. An unidentifiable model is a model whose parameters cannot be uniquely determined from the data, due to a lack of information (structural unidentifiability) or highly noise-sensitive parameters (practical unidentifiability). Structural unidentifiability arises when there is insufficient information to constrain the parameters, leading to large variations, even without noise. On the other hand, practical unidentifiability results from significant variability in the parameters due to noise, which can be addressed by improving data precision or experimental control [110].

It is necessary to understand which parameters can be estimated, and in particular, which can be uniquely identified [111]. Parameter uniqueness is an essential component of practical identifiability, and it translates the capacity of the system to uniquely determine the value of a parameter through the formulation of the model [112]. Studying the uniqueness of parameters is typically done through correlation coefficients and sensitivity analysis [111].

Sensitivity analysis is used to assess the significance and non-identifiability of the parameters, which also aids in the experimental design process. It can be local, in which small perturbations are added to each variable and the effect it has on the output is measured, or global, in which the impact of parameter variations across their entire range on model output is studied [111].

Estimation involves obtaining parameter values that allow the model's predictions to best approximate the observed values for a given system, considering the structure of the model. This can be done through trial and error, which involves manually changing the values of one or more parameters to achieve a satisfying model fit. Although this method lacks objectivity and a scientific basis, a deficit in knowledge regarding statistical theory and contact with modelling software makes this a common approach within both industry and academic settings [111]. Proper statistical methods use frameworks such as minimisation of an objective function or sampling algorithms to achieve numerical solutions, and this objective, or *cost*, function measures the distance between a model and a data point [113].

1.4 Aim of the Study

Plasmids have great biological importance as genetic material carriers capable of autonomous replication [15]. They can be applied towards delivering therapeutics and prophylactic transgenes, gene editing machinery, and starting materials for the manufacturing of bioproducts [18].

Despite their potential in vaccines, gene therapies, and recombinant protein production, large-scale manufacturing of plasmids faces significant challenges, principally in scale-up and GMP standard compliance [23]. This is mainly due to the lack of reproducibility and intrinsic variability of the plasmid manufacturing process, a common issue in biologics manufacturing [74]. Adding to the scale-up issues, low yields and plasmid instability also increase the difficulty in large-scale plasmid manufacturing [114]. The selection of appropriate vectors and host strains can be facilitated using strain and genetic engineering, through which higher-yielding strains, such as the GALG20 strain, can be developed [44]. Even so, the unexplained lack of performance consistency across scales and high sensitivity to process variability jeopardise the scale-up process, highlighting the importance of process understanding [24].

For robust process and strain development, the relationships and interactions between parameters should be understood and studied through a DoE framework, essential for extracting the maximum amount of information while minimising resources spent [71]. Prioritising QbD, through the implementation of PAT tools and knowledge-based models, can strengthen process understanding and reduce the experimental workload. Digital tools such as soft sensors and real-time monitoring systems can support this effort by facilitating predictive modelling and control [68].

The study of strain performance towards maximum productivity, especially when followed by scale-up procedures, can require extensive experimentation [24], which might still be subjected to high process variability and low reproducibility. Mechanistic models can play an important role in tackling these challenges, as they allow the simulation of process dynamics under different conditions, generating process understanding and reducing trial-and-error experimentation [72]. Additionally, this facilitates the estimation of parameters and the analysis of input and output sensitivity, a crucial step in ensuring the validity and robustness of a model [105].

Considering this context, implementing and integrating modelling approaches in the early stages of process development can facilitate and improve experimental design and optimisation, ultimately aiming to streamline the scale-up process. This thesis aimed to implement a modelling framework designed for early-stage process development, capable of predicting the behaviour of different plasmid-producing *E. coli* strains. Additionally, the development of models from experimental data according to a rigorous framework of identifiability and sensitivity analysis sought to extract insights regarding the structure of the model and the biological interactions it aimed to simulate. Building on these insights, a comparison of the predictive capacity of the model was made using testing data from shake flask and batch fermentations,

to demonstrate the biological differences between these two.

The use of kinetic models to describe plasmid-producing cultures using *E. coli* has been documented under different conditions and to study different phenomena, such as the effect of using glucose or glycerol as a CS [26] [100] or the effect of operation parameters on outputs [99]. However, these studies were performed for DH5 α , which, although a very common laboratory strain and therefore used by many, often underperforms when compared to engineered strains like MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA or GALG20, particularly when using glucose as a CS [24]. Given this, glucose was used as a single main carbon source, and acetate as a secondary carbon source, and a kinetic model was selected from previous work [26] and adapted accordingly.

The model formulation aimed to describe the mass balances of the evolution of biomass, plasmid, glucose, and acetate over time, modelled through parameters related to Monod kinetics, yields of consumption and production, and inhibition constants. Although shake flask experiments can be very useful for strain screening during strain engineering studies, the results from this operation mode are typically not transferable to batch or fed-batch fermentations [24]. As the mass balances are formulated equally for shake flask and batch bioreactor experiments, these two fermentation systems were selected to be tested through the same model. The model aimed to describe multiple strains used in plasmid production, with the following strains selected for analysis: DH5 α (very commonly used), MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA (commonly used engineered strain), and GALG20 (novel strain engineered for glucose consumption) [44]. The parameters were estimated from separate batch-mode datasets, and these parameters were tested in bioreactor and shake flask conditions. To build a robust model and understand its strengths and limitations, a framework for the analysis of sensitivity and identifiability was implemented using Python and applied to each model.

While batch bioreactor data were obtained from previously available datasets, new shake flask experiments were conducted as a part of this work. These experiments used the same plasmid (pVAX1-GFP), initial glucose concentration, and the three strains of interest, DH5 α , MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA, and GALG20, with the pVAX1-GFP plasmid.

It is important to note that the original aim of this project entailed a different approach, namely to estimate parameters for both batch bioreactors and shake flask conditions, and then use only the batch bioreactor models for validation. However, due to insufficient data points in the shake flask experiments, parameter estimation for those conditions was not possible, and instead, shake flask data was directed towards testing the model, and the resulting predictions were compared to those obtained from batch bioreactor experiments.

2

Material and Methods

Contents

2.1	Experimental Data	29
2.2	Kinetic Model	31

2.1 Experimental Data

2.1.1 Host strains and plasmid

The strains used in the experiments described in the following sections are indicated in the table below (Table 2.1).

Table 2.1: Strains used and their respective genotypes.

Strain	Genotype	Reference
DH5 α	F- Φ 80 <i>lacZ</i> Δ M15 Δ (<i>lacZYA-argF</i>)U169 <i>recA1 endA1 hsdR17</i> (r_k^- , m_k^+) <i>phoA supE44 thi-1 gyrA96 relA1</i>	StrateGene
MG1655	F- λ - <i>ilvG-rfb-50 rph-1</i>	[44]
GALG20	MG1655 Δ <i>endA</i> Δ <i>recA</i> Δ <i>pgi</i> (F- λ - Δ G <i>rfb-50</i> Δ 1 Δ <i>endA</i> Δ <i>recA</i>)	[44]

The DH5 α strain was purchased from StrateGene, while the original MG1655 was given by the Prather Lab, MIT. The simple knockout (*endA*) was performed according to Gonçalves et al. (2013) [44], and the double knockout (*endArecA*) according to Datsenko et al. (2000) [115]. The GALG20 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* Δ *pgi* was obtained by adding another knockout(*pgi*) to the MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA*, as described in Gonçalves et al. (2013) [44]¹.

The plasmid used was the pVAXI-GFP (3697 bp), it was constructed according to the protocol described by Azzoni et al. (2007) [116]. It contained an antibiotic resistance marker for kanamycin². The sequence of this plasmid is presented in Appendix B.

2.1.2 Media composition and preparation

The inoculum and the production media were prepared based on the formulations described by Listner et al. (2006) [35]. Both media are composed of a basal media, a Seed supplement solution (SSS), and a Trace element solution (TES). These components were prepared in water, except for the trace element solution (TES), which was prepared in 1.2*N* HCL. The final concentration of each component is expressed in *g/L*.

The inoculum medium was prepared in basal medium with the following composition per liter of water: 7*g* of KH₂PO₄ (PanReac), 7*g* of K₂HPO₄ (PanReac), 6*g* of (NH₄)₂SO₄ (PanReac), 5*g* of monosodium glutamate, and 20*g* of glucose (Scharlau). The pH of the basal medium was adjusted to 7.2 using a 30% NaOH solution prior to sterilisation of the Basal media through filtration. After sterilisation, the SSS at 8.3 *mL/L* and the TES at 1 *mL/L* were added.

¹This procedure had been done before this work began.

²Same as footnote 1.

The SSS contained the following components per litre of water: 24g of thiamine-HCl, 240g of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and 0.64g of neomycin sulfate. The TES, prepared in 1.2N hydrochloric acid, contained per liter: 27g of $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2g of ZnCl_2 , 2g of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2g of $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1g of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1.3g of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and 0.5g of H_3BO_3 .

In the production medium, the SSS was replaced by the Production supplement solution (PSS), which contained 72g of thiamine-HCl and 240g of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ per litre of water. Additionally, for plasmid-producing cultures, the antibiotic kanamycin was added to the production medium at a final concentration of 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$.

2.1.3 Inoculum and cultivation

Cultures were grown in agar plates, with the strains that produce plasmid being grown with the addition of 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of kanamycin. From single colonies picked from these plates, seed banks were created using LB medium. After growing to mid-exponential phase at 250 *rpm* and 37 °C, seed stocks were created and stored at -80 °C in 15% (v/v in glycerol).

These seed stocks and the inoculum media were used to prepare the inoculum. The amount inoculated was calculated to achieve an initial OD of 0.1. The cultures were grown in shake flasks containing 30 *mL* of the production media at 250 *rpm* and 37 °C for 24 hours.

Glucose was used as the primary CS, used at an initial concentration of 20 *g/L*. Biomass and pH were measured hourly, while pDNA, acetate and glucose were measured at 5, 7, 9, and 24 hours. Additionally, glucose was measured at the beginning of the experiment.

2.1.4 Data collection and analysis

The OD measurement was performed by diluting the culture 1 : 10 in sterile water, to a final volume of 1000 μL . The OD was then measured at 600 *nm* using a spectrophotometer. For pH measurement, the pH was directly determined in the shake flask using a previously calibrated pH meter.

For pDNA purification and quantification, 1 *mL* of the culture was collected. Plasmid DNA was extracted using the High Pure Plasmid Purification Kit from Roche. Quantification was carried out using a Nanodrop Nanovue, specifically measuring the double-stranded DNA section.

Glucose and acetate quantification was performed by High-performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) using a Rezex ROA-Organic Acid H+ 8% column (300 *mm* × 7.8*mm*). The Hitachi LaChrom Elite device was used, which was equipped with an HPLC pump (Hitachi LaChrom Elite L-2130), an auto-sampler (Hitachi LaChrom Elite L-2200), and a column heater (Croco-CIL 100-040-220*P*, 40*cm*8*cm*8*cm*, 30–99° C), externally connected to the HPLC system. A Hitachi L-2490 Refractive Index (RI) detector was used for glucose quantification, while acetate was measured with a Hitachi L-2420 UV–Vis detector.

The HPLC analysis was carried out with an injection volume of 20 μL , using 5 mM H_2SO_4 as the eluent. The column was maintained at 65 $^\circ\text{C}$, and the pump operated at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min .

For sample preparation, the culture samples were centrifuged at 10000 g for 5 minutes at room temperature. From the supernatant, 550 μL was mixed with an equal volume (550 μL) of 50 mM H_2SO_4 . A second centrifugation was performed under the same conditions. Finally, 1 mL of the resulting supernatant was transferred into an HPLC vial for analysis.

2.2 Kinetic Model

2.2.1 Datasets

Parameter estimation was done using data from Lopes et al. (2015) [47] for MG1655 ΔendA ΔrecA and GALG20, and from Gonçalves et al. (2014) [24] for DH5 α . Additionally, batch bioreactors cultures with MG1655 ΔendA ΔrecA and GALG20 from Gonçalves et al. (2014) [24] were used to test the corresponding models. These test datasets do not aim to be a replicate of the estimation datasets, but can nevertheless provide some insights regarding the performance of the model. The data obtained from shake flask cultures for the three strains, DH5 α , MG1655 ΔendA ΔrecA (MG1655), and GALG20, was used for testing the model with the parameters obtained for batch bioreactors. The main characteristics of the datasets are summarised below, in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2: Summary of the datasets used in this work.

Strain	Mode	Nr. data points	Purpose	Ref.
DH5 α	Shake flask	12 [†]	Testing	This work
MG1655	Shake flask	12 [†]	Testing	This work
GALG20	Shake flask	12 [†]	Testing	This work
DH5 α	Batch bioreactor	5 [*]	Estimation	[24]
MG1655	Batch bioreactor	60	Estimation	[47]
GALG20	Batch bioreactor	60	Estimation	[47]
MG1655	Batch bioreactor	5 [*]	Testing	[24]
GALG20	Batch bioreactor	8 [*]	Testing	[24]

^{*} As explained in the previous section, glucose, acetate, and plasmid were not measured on all time points.

[†] Initial plasmid and/or acetate missing. For $t = 0$ in these datasets, acetate and plasmid were considered to be zero and $1E - 03$, respectively.

2.2.2 Model formulation

The model used was adapted from the reduced version of the kinetic model developed by Lopes et al. (2014) [26], also employed by Grijalva-Hernandez et al. (2018) [101]. In this adaptation, a single initial CS was considered (glucose), thereby excluding mechanisms related to glycerol metabolism originally present in the formulation of the reduced model.

The model described four variables: biomass concentration (g/L) (X), glucose concentration (g/L) (S), plasmid concentration (g/L) (P), and acetate concentration (g/L) (A); and is governed by nine kinetic parameters: maximum specific growth rate on glucose (h^{-1}) (μ_{maxS}), maximum specific growth rate on acetate (h^{-1}) (μ_{maxA}), biomass yield on glucose (g/g) ($Y_{X/S}$), biomass yield on acetate (g/g) ($Y_{X/A}$), plasmid yield on biomass growth on glucose (g/g) (Y_{P/X_S}), plasmid yield on biomass growth on acetate (g/g) (Y_{P/X_A}), acetate yield on glucose (g/g) ($Y_{P_A/S}$), affinity constant for glucose (g/L) (K_S), affinity constant for acetate (g/L) (K_A), and inhibition constant of biomass growth by acetate (g/L) (K_{iX-A}). These parameters regulate the system of ODEs used to translate the dynamics of pDNA production in *E. coli* fermentation.

The specific growth rates on glucose and acetate, denoted specific growth rate on glucose (h^{-1}) (μ_S) and specific growth rate on acetate (h^{-1}) (μ_A), respectively, follow the Monod kinetics equation [117] (Equation 2.1).

$$\mu_\alpha = \mu_{max\alpha} * \frac{[C_\alpha]}{(K_\alpha + [C_\alpha])} \quad (2.1)$$

The total growth rate, represented by total specific growth rate (h^{-1}) (μ_T), is defined as the sum of the individual substrate-specific rates (Equation 2.2).

$$\mu_T = \sum_{\alpha} \mu_\alpha \quad (2.2)$$

To account for the inhibition of biomass growth (K_{iX-A}) due to the presence of acetate, an inhibition factor (Equation 2.3) was added to μ_S and the μ_A .

$$\frac{K_{iX-A}}{K_{iX-A} + A} \quad (2.3)$$

The consumption rate of glucose and acetate (r_S and r_A) considered the respective growth rates (μ_S and the μ_A), as well as the $Y_{X/S}$ and the $Y_{X/A}$ (Equation 2.4).

$$r_\alpha = -\frac{\mu_\alpha}{Y_{x/\alpha}} * X \quad (2.4)$$

The production rate of plasmid (r_P) considered the different plasmid yields on glucose and acetate, Y_{P/X_S} and Y_{P/X_A} , and the respective growth rates of these CSs (Equation 2.5). Similarly, the production of acetate as a result of glucose metabolism (r_{PA}) was also taken into account, considering the $Y_{P_A/S}$ (Equation 2.6).

$$r_P = \sum_{\alpha} (Y_{P/X_\alpha} * \mu_\alpha) * X \quad (2.5)$$

$$r_{PA} = Y_{PA/S} * \mu_S * X \quad (2.6)$$

These parameters were used to construct a system of ODEs describing the use of acetate and glucose as CSs, whose growth rate followed the Monod equation and considered the inhibitory effect of biomass growth by acetate (Equations 2.7 and 2.8).

$$\mu_S = \mu_{maxS} * \frac{[C_S]}{(K_S + [C_S])} * \frac{K_{i_{X-A}}}{K_{i_{X-A}} + A} \quad (2.7)$$

$$\mu_A = \mu_{maxA} * \frac{[C_A]}{(K_A + [C_A])} * \frac{K_{i_{X-A}}}{K_{i_{X-A}} + A} \quad (2.8)$$

This originates into the final model used, composed of the following system of ODEs (Equation 2.9-2.12):

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = (\mu_S + \mu_A) * X \quad (2.9)$$

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = -r_S = -\frac{\mu_S}{Y_{X/S}} * X \quad (2.10)$$

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = -r_A + r_{PA} = \left(-\frac{\mu_A}{Y_{X/A}} + Y_{PA/S} * \mu_S\right) * X \quad (2.11)$$

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = r_P = (Y_{P/X_S} * \mu_S + Y_{P/X_A} * \mu_A) * X \quad (2.12)$$

2.2.3 Identifiability analysis

The subsequent parameter estimation, sensitivity and uncertainty analyses were based on the workflow described by Fernandes et al. (2013) [107] for systematic model analysis, implemented in Python.

For simulation and analysis purposes, the initial guess for the parameter values (nominal parameter values) was taken from the apparent or estimated values of these parameters, as described in the work from which the model was derived. Where available, the apparent values of the parameters under 6.0 g/L of glucose were used (marked with α in Table 2.3), otherwise, the nominal parameter value was taken from the estimated values under a mixture of 6.8 g/L of glucose and 5.4 g/L of glycerol (marked with β in Table 2.3). These values were used as the nominal parameter vector in all simulations.

To determine the identifiable subsets of parameters that could be estimated, two sensitivity measures based on a scaled sensitivity matrix ($\mathbf{S}^{sc} = \{s_{ij}\}$) were applied: the parameter importance (δ_j^{msqr}) and the collinearity index (γ_K). This methodology was adapted from Brun et al. (2002) [118].

Table 2.3: Nominal values and units of parameters used in simulations, taken from apparent experimental values from glucose cultures (α) or estimated values from mixed cultures (β), described by Lopes et al. (2014) [26].

Parameter	Value	Units
$\mu_{\max,S}$	0.38^α	h^{-1}
$\mu_{\max,A}$	0.14^α	h^{-1}
$Y_{X/S}$	0.80^α	$g_{\text{biomass}}/g_{\text{glucose}}$
$Y_{X/A}$	0.60^α	$g_{\text{biomass}}/g_{\text{acetate}}$
Y_{P/X_S}	$2.2E-03^\alpha$	$g_{\text{plasmid}}/g_{\text{biomass}}$
Y_{P/X_A}	$1.7E-03^\alpha$	$g_{\text{plasmid}}/g_{\text{biomass}}$
$Y_{P_A/S}$	1.20^β	$g_{\text{acetate}}/g_{\text{glucose}}$
K_S	0.11^β	g_{glucose}/L
K_A	0.24^β	g_{acetate}/L
$K_{i,X-A}$	39.60^β	—

The final sensitivity matrix was obtained by averaging the pointwise sensitivities over all N_t experimental time points (Equation 2.13). Each coefficient of the sensitivity matrix was calculated using the range of variation (uncertainty) attributed to each parameter j ($\Delta\theta_j$), the scaling factors attributed to each output i (sc_i), and the derivative of the model output i evaluated at time t_k given the nominal parameter vector θ_i ($\frac{\partial\eta_i(t_k;\theta)}{\partial\theta_j}$).

$$s_{ij} = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{k=1}^{N_t} \left[\frac{\Delta\theta_j}{sc_i} \cdot \frac{\partial\eta_i(t_k;\theta)}{\partial\theta_j} \right] \quad (2.13)$$

The scaling factors (sc_i) used to normalise sensitivities corresponded to the average experimental value of all non-zero outputs. The time-point derivatives were calculated using a finite difference approximation (Equation 2.14). The perturbations $\Delta\theta_j$ were defined *a priori* as a fixed percentage of the nominal value of each parameter. Nominal parameter values can be taken from the literature or experimental data, and attributed different levels of uncertainty based on parameter knowledge and accuracy. However, as the nominal parameters were taken from a previously calibrated model [26], a fixed value of 30 % was used for all parameters.

$$\frac{\partial\eta_i(t_k;\theta)}{\partial\theta_j} \approx \frac{\eta_i(t_k;\theta_j + \Delta\theta_j) - \eta_i(t_k;\theta_j)}{\Delta\theta_j} \quad (2.14)$$

This analysis was used to derive the importance of a parameter (δ_j), which corresponds to the mean squared norm of its respective column in the sensitivity matrix (s_j) (Equation 2.15). The parameters were then ranked according to importance, either globally (by averaging the values across the n outputs) or individually for each parameter.

$$\delta_j = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n s_{ij}^2} \quad (2.15)$$

The identifiable subsets of parameters (K) were determined by calculating the collinearity index (γ_K). In Equation 2.16, the collinearity index γ_K was defined as the inverse of the square root of the smallest eigenvalue of the matrix $\tilde{S}_K^T \tilde{S}_K$ ($\tilde{\lambda}_k$), where \tilde{S}_K is the normalized sensitivity matrix restricted to the parameters in K .

$$\gamma_K = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\tilde{\lambda}_k}} \quad (2.16)$$

It was established an identifiability threshold of 20 [118], so all subsets with a collinearity index lower than the established value were considered identifiable.

2.2.4 Parameter estimation

The identifiable parameters of each subset were estimated through a Weighted Least Squares (WLS) regression, minimising the WRSS (Equation 2.17), as described by Brun et al. (2002) [118].

$$WRSS = (\mathbf{Y} - \eta(\theta))^T \cdot \mathbf{W}(\mathbf{Y} - \eta(\theta)) \quad (2.17)$$

With \mathbf{Y} being the vector containing experimental data, and $\eta(\theta)$ the vector of model predictions using parameter vector θ , made up of the parameters being estimated and the remaining fixed parameters. $\mathbf{Y} - \eta(\theta)$ corresponds to the residuals. The weight matrix, \mathbf{W} , corresponded to $diag(1/sc_i^2)$, and served to normalise the residuals.

This estimation was done for all subsets below the identifiability threshold established in the previous step, with the subset with the lowest value of WRSS being selected as the final subset used in the subsequent steps.

The fit between the model predictions and the experimental data was evaluated through the R^2 of each output (Equation 2.18), as well as through the nRMSE (Equation 2.19).

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_t (y_{i,t}^{exp} - y_{i,t}^{sim})^2}{\sum_t (y_{i,t}^{exp} - \bar{y}^{exp})^2} \quad (2.18)$$

$$nRMSE_i = \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\frac{y_{i,t}^{exp} - y_{i,t}^{sim}}{sc_i} \right)^2} \quad (2.19)$$

To assess the degree of confidence attached to each estimated parameter, the IC were determined. This was achieved by calculating the covariance matrix for the estimated parameters using Equation 2.20, as described by Sin et al. (2008) [79].

$$\text{Cov}(\theta) = (J^T W J)^{-1} \cdot \frac{1}{N \cdot n - M} \quad (2.20)$$

In the equation, \mathbf{J} corresponds to the Jacobian matrix of the outputs with respect to the estimated parameters ($\frac{\partial y_k}{\partial \theta}$), \mathbf{W} is the weight matrix, M the number of estimated parameters, and N and n the number of time points and outputs, respectively. The uncertainty associated with experimental values was based on the method used to analyse the samples, with a 20% error being attributed to the conversion of OD to DCW in biomass [107], 5% to the measurement using HPLC of glucose and acetate [107], and 10% to plasmid, which used a Nanodrop device.

The IC of each estimated parameter was calculated using Equation 2.21, where, $t(N - M, \alpha/2)$ is the value of the t -distribution ($\alpha/2$ percentile), and $N - M$ the difference between number of experimental points (N) and number of parameters (M).

$$\theta_{1-\alpha} = \theta \pm \sqrt{\text{diag}(\text{Cov}(\theta))} \cdot t(N - M, \alpha/2) \quad (2.21)$$

2.2.5 Uncertainty analysis

To assess the impact of input parameter variability on model outputs, an uncertainty analysis was conducted following the methodology described by Fernandes et al. (2013) [107].

The parameter space was defined using the 95 % IC previously estimated for the fitted parameters, and a ± 30 % variability around the nominal values for the remaining fixed parameters. Parameter sampling was performed using the Latin Hypercube Sampling method, incorporating the correlation structure among estimated parameters, as described by the correlation matrix (Equation 2.22):

$$\text{Corr}(\theta_j, \theta_i) = \frac{\text{Cov}(\theta_j, \theta_i)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(\theta_j)} \cdot \sqrt{\text{Var}(\theta_i)}} \quad (2.22)$$

Each generated parameter set was used to simulate the model dynamics, from which the output trajectories were aggregated to compute the mean profile and the 10th and 90th percentiles over time. These percentiles define a prediction interval that encompasses 80 % of the simulated results, providing a non-parametric representation of the uncertainty in predictions of the model.

2.2.6 Global sensitivity analysis

The Morris screening method was selected for global sensitivity analysis, as it is often more indicated for non-linear models when compared to, for example, the standardised regression coefficient [107]. The method is based on the Morris sampling [119], in which the sensitivity analysis is done through randomised calculation using a one-factor-at-a-time approach [107].

In accordance with what was described by Fernandes et al. (2013) [107], the maximum and minimum values for the parameters corresponded to the IC for estimated parameters and to a variability of 30 % for the fixed parameters. A total of 1080 parameter combinations were tested (with $r = 90$ and $N = r(k + 1)$),

k being the total number of parameters). The scaling factors used previously (corresponding to the average of all non-zero values of each output) were also used to obtain the scalar outputs (sy_k).

To measure the effect of a small change on the output of the model, the Elementary Effects (EE) of each parameter on each output was calculated according to Equation 2.23:

$$EE_j^{(k)} = \frac{sy_k(\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_j + \Delta, \dots, \theta_M) - sy_k(\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_j, \dots, \theta_M)}{\Delta} \quad (2.23)$$

In this expression, $EE_j^{(k)}$ is the elementary effect of the j -th input parameter θ_j on the k -th model output variable. The term sy_k denotes the scalar output extracted from each of the model simulations. The vector $(\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_M)$ contains all M model parameters, and Δ is a perturbation factor applied to parameter θ_j .

The magnitude of Δ depends on the number of levels p defined for the Morris method grid [120], which in this case was 8.

The distribution of EE was used to interpret the sensitivity of each parameter. From this distribution, the mean value of the EE of an output ($\mu_j^{(k)}$), the mean of the absolute values ($\mu_j^{*(k)}$), and the standard deviation $\sigma_j^{(k)}$ were extracted for analysis. This allows the interpretation of linear and non-linear effects [120].

3

Results and Discussion

Contents

3.1	Shake Flask Fermentations	41
3.2	Kinetic Model	46

In this chapter, the experimental results obtained from shake flask cultures of three *E. coli* strains are presented and discussed. Following this, the results from the model analysis, including identifiability, sensitivity and uncertainty analyses, as well as parameter estimation, are also presented and discussed. Finally, the model is tested using either experimental data from shake flask experiments and batch bioreactors and by simulating different initial conditions.

3.1 Shake Flask Fermentations

3.1.1 Overview

The results obtained during the shake flask experiments are presented in Figure 3.1 (DH5 α), 3.2 (MG1655), and 3.3 (GALG20), where each data point is shown along with its corresponding standard deviation. The data points corresponding to the plasmid concentration at hours 5 and 7 were excluded, as insufficient biomass was available to allow for accurate calculation. A complete list of the data points and their respective standard deviations is also presented in the Appendix A.

Figure 3.1: Experimental results from shake flask cultures with 20g/L of glucose for DH5 α . The figure displays time-series data for biomass (green), glucose (blue), pDNA (red), and acetate (yellow) concentrations. Biomass and glucose, and acetate should be read on the primary (left) y-axis, while pDNA are represented on the secondary (right) y-axis. Each data point represents the mean of two replicates, with error bars indicating the standard deviation. The lines connecting the points are provided solely for visual guidance and do not represent a fitted model.

All cultures exhibited growth and plasmid production, with low standard deviations for biomass, glucose, and acetate, indicating good reproducibility. However, plasmid concentration measurements showed significant variability. Considering the consistent trends between the replicates for the other

variables, it is likely that the variability in plasmid data resulted from experimental or technical errors associated with plasmid quantification. This can be attributed to the greater complexity of measuring plasmid concentration, which involves cell lysis, plasmid purification, and determination of concentration. In comparison, biomass is measured directly via optical density, typically requiring only dilution, and glucose and acetate are quantified by HPLC, which does not require complex purification steps.

Figure 3.2: Experimental results from shake flask cultures with 20g/L of glucose for **MG1655**. The figure displays time-series data for biomass (green), glucose (blue), pDNA (red), and acetate (yellow) concentrations. Biomass and glucose, and acetate should be read on the primary (left) y-axis, while pDNA are represented on the secondary (right) y-axis. Each data point represents the mean of two replicates, with error bars indicating the standard deviation. The lines connecting the points are provided solely for visual guidance and do not represent a fitted model.

The main results for each strain are presented in Table 3.1. GALG20 obtained the highest biomass and volumetric plasmid yields, with a final biomass and plasmid concentration of 2.11g/L and 12.6mg/L , respectively. This strain also consumed the most glucose and produced the least amount of acetate. DH5 α followed, with biomass and plasmid concentrations of 2.04g/L and 11.8mg/L , respectively. This strain consumed the least amount of glucose, but produced the most acetate. Lastly, MG1655 $\Delta\text{endA}\Delta\text{recA}$ (MG1655) achieved a biomass concentration of 1.66g/L and a plasmid concentration of 8.88mg/L . The specific plasmid yields followed the same trend, with GALG20, DH5 α , and MG1655 reaching 5.99 , 5.76 , and 5.35mg/g_{DCW} , respectively.

Figure 3.3: Experimental results from shake flask cultures with 20g/L of glucose for **GALG20**. The figure displays time-series data for biomass (green), glucose (blue), pDNA (red), and acetate (yellow) concentrations. Biomass and glucose, and acetate should be read on the primary (left) y-axis, while pDNA are represented on the secondary (right) y-axis. Each data point represents the mean of two replicates, with error bars indicating the standard deviation. The lines connecting the points are provided solely for visual guidance and do not represent a fitted model.

Table 3.1: Maximum biomass and plasmid (specific and volumetric) yield and maximum acetate detected for DH5 α , MG1655, and GALG20 in shake flask cultures.

Strain	Biomass	Plasmid	Plasmid	Glucose	Acetate
DH5 α	2.04 g/L	11.8 mg/L	5.76 mg/g_{DCW}	6.10 g/L	10.6 g/L
MG1655	1.66 g/L	8.88 mg/L	5.35 mg/g_{DCW}	5.05 g/L	9.41 g/L
GALG20	2.11 g/L	12.6 mg/L	5.99 mg/g_{DCW}	4.89 g/L	7.80 g/L

In none of the cultures was glucose fully consumed, which typically occurs before the onset of acetate consumption. The full consumption of acetate is usually associated with the point at which the maximum biomass and plasmid concentrations are achieved [46]. Initially, one could suggest that the final concentrations observed do not reflect the full potential of the cultures, considering that glucose and acetate were not depleted. However, it was observed that the rates of acetate and biomass were different, with acetate achieving a concentration between ~ 8 and $\sim 11\text{g/L}$, and biomass reaching a concentration of $\sim 2\text{g/L}$. Given this, it could be concluded that cell growth had ceased or would soon cease, and as such, these cultures were unlikely to enter an acetate consumption phase.

3.1.2 Acetate accumulation

The previous suggestion that the cultures were unlikely to reach an acetate consumption phase is reasonable given the small-scale operation and reduced culture volumes. However, under similar conditions, Gonçalves et al. (2014) [24] and Gonçalves et al. (2013) [44] (also mentioned in Table 1.1) reported little to no acetate accumulation. A key factor that could explain these differences lies in the medium composition. Those studies used media supplemented with Bacto peptone and yeast extract, whereas the present work employed a chemically defined media. This could partially explain the higher acetate accumulation observed here.

Volume could also be a contributing factor. Gonçalves et al. (2013) [44] used 50mL cultures and observed higher acetate levels (between ~ 4.70 and $\sim 5.7g/L$ for MG1655 and DH5 α) than Gonçalves et al. (2014) [24], who used 100mL cultures and reported between ~ 2.2 and $\sim 3.1g/L$. This could suggest a possible inverse relationship between the volume of medium and the accumulation of acetate. In this work, MG1655 and DH5 α accumulated even higher acetate concentrations (between ~ 9.4 and $\sim 10.6g/L$) when 30 mL of medium was used, which is consistent with this trend (Table 3.1).

This rationale, however, could not be extended to GALG20. In the present work, GALG20 accumulated lower values of acetate (7.8g/L) than the previous strains, aligning with reported capacities of GALG20 to accumulate less acetate [44] [24]. However, unlike those reports, the final acetate obtained in the present work was still comparable to MG1655 and DH5 α (Table 3.1), while the previously mentioned studies reported virtually no acetate accumulation in GALG20.

The glucose concentration may have also played a factor in the increased acetate concentration in all strains. In none of the cultures was the glucose fully consumed at 24 hours; while during the first 9 hours, glucose concentration decreased only modestly by 0.7g/L in MG165 and 4.9g/L in GALS20. Because glucose was consumed at a slow rate, it remained in the medium at high concentrations, triggering the aerobic phenomenon that results in acetate production [27]. Based on this, the low biomass could also be explained.

3.1.3 Biomass and plasmid

According to Gonçalves et al. (2013) [44], MG1655 produced slightly less biomass than DH5 α , while GALG20 produced almost three times more biomass than the previous strains. In the present work, although MG1655 produced less biomass than DH5 α , DH5 α and GALG20 produced very similar biomass levels. Biomass final concentrations were about half of what was reported by Gonçalves et al. (2013) [44] for DH5 α and MG1655, and for GALG20 about five times lower.

Regarding the results for the strains DH5 α and MG1655, despite producing lower amounts of biomass when compared to literature results (between 3.5 and 3.8g/L [44]), the plasmid yields obtained in the

present work were similar or higher. According to Gonçalves et al. (2014) [24], MG1655 and DH5 α exhibited a volumetric and specific plasmid yield of 8.8 and 8.2 g/L and 2.9 and 2.4 mg/g_{DCW}, respectively. MG1655 produced a similar concentration of plasmid, 8.88 mg/L, while DH5 α achieved a final concentration of 11.8 mg/L. The specific yields obtained were significantly higher than those reported [44] [24], 5.35 mg/g_{DCW} for MG1655 and 5.76 mg/g_{DCW} for DH5 α .

On the other hand, GALG20 noticeably underperformed. The final concentration of biomass was about five times lower than those reported by Gonçalves et al. (2013) [44] and Gonçalves et al. (2014) [24], and plasmid levels were about seven to eleven times lower. Furthermore, the specific yield of GALG20 was also two to three times lower than those reported by the previously mentioned authors. While difficult to assess the reasoning behind this, the behaviour could be attributed to a high sensitivity to acetate and an induced inhibitory effect.

Additionally, all cultures showed an initial decrease in biomass concentration, suggesting an adaptation to the medium. While for DH5 α and GALG20 recovered after one hour, MG1655 only surpassed its initial biomass concentration at hour six, indicating a prolonged period of adaptation.

The stunted growth of biomass can also be correlated to acetate accumulation because it acidifies the medium, which can result in lower growth rates [121]. All strains presented slow glucose consumption and high acetate production, but this impact was particularly notable for GALG20.

Typically, the lack of acetate accumulation in GALG20 would result in higher biomass production [27], but in this case, because the strain accumulated significantly more acetate than expected, its capacity as a more productive strain when compared to MG1655 and DH5 α was not demonstrated in terms of biomass concentration. This could explain the much lower biomass yield observed when compared to those reported in literature by Gonçalves et al. (2013) [44] and Gonçalves et al. (2014) [24] (Table 1.1). The slow consumption rate of glucose in all strains can be linked not just to the adaptation period, but also to the use of a chemically defined media, which can lead to lower growth rates and cell densities [122]. Indeed, the calculated growth rate in the first nine hours of experiment for DH5 α , MG1655, and GALG20 corresponded to 0.178 h⁻¹, 0.182 h⁻¹, and 0.344 h⁻¹, while literature values from Gonçalves et al. (2013) [44] using complex media reported values of 0.055 h⁻¹, 0.60 h⁻¹, and 0.60 h⁻¹, respectively.

Having said that, there was no straightforward relationship between glucose consumption and productivity. GALG20 produced the most biomass and plasmid and consumed the most glucose, but the final concentration of glucose for GALG20 (4.89g/L) was similar to that of MG1655 (5.05g/L), which yielded the lowest results. Interestingly, DH5 α consumed the least glucose (with a final concentration of 6.10g/L), but the CS was directed towards producing comparable amounts of biomass and plasmid to GALG20, and producing the highest concentration of acetate. It can be suggested that MG1655 experienced a particularly poor adaptation to the medium that resulted in the initial drop in biomass, from which the cells did not fully recover, leading to abnormally low values.

3.2 Kinetic Model

3.2.1 Batch bioreactors datasets

The batch bioreactors datasets with an initial glucose concentration of 20g/L for the three strains, $\text{DH5}\alpha$, $\text{MG1655 } \Delta\text{endA}\Delta\text{recA}$ (MG1655), and GALG20, were used to build the corresponding kinetic models, which are presented in the next chapter. For each dataset, an identifiability analysis was first conducted to determine the identifiable parameter subsets. These parameters were then estimated and their respective IC determined. Following this, uncertainty and sensitivity analyses were performed to evaluate the robustness of the model and the influence of each parameter on model outputs. Using the parameters estimated for $\text{DH5}\alpha$, MG1655 and GALG20, the models were then tested against two independent batch bioreactors datasets (for MG1655 and GALG20) and three shake flask datasets, all with an initial glucose concentration of 20g/L , equal to the initial conditions of the datasets used to simulate them. Finally, considering these test results for MG1655 and GALG20 along with additional simulations involving variations in the initial substrate concentrations, the model structure and the parameter values were analysed in the context of the biological differences between MG1655 and GALG20.

Note that, due to the large amount of data and outputs generated in these analyses, not all of the figures and tables are represented in this section, but they can be found in the Appendix B for reference.

Before proceeding with the analysis, a brief description of the datasets used for estimation is provided. The datasets for MG1655 and the GALG20 were derived from bioreactor cultures monitored using Near-Infrared (NIR) spectroscopy [47], which can be subject to signal interference from other compounds present in the culture medium, which may compromise data reliability [123]. Indeed, the datasets occasionally presented null values and abrupt fluctuations, which were likely artefacts of the measurement system. To address this, linear interpolation was applied to the specific zero values to improve continuity and analytical robustness, as these were deemed likely to result from instabilities in the NIR measurement system. The datasets used in the following sections are presented in Figure 3.4.

The experimentally measured initial glucose concentration ranged from $\sim 20 - 27\text{g/L}$. GALG20 presented the lowest accumulation of acetate and achieved a similar plasmid production levels similar to those of MG1655. To maintain consistency across datasets, the data was restricted to the first 24 h of the cultivation. An unusual behaviour was observed in the GALG20 dataset, in which the acetate was produced and subsequently consumed while glucose was still abundant in the media. This deviates from the expected behaviour, in which acetate consumption typically begins after glucose depletion. On the other hand, MG1655 exhibited a rapid drop in glucose levels during the first hours, which did not align with the production of biomass and acetate. The dataset for the $\text{DH5}\alpha$ culture is noticeably scarce, which can impact the model analysis and associated robustness.

DH5 α

MG1655

GALG20

Figure 3.4: Representation of estimation datasets for **batch bioreactors** experiments using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right). The figure displays time-series data for biomass (green), glucose (yellow), pDNA (red), and acetate (blue) concentrations. Biomass, glucose, and acetate should be read on the primary (left) y-axis, while pDNA are represented on the secondary (right) y-axis for DH5 α and MG1655. For GALG20, the acetate is also read on the (right) y-axis. The lines connecting the points are provided solely for visual guidance and do not represent a fitted model.

3.2.2 Analysis

The initial step of this analysis was to compute the sensitivity matrix (\mathbf{S}^{sc}) for each dataset using the developed model (in Appendix B, Table B.1 to B.3). This matrix was then used to determine and rank the average importance of each parameter (δ_j) for all model outputs (Figure 3.5), using the average of the individual importance on each output (in Appendix B, Figure B.1).

The sensitivity indexes (s_{ij}) consistently presented a range of ± 0.70 , with the noticeable exception of the values for the acetate output, whose sensitivity indexes ranged from about -6.3 to $+14.6$. This discrepancy could be attributed to the low value of the scaling factor (sc_i) for acetate in the GALG20 dataset ($\sim 0.12g/L$), due to the very low quantities of acetate produced in this experiment. For comparison, the scaling factors for DH5 α and MG1655 were ~ 3.9 and $2.9g/L$, respectively. This was reflected in the importance of the parameters (δ_j), represented in Figure 3.5, where GALG20 also presented a significantly larger maximum value (~ 7) than the other two strains (~ 0.35).

Despite the difference in values, the results were mostly consistent across strains, with μ_{maxS} and $Y_{PA/S}$ amongst the most important parameters, and K_S , K_A , and K_{iX-A} the least. $Y_{X/S}$ also ranked among the top three most important parameters for DH5 α and MG1655, while for GALG20 $Y_{X/A}$ showed greater relative importance. The parameters associated with plasmid production (Y_{P/X_S} and Y_{P/X_A}) consistently ranked lower, particularly for GALG20. This makes sense because these parameters influence only the plasmid output and not the other model variables, thereby decreasing their overall importance, especially in the case of GALG20, where the importance of acetate-related parameters is inflated. Overall, this ranking aligns well with the structure of the model (Equations 2.9 - 2.12), where parameters associated with biomass concentration (X) and its growth kinetics (μ_S and $Y_{X/S}$) are expected to be the most influential.

Lastly, before parameter estimation, the identifiable subsets were determined using the collinearity index (γ_K), where the subsets with a γ_K lower than 20 were considered for parameter estimation. High collinearity would indicate that the parameters cannot be uniquely identified. Additionally, to reduce computation time, only subsets with more than two parameters were considered.

The collinearity indexes for each strain, grouped by subset size, are presented in Figure 3.6. A significant gap in γ_K values is observed in all strains, ultimately resulting in extremely large values for larger subsets. While larger collinearity indexes are typically expected for larger subsets, the γ_K values do not usually reach such high orders of magnitude. This was attributed to low sensitivity values for some parameters that resulted in disproportional values. Indeed, the subsets with the highest collinearity typically contained multiple parameters with the lowest sensitivity and importance score, such as K_S , K_A , and K_{iX-A} . Despite this, both DH5 α and MG1655 yielded a large number of identifiable subsets that met the previously stated required criteria, with 130 and 177 subsets, respectively. In contrast, GALG20 exhibited only 26 identifiable subsets. Across all strains, the maximum number of parameters

DH5 α

MG1655

GALG20

Figure 3.5: Ranked importance of parameters (δ_j) using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right).

DH5 α

MG1655

GALG20

Figure 3.6: Collinearity indexes (γ_K) according to subset size using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right). Each subset is represented by a dot, and corresponds to an index (x-axis), a collinearity index value (left y-axis), and a subset size (right y-axis).

in any identifiable subset was four. While for DH5 α or GALG20 no subsets with four parameters exhibited a γ_K value lower than 5 (minimal threshold for collinearity according to Brun et al. (2002) [118]), for MG1655, 40 out of the 177 subsets satisfied this condition, indicating low collinearity between the parameters.

As previously mentioned, a single subset was not selected a priori for parameter estimation. Instead, all subsets with more than two parameters and a γ_K below 20 were considered for estimation, and those were then ordered according to WRSS, with the subset with the lowest WRSS corresponding to the best one. However, an exception was made to DH5 α , where the WRSS of the top two subsets (between ~ 0.118 to ~ 0.1214) were very similar to that of the third subset (~ 0.1214), but the collinearity index was significantly higher (19.8 to 15.0, from lowest to highest WRSS) than the third subset (5.70). Given this, the collinearity threshold was lowered to 10 for this strain to favour this more robust subset.

Table 3.2 shows the estimated parameters used to assess the model for all studied cases. Parameters that were estimated were highlighted in blue, the remaining were taken from Lopes et al. (2014) [26] as fixed values (Table 2.3).

It was observed that the best subsets for the three strains contained two common parameters, $Y_{X/S}$ and Y_{P/X_A} , with $Y_{X/A}$ only estimated in MG1655. Both specific growth rates were estimated, μ_{maxS} in DH5 α and MG1655, and μ_{maxA} in DH5 α and GALG20.

Table 3.2: Final parameter set for the three strains (DH5 α , MG1655, GALG20), with estimated parameter values highlighted in blue.

Strain	μ_{maxS}	μ_{maxA}	$Y_{X/S}$	$Y_{X/A}$	Y_{P/X_S}	Y_{P/X_A}	$Y_{P_A/S}$	K_S	K_A	K_{iX-A}
DH5α	0.377	0.021	0.316	0.600	0.002	0.025	1.200	0.110	0.240	39.600
MG1655	1.199	0.140	0.144	3.294	0.002	0.008	1.200	0.110	0.240	39.600
GALG20	0.380	2.224	0.257	0.600	0.002	0.011	1.200	0.110	0.240	39.600

It is important to note that the estimated parameter values are not intended for direct comparison of biological significance across different operation modes or strains, since only a subset of parameters was estimated in each case. The remaining parameters were fixed at the corresponding nominal values, which may differ from their true biological values. As a result, the estimated parameters may compensate for inaccuracies in the fixed parameters, thereby deviating from their intrinsic biological meaning. Consequently, neither the estimated nor the fixed parameters should be interpreted as precise representations of the underlying biological phenomena.

Figure 3.7: Model simulation vs experimental data for **DH5 α** . The figure displays time-series data for biomass (green), glucose (blue), pDNA (red), and acetate (yellow) concentrations. Biomass, glucose, and acetate should be read on the primary (left) y-axis, while pDNA are represented on the secondary (right) y-axis. The dashed lines represent the fitting obtained for each output, and match the colour of the corresponding output.

Figure 3.7 (DH5 α), 3.8 (MG1655), and 3.9 (GALG20) present the model fitting results for the three strains. Individual output plots are also present in Appendix B (Figure B.2) for each strain.

To quantitatively assess the fitting, the R^2 for each output and the average nRMSE of all outputs were calculated for each strain in each condition. These values are presented in Table 3.3, along with the WRSS, which corresponds to the lowest value obtained during estimation.

Table 3.3: Values for the R^2 of each output, the final WRSS, and the average nRMSE of each output, for the three strains (DH5 α , MG1655, GALG20). $R^2 \geq \sim 80$ are highlighted.

Strain	R^2 Biomass	R^2 Glucose	R^2 Plasmid	R^2 Acetate	WRSS	Avg. NRMSE
DH5α	0.976	1.00	0.994	0.996	0.121	0.006
MG1655	0.836	0.160	0.848	0.150	80.2	0.334
GALG20	0.881	0.423	0.797	0.041	25.4	0.106

Figure 3.8: Model simulation vs experimental data for **MG1655**. The figure displays time-series data for biomass (green), glucose (blue), pDNA (red), and acetate (yellow) concentrations. Biomass, glucose, and acetate should be read on the primary (left) y-axis, while pDNA are represented on the secondary (right) y-axis. The dashed lines represent the fitting obtained for each output, and match the colour of the corresponding output.

The subsets with a WRSS value below 100 were assessed. The best estimation for GALG20 was closely followed by another where Y_{P/X_S} was estimated instead of Y_{P/X_A} , with all the remaining estimations having WRSS values over ~ 60 . This also occurred in MG1655, where only two estimations had a WRSS below 100, the second one corresponding to a value of ~ 96 . On the other hand, DH5 α had over 100 estimations matching this criteria, with values gradually increasing and in total containing subsets that estimated all parameters.

Using the estimated parameters from the subset with the lowest WRSS and the nominal parameter values for the remaining ones, the model was simulated using the initial conditions of each dataset and its corresponding parameters.

For the batch simulation, GALG20 yielded values of WRSS and nRMSE about three times lower than those of MG1655. For biomass and plasmid, the R^2 values were similar between the two strains, between ~ 0.80 and ~ 0.88 . In the MG1655 simulation, the fitting originated a similarly low R^2 for glucose and acetate, while in GALG20 these values were distinct, corresponding to ~ 0.42 and ~ 0.04 ,

respectively. The values for R^2 in DH5 α were extremely high, attributed to the low number of points in this dataset that can result in near-perfect fittings. This is supported by the particularly low values of WRSS (< 0.2) and nRMSE (< 0.01).

Figure 3.9: Model simulation vs experimental data for **GALG20**. The figure displays time-series data for biomass (green), glucose (blue), pDNA (red), and acetate (yellow) concentrations. Biomass, glucose, and acetate should be read on the primary (left) y-axis, while pDNA are represented on the secondary (right) y-axis. Biomass, glucose, should be read on the primary (left) y-axis, while pDNA and acetate are represented on the secondary (right) y-axis. The dashed lines represent the fitting obtained for each output, and match the colour of the corresponding output.

The correlation between estimated parameters was also studied through their correlation matrix (in Appendix B, Figure B.3). MG1655 and GALG20 showed reasonable correlations values, not exceeding ~ 0.70 , which occurred for μ_{maxS} and $Y_{X/S}$ in MG1655, and for $Y_{X/S}$ and Y_{P/X_A} in GALG20, both positive correlations. However, in DH5 α this last pair of parameters had a high negative correlation value of -0.879 .

Overall, the correlations between pairs of parameters were not consistent or explained by the model structure across strains, which can be attributed to differences in the estimated subsets and, therefore, the inability to perform comparisons between the strains. Regarding the model fitting, as in the context of this work, biomass and plasmid are the most important variables, although the R^2 values for glucose and

Table 3.4: Estimated parameter values, respective 95% IC, for the three strains (DH5 α , MG1655, GALG20).

Strain	Parameter	Estimate	CI	CI (%)	γ_K
DH5 α	μ_{maxS}	0.377	$\pm 2.6E - 03$	0.68%	5.70
	μ_{maxA}	0.0206	$\pm 6.0E - 04$	2.91%	
	$Y_{X/S}$	0.316	$\pm 4.7E - 03$	1.48%	
	Y_{P/X_A}	0.0249	$\pm 1.3E - 03$	5.04%	
MG1655	μ_{maxS}	1.199	$\pm 5.5E - 04$	0.05%	1.91
	$Y_{X/S}$	0.144	$\pm 1.6E - 04$	0.11%	
	$Y_{X/A}$	3.294	$\pm 6.3E - 03$	0.19%	
	Y_{P/X_A}	0.0081	$\pm 1.6E - 05$	0.19%	
GALG20	μ_{maxA}	2.224	$\pm 8.5E - 03$	0.38%	18.40
	$Y_{X/S}$	0.257	$\pm 4.3E - 04$	0.17%	
	Y_{P/X_A}	0.0106	$\pm 2.9E - 05$	0.28%	

acetate were considerably low (except for the DH5 α model), the first two variables being well described by the model make these results overall positive.

Additionally, the IC of each parameter estimated was determined in order to assess the confidence degree associated with each estimation. The IC should not reach zero, which can indicate parameter redundancy (over-parametrisation). Narrow intervals are preferred, as it can otherwise indicate low parameter sensitivity and, consequently, reduced reliability in estimation.

The results of this analysis are presented in Table 3.4, which contains the estimated parameters for all studied cases, alongside the corresponding IC (and respective percentages). In order to relate this analysis with the previous one, the collinearity index of the selected subset for each case was also presented.

The best subsets for the three strains, their estimated parameters, and the corresponding IC are present in Table 2.21. DH5 α displayed the widest values for each IC, but still remained below 10%, with μ_{maxS} , showing the narrowest IC and an estimated value similar value as the nominal one ($0.38h^{-1}$, Table 2.3). The collinearity index associated with the subset was also low, which would indicate that the estimation is meaningful. However, a low number of points in this dataset can result in very narrow estimations due to overconfidence, as was observed in the fitting of the data and the values of R^2 and nRMSE. The other two strains yielded similarly good results, with the highest IC corresponding to $\sim 0.38\%$. Both these estimations originated from large datasets, so overconfidence was not a concern, but the subset selected for simulating GALG20 had a corresponding collinearity index of 18.40, significantly higher than the previous ones. However, considering the acceptable results and behaviour of the model, this was not considered problematic.

Following parameter estimation, the impact of output variance considering parameter variability was studied through an uncertainty analysis. The model was simulated using a parameter space defined by

1000 generated samples. For these simulations, the mean value and the prediction band including 80% of simulations (between the 10th and 90th percentiles) were determined. These results are presented in Figures 3.10 to 3.12. As described in the methods section, the parameter space was defined using either the IC (for an estimated parameter) or a variability of $\pm 30\%$ (for fixed parameters).

Figure 3.10: Uncertainty analysis according to output, with corresponding mean and 10th and 90th percentiles, for $DH5\alpha$. The bands represent the 80 % prediction interval and the black line the mean value of predictions. For the three strains, the biomass is presented on the top left; the glucose on the top right; the plasmid on the bottom left; and the acetate on the bottom right.

In Figure 3.10 ($DH5\alpha$), 3.11 (MG1655), and 3.12 (GALG20), the robustness of the model predictions can be assessed through the width of the prediction bands. Narrow bands indicate robust predictions, as observed for all variables in the $DH5\alpha$ model, except for acetate. Acetate predictions were poor across all models, consistently showing wide uncertainty bands. Comparing MG1655 and GALG20, it is noted that GALG20 exhibits wider bands earlier in the simulation, and produces significantly less robust predictions for glucose. In contrast, MG1655 presents a very narrow band for glucose, indicating high confidence in this output. These differences can be largely attributed to the estimated parameters (Table 3.4) and their relative importance for each output (Appendix B, Figure B.1). Parameters that were estimated (and thus defined by their IC) had a considerably smaller range of variability than fixed parameters.

Figure 3.11: Uncertainty analysis according to output, with corresponding mean and 10th and 90th percentiles, for **MG1655**. The bands represent the 80 % prediction interval and the black line the mean value of predictions. For the three strains, the biomass is presented on the top left; the glucose on the top right; the plasmid on the bottom left; and the acetate on the bottom right.

According to the results, μ_{maxS} is consistently the most important parameter for glucose estimation across all three strains, being about 4 to 6 times more important than the second most important parameter. In GALG20, this parameter was not estimated, so its variability is significantly larger ($\pm 30\%$) than the variability for DH5 α ($\pm 0.67\%$) and MG1655 ($\pm 0.05\%$), making the simulation range of this parameter wider. In this model structure, μ_{maxS} is also among the more important parameters for biomass, plasmid, and glucose, so its larger variability leads to less robust results. $Y_{X/S}$, μ_{maxS} , and μ_{maxA} were estimated in the DH5 α model, and were also the three most influential parameters for biomass and glucose, with $Y_{X/S}$ and μ_{maxS} being in the top three most important parameters for plasmid production. For acetate, the most influential parameter is $Y_{PA/S}$, being twice as important as the second most influential parameter for DH5 α and MG1655. However, $Y_{PA/S}$ has never been estimated in any of the models. In the GALG20 model, $Y_{PA/S}$ and μ_{maxS} are similarly important, but neither was estimated. This is in accordance with the uncertainties observed for the different outputs, represented by the width of bands in Figures 3.10 to 3.12.

Figure 3.12: Uncertainty analysis according to output, with corresponding mean and 10th and 90th percentiles, for **GALG20**. The bands represent the 80 % prediction interval and the black line the mean value of predictions. For the three strains, the biomass is presented on the top left; the glucose on the top right; the plasmid on the bottom left; and the acetate on the bottom right.

Finally, a global sensitivity analysis is performed, using Morris screening. The randomised Morris sampling was used, and the same upper and lower bounds as the parameter space in the previous analysis were applied. The EE were estimated using 90 repetitions (r) and 1080 parameter combinations, which originated the simulations represented in Figure 3.13 (DH5 α), 3.14 (MG1655), and 3.15 (GALG20). These results seemed to align well with the previous analysis, showing similar bands in each corresponding output and strain.

Figure 3.13: Sensitivity analysis using Morris screening, with mean and 10th and 90th percentiles, for each output in cultures for $DH5\alpha$. The bands compose the spectrum of simulations, the dashed black lines the 10th and 90th percentile intervals, and the solid black line the mean value of predictions. For the three strains, the biomass is presented on the top left; the glucose on the top right; the plasmid on the bottom left; and the acetate on the bottom right.

Figure 3.14: Sensitivity analysis using Morris screening, with mean and 10th and 90th percentiles, for each output in cultures for **MG1655**. The bands compose the spectrum of simulations, the dashed black lines the 10th and 90th percentile intervals, and the solid black line the mean value of predictions. For the three strains, the biomass is presented on the top left; the glucose on the top right; the plasmid on the bottom left; and the acetate on the bottom right.

Figure 3.15: Sensitivity analysis using Morris screening, with mean and 10th and 90th percentiles, for each output in cultures for **GALG20**. The bands compose the spectrum of simulations, the dashed black lines the 10th and 90th percentile intervals, and the solid black line the mean value of predictions. For the three strains, the biomass is presented on the top left; the glucose on the top right; the plasmid on the bottom left; and the acetate on the bottom right.

From the distribution of the EEs of each output, the effect of parameters on each variable was assessed through the mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of the distribution function. To interpret these results, the data was mapped using previous examples [120] [107], in which the mean and standard deviations of each parameter were plotted for each variable. To evaluate the significance of the effect of a parameter, a U-shape boundary was defined using the expression $sem_i = \pm 2\sigma_i/\sqrt{r}$. The parameter effect was considered insignificant when falling inside the parabola, and significance when falling outside the parabola. Significant effects were classified as non-linear if σ was non-zero, and linear if σ was zero. These results are presented in Figure 3.16 (DH5 α), 3.17 (MG1655), and 3.18 (GALG20).

Figure 3.16: Morris screening for each output in cultivations for **DH5 α** . The dashed lines represent the wedge formed by sem_i , and the dots present each parameter according to mean value (x-axis) and standard deviation (left y-axis). The parameters inside the wedge are in blue. For the three strains, the biomass is presented on the top left, the glucose on the top right, the plasmid on the bottom left, and the acetate on the bottom right.

As expected, the two plasmid-related parameters (Y_{P/X_S} and Y_{P/X_A}) had a null μ and corresponding σ for all strains and all outputs except plasmid. Apart from this, K_S in the acetate output for the GALG20 model and $Y_{X/A}$ for the DH5 α plasmid output were the only other insignificant parameters found for the three models in batch bioreactors mode. All remaining parameter effects fall into the non-linear category, which is common in biological models. The wedge obtained was noticeably narrow, likely because of low σ values.

The significance of each parameter was assessed using the absolute mean (μ^*), allowing the parameters to be ranked according to the significance for each output. The absolute values were ranked and the top 5, presented in Table 3.5 according to output and strain, were analysed.

Figure 3.17: Morris screening for each output in cultivations for **MG1655**. The dashed lines represent the wedge formed by sem_i , and the dots present each parameter according to mean value (x-axis) and standard deviation (left y-axis). The parameters inside the wedge are in blue. For the three strains, the biomass is presented on the top left, the glucose on the top right, the plasmid on the bottom left, and the acetate on the bottom right.

The top 5 most influential parameters did not generally correspond to the most important parameters (Figure 3.5), in most cases, with notable exceptions such as Y_{P/X_S} and Y_{P/X_A} , which had significant influence on plasmid production, and $Y_{P_A/S}$ and $Y_{X/S}$, which were important parameters for acetate and glucose, respectively, and also presented the highest effect on the corresponding output.

Figure 3.18: Morris screening for each output in cultivations for **GALG20**. The dashed lines represent the wedge formed by sem_i , and the dots present each parameter according to mean value (x-axis) and standard deviation (left y-axis). The parameters inside the wedge are in blue. For the three strains, the biomass is presented on the top left, the glucose on the top right, the plasmid on the bottom left, and the acetate on the bottom right.

Interestingly, certain low-importance parameters like K_{iX-A} , K_A , and K_S inflicted a considerable effect on certain outputs. For example, K_{iX-A} was consistently among the most influential parameters for DH5 α and MG1655, but was completely absent in the top 5 parameters for GALG20. Considering that GALG20 produces very little acetate, it is expected that the inhibition constant would have little influence on the outputs when compared to the remaining strains. While K_S was only highly influential in glucose, K_A , like other acetate-related parameters such as $Y_{PA/S}$ and μ_{maxA} , had a considerable effect in all strains and outputs. These results seem to reinforce the strong influence of acetate in plasmid production [44].

Table 3.5: Morris ranking of the top 5 parameters, θ , according to absolute mean value, μ^* , for cultures using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (middle), and GALG20 (bottom).

Strain		X		S		P		A	
		θ	μ^*	θ	μ^*	θ	μ^*	θ	μ^*
DH5 α	1	K_{iX-A}	0.0222	K_{iX-A}	0.008	Y_{P/X_S}	0.200	$Y_{PA/S}$	0.799
	2	$Y_{X/S}$	0.020	μ_{maxS}	0.007	Y_{P/X_A}	0.067	$Y_{X/A}$	0.208
	3	$Y_{PA/S}$	0.014	$Y_{PA/S}$	0.006	K_{iX-A}	0.065	$Y_{X/S}$	0.022
	4	μ_{maxA}	0.010	$Y_{X/S}$	0.005	μ_{maxA}	0.045	μ_{maxA}	0.022
	5	μ_{maxS}	0.009	K_S	0.002	$Y_{PA/S}$	0.039	K_{iX-A}	0.014
MG1655	1	μ_{maxA}	0.354	μ_{maxA}	0.014	μ_{maxA}	0.470	$Y_{PA/S}$	0.558
	2	$Y_{PA/S}$	0.148	K_{iX-A}	0.006	$Y_{PA/S}$	0.197	μ_{maxA}	0.291
	3	K_A	0.033	K_A	0.006	Y_{P/X_S}	0.075	K_A	0.025
	4	K_{iX-A}	0.026	K_S	0.003	K_A	0.043	K_{iX-A}	0.019
	5	$Y_{X/S}$	0.002	$Y_{PA/S}$	0.001	K_{iX-A}	0.033	$Y_{X/S}$	0.001
GALG20	1	μ_{maxS}	0.488	μ_{maxS}	0.441	$Y_{PA/S}$	0.508	K_A	0.077
	2	$Y_{PA/S}$	0.384	$Y_{PA/S}$	0.120	$Y_{X/A}$	0.480	$Y_{PA/S}$	0.067
	3	$Y_{X/A}$	0.360	$Y_{X/A}$	0.107	μ_{maxS}	0.415	$Y_{X/A}$	0.062
	4	K_A	0.015	K_A	0.013	Y_{P/X_S}	0.114	μ_{maxS}	0.008
	5	$Y_{X/S}$	0.003	K_S	0.002	K_A	0.014	μ_{maxA}	0.001

3.2.3 Model testing

Finally, to exemplify the model behaviour under different but comparable initial conditions, the defined parameter set was used to simulate new datasets (testing data), using the initial conditions of this set. Considering the available datasets, this was only done for two models under batch bioreactors conditions, MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA (MG1655 batch bioreactors model) and GALG20 (GALG20 batch bioreactors model). Additionally, the experimental data produced in this work under shake flask conditions was used to test all the three models, namely, DH5 α (DH5 α shake flask model), MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA (MG1655 shake flask model) and GALG20 (GALG20 shake flask model).

3.2.3.1 Batch bioreactors

The model was simulated using the parameter sets described in Table 3.2 and the initial conditions specific to each dataset. The resulting simulations were analysed and compared to those obtained using the data originally used for parameter estimation. The simulation and testing data are also compared according to strain and output (represented in Appendix B, Figure B.4).

In Figure 3.19 (MG1655) and 3.20 (GALG20), a visual comparison is made between the datasets (in colours) used for estimating the parameters (dashed line) and testing the model (filled line) and the corresponding simulations (in black). As can be observed in the figures, the estimating and testing datasets are not significantly different in terms of the final value of plasmid concentration and the maximum value of acetate. However, in the dataset used for estimating the parameters, significantly more biomass was produced in both cultures. Additionally, the curves describing the evolution of each variable present

visible differences between datasets.

Considering the MG1655 testing results in Figure 3.19, it is evident that the simulation curves are not significantly distinct in the first half of the experiment in the estimation or testing, particularly in the case of plasmid production. For testing and estimating, the model did not follow glucose consumption and failed to reach the corresponding levels of acetate accumulation. Furthermore, while the model predicted accurately the final concentration of biomass during estimation, the value obtained during testing was significantly higher than the actual value. However, the reverse occurred in the case of plasmid production, where the testing prediction was much closer to the actual value than during estimation.

Figure 3.19: Comparison of data used for estimation and respective simulation with data used for **batch bioreactors** testing and respective simulation, for **MG1655**. The dashed lines represent the experimental data and the fitting obtained during parameter estimations, and the solid lines refer to the experimental data and the fitting obtained for batch bioreactors testing. The figure displays time-series data for biomass (top left, green), glucose (top right, blue), pDNA (bottom left, red), and acetate (bottom right, yellow) concentrations for each strain.

Similarly to the MG1655 model, the GALG20 model did not predict the accumulation of acetate accurately (Figure 3.19 and 3.20), but was able to follow the glucose consumption with a reasonable degree of accuracy, and resulted in a final biomass concentration aligned with the testing dataset. Plasmid production predictions using the initial conditions of the testing datasets were considerably lower than the actual value, which also occurred using the estimation dataset.

Figure 3.20: Comparison of data used for estimation and respective simulation with data used for **batch bioreactors** testing and respective simulation, for **GALG20**. The dashed lines represent the experimental data and the fitting obtained during parameter estimations, and the solid lines refer to the experimental data and the fitting obtained for batch bioreactors testing. The figure displays time-series data for biomass (top left, green), glucose (top right, blue), pDNA (bottom left, red), and acetate (bottom right, yellow) concentrations for each strain.

These observations were quantitatively assessed using the R^2 values. The R^2 values for both tests were calculated to describe how the model fit the datasets. The R^2 for the plasmid output reached nearly 0.5 in both models (0.49 for MG1655 and 0.67 for GALG20). The only other value surpassing 0.5 was the R^2 value for the glucose output in the GALG20 model, which corresponded to 0.96, with this being the only value higher in the testing simulation than in the estimation simulation. This aligned with what was observed in Figure 3.19 and 3.20, but was not expected considering the low values of R^2 for glucose obtained after parameter estimation (0.423 - Table 3.3).

The value of the average nRMSE was also determined for the MG1655 and the GALG20 model, corresponding to 0.467 and 0.244, which are comparable to values obtained for the original dataset (0.334 and 0.106, respectively), as shown in Table 3.3. It is worth noting that the large difference in data points (Table 2.2) in each dataset can also affect these results.

The primary objective of this work was to support experimentalists through the development of a predictive model capable of anticipating experimental outcomes. By doing so, the model aims to reduce the need for extensive trial-and-error, saving both time and resources while accelerating the overall process development. Considering this, comparing experimental and predicted key process parameters, such as the maximum values for biomass, plasmid and acetate, is relevant. Note that in the case of plasmid and biomass, the maximum value typically corresponds to the final value. The results of this analysis are presented in Table 3.6.

Table 3.6: Comparison of maximum values (g/L) for the **batch bioreactors** testing dataset and the corresponding simulation for each output, and respective error (%).

Model	Output	Simulated Max	Experimental Max	Error
MG1655	X	14.57 g/L	9.68 g/L	50.5%
	P	0.0995 g/L	0.0943 g/L	5.6%
	A	3.096 g/L	6.122 g/L	-49.4%
GALG20	X	8.966g/L	8.260 g/L	8.6%
	P	0.0517 g/L	0.0873 g/L	-40.8%
	A	0.0334 g/L	0.1013 g/L	-67.0%

The results presented in Table 3.6 align well with what has been previously observed. The plasmid in the MG1655 model and the biomass in the GALG20 model obtained very similar values to those in the testing dataset, with an associated error of 5.6% and 8.6%, respectively. Acetate was significantly underestimated in both cases (49.4% and 67.0% lower for the MG1655 and GALG20 model, respectively).

Some of the results presented in this section are consistent with those obtained after parameter estimation, namely, the poor performance of both models regarding the prediction of acetate production. A low R^2 value for glucose was also verified in the MG1655 across datasets, but as expected, the model

performed worse using the initial conditions from the testing dataset than from the estimation dataset. Not only were the parameters used in both cases estimated specifically to obtain a better fit to the estimation dataset, but the latter was also considerably different from the testing dataset, resulting in typically lower R^2 values and higher errors.

3.2.3.2 Shake Flask

The methodology in the previous section was then applied to the three shake flask datasets derived from the experimental part of this work, again simulating it using the parameter values stated in Table 3.2. The simulation and shake flask results are also compared according to strain and output (represented in Appendix B, Figure B.5).

Figure 3.21 (DH5 α), 3.22 (MG1655), and 3.23 (GALG20) shows a comparison between the simulation datasets (in black) using the estimation datasets (dashed lines) as well as the shake flask data (full line). As expected, the datasets are significantly different in all aspects, in particular, the biomass, plasmid and acetate produced and the rate of glucose consumption.

Noticeably, all predictions differed quite significantly from the experimental values. This was expected in this analysis, as the estimating and testing datasets were derived from different operational conditions. In particular, differences in culture volume, as well as the lack of oxygen and pH control in the shake flask experiments, can easily explain these differences. Nevertheless, the simulation behaviour can still provide useful insights into the behaviour of the model. Additionally, the simulations did not consider the adaptation phase verified in all shake flask cultures, particularly MG1655, further contributing to the observed deviations.

Overall, the models predicted much higher final concentrations of plasmid and biomass than the actual concentrations in the shake flask cultures. For acetate, the reverse occurred, with the simulations producing lower amounts of acetate. These discrepancies can be broadly attributed to operational differences between bioreactors and shake flask conditions, differences that are not captured in the parameters used. The impact of these conditions appears to be more significant here than in the previous analysis.

The DH5 α model (Figure 3.21) was the only one where the plasmid and biomass concentrations were still increasing by the end of the simulation, with GALG20 (Figure 3.23) and MG1655 (Figure 3.22) achieving a plateau after glucose and acetate depletion. This would reflect the typical behaviour of plasmid-producing cultures, even if the values were much higher than the actual shake flask measurements. In the simulation, GALG20 only accumulated 0.03 g/L of acetate (Table 3.7), which was a considerable difference from the measured values. Due to this small acetate production, it was quickly consumed after glucose depletion, causing the culture to plateau at around hour seven.

Figure 3.21: Comparison of data used for estimation and respective simulation with data used for **shake flask** testing and respective simulation for **DH5 α** . The dashed lines represent the experimental data and the fitting obtained during parameter estimations, and the solid lines refer to the experimental data and the fitting obtained for shake flask testing. The figure displays time-series data for biomass (top left, green), glucose (top right, blue), pDNA (bottom left, red), and acetate (bottom right, yellow) concentrations for each strain.

In the MG1655 simulation, acetate was produced at significantly lower values than observed experimentally, and was subsequently consumed. This simulation resulted in the largest errors for biomass ($\sim 590\%$) and plasmid ($\sim 800\%$). These large errors can be partially attributed to the long adaptation period of MG1655 in shake flask (discussed previously), which led to particularly low experimental values. However, the main reason for such large errors is that, unlike in batch bioreactor, in shake flask GALG20 outperforms MG1655 [44] [44]. Because the parameters were estimated using batch bioreactor data, in which MG1655 slightly outperformed GALG20, in addition to the particularly poor performance of MG1655 in shake flask experiments, the errors obtained between simulated and shake flask results

Figure 3.22: Comparison of data used for estimation and respective simulation with data used for **shake flask** testing and respective simulation for **MG1655**. The dashed lines represent the experimental data and the fitting obtained during parameter estimations, and the solid lines refer to the experimental data and the fitting obtained for shake flask testing. The figure displays time-series data for biomass (top left, green), glucose (top right, blue), pDNA (bottom left, red), and acetate (bottom right, yellow) concentrations for each strain.

were particularly large. Glucose was fully consumed in the simulation, as was acetate, which only started being consumed when glucose was depleted. The behaviour of the model was similar to the estimation model, but it largely did not reflect the experimental results of the shake flask cultures.

DH5 α presented similar behaviour to the previous strains, but, as it occurred in the estimation model, the simulated production and consumption rates were lower than for MG1655. This allowed for a lower error (Table 3.7) to be obtained regarding biomass (229.5%), plasmid (335.4%) and acetate (-47.2%) compared to MG1655. This was the only model that presented a simulated final concentration of acetate different from zero.

Figure 3.23: Comparison of data used for estimation and respective simulation with data used for **shake flask** testing and respective simulation for **GALG20**. The dashed lines represent the experimental data and the fitting obtained during parameter estimations, and the solid lines refer to the experimental data and the fitting obtained for shake flask testing. The figure displays time-series data for biomass (top left, green), glucose (top right, blue), pDNA (bottom left, red), and acetate (bottom right, yellow) concentrations for each strain.

Initially, the simulations were constructed using the predicted values of each variable at a corresponding experimental time point. However, considering the reduced time points of these datasets, this was changed in order to improve accuracy. The largest difference was observed in the $DH5\alpha$ simulation. In the first scenario, the glucose seemed to be consumed at a much reduced rate because it appeared to decrease linearly from its value at nine hours to zero at 24 hours, misrepresenting the depletion time of the CS. Similarly, the acetate appeared to be continuously growing, because the concentration at hour nine (last experimental point before the end of the experiment) was lower than the concentration at the end of the experiment. This can highlight the importance of building accurate models and building them from informative and complete data. Particularly in the case of shake flask cultures, this can be limited by the amount of media available for sample extraction, hindering the accurate monitoring of cultures. However, this could be facilitated through the development and implementation of digital methods.

Table 3.7: Comparison of maximum values (g/L) for the **shake flask** testing dataset and the corresponding simulation for each output, and respective error (%).

Model	Output	Simulated Max	Experimental Max	Error
DH5α	X	6.72 g/L	2.04 g/L	229.5%
	P	0.0512 g/L	0.0118 g/L	335.4%
	A	5.602 g/L	10.615 g/L	-47.2%
MG1655	X	11.48 g/L	1.66 g/L	591.3%
	P	0.0795 g/L	0.0089 g/L	795.6%
	A	2.675 g/L	9.405 g/L	-71.6%
GALG20	X	7.25 g/L	2.11 g/L	244.1%
	P	0.0420 g/L	0.0126 g/L	232.7%
	A	0.0334 g/L	7.7950 g/L	-99.6%

Overall, the results demonstrate that the models were not able to accurately predict the behaviour of the variables in shake flask cultures. As previously discussed, this result was expected considering the different operational conditions between shake flask cultures and batch bioreactor systems. Furthermore, the behaviour observed in the shake flask cultures—particularly with respect to acetate accumulation and glucose consumption—deviated from previously reported results, further contributing to the discrepancies between the simulations and experimental data.

In these sections, simulations were performed using the initial conditions measured in datasets designated for testing, originating from two batch bioreactors cultures with either MG1655 $\Delta\text{endA}\Delta\text{recA}$ or GALG20 and three shake flask cultures using DH5 α , MG1655 $\Delta\text{endA}\Delta\text{recA}$, or GALG20. However, the intended application of the model does not rely on experimentally measured initial conditions, as this would require performing the experimental setup for every initial prediction. Ideally, these conditions should be assumed or inferred based on prior experiments or on defined process specifications. In practice, however, this can be challenging, as measured values often deviate from intended ones. For instance, although glucose was consistently intended to begin at 20g/L, the actual measured initial concentrations varied between 16 g/L and approximately 27 g/L, for all datasets. This variability highlights a broader issue of reproducibility commonly found in bioprocesses, particularly in cell culture systems [124], and further contributes to the difficulty of developing robust and generalizable models.

3.2.4 Impact of initial conditions

The initial conditions used for MG1655 and GALG20 are described in Table 3.8, where the values that were assumed due to missing data were highlighted in blue. DH5 α was excluded for this analysis due to the overconfidence observed for this model, likely resulting from the low data points used in estima-

tion. For most datasets, the initial concentration of plasmid was not measured and had to be assumed. Similarly, the initial acetate value was also not measured in the shake flask cultures. Although different simulation results were observed in the previous section using the same parameters but different initial conditions, these conditions differed across multiple variables, making it difficult to establish a direct correlation between input values and model behaviour. Additionally, as mentioned previously, the estimated parameters cannot be linked with biological differences across strains or directly with literature values. Nevertheless, the effect of varying initial concentrations on model outputs was further performed in order to assess how these differences connect to experimental outcomes.

Most cultures began with a biomass concentration below $0.1g$, except the batch bioreactors simulations (MG1655 and GALG20). Only the estimation datasets for the previously mentioned strains contained the initial concentrations of plasmid, both close to 6.0 mg/L , the remaining ones being assumed to correspond to 1.0 mg/L . The glucose concentration was higher in the datasets used for estimation than in the simulations, and only in the estimation dataset for MG1655 was the initial acetate concentration different from zero.

Table 3.8: Initial concentrations of biomass (X), plasmid (P), glucose (S), and acetate (A) for each estimation and testing in **batch** (B) and **shake flask** (SF). Highlighted in blue are the values that were assumed.

Strain	X (g/L)	P (g/L)	S (g/L)	A (g/L)
MG1655	$8.5E - 02$	$5.8E - 03$	$2.2E + 01$	$2.7E - 02$
MG1655 (B)	$2.8E - 01$	$1.0E - 03$	$2.0E + 01$	0
MG1655 (SF)	$8.4E - 02$	$1.0E - 03$	$1.6E + 01$	0
GALG20	$8.5E - 02$	$6.1E - 03$	$2.7E + 01$	0
GALG20 (B)	$1.2E - 01$	$1.0E - 03$	$2.0E + 01$	0
GALG20 (SF)	$9.4E - 02$	$1.0E - 03$	$1.6E + 01$	0

The purpose of this section was not to quantify the precise impact of specific variations in initial concentrations on the final values of the model output; rather, it aimed to establish broad trends and correlations between the differences in input values and the resulting simulations.

For each model, three different initial concentrations of glucose were tested (10 , 20 , and 30 g/L), while keeping the initial concentration of biomass, plasmid, and acetate of 0.1 g/L , 2.0 mg/L , and 0 . Using the 30 g/L simulation and its conditions, two other initial concentrations of plasmid were tested, 8.0 mg/L and 0.5 mg/L . Using the 20 g/L simulation, two other initial concentrations of biomass were simulated, 0.5 g/L and 0.01 g/L , maintaining the other conditions equal. Finally, using the 10 g/L simulation, two additional initial concentrations of acetate were tested, 1.0 g/L and 0.1 g/L .

The results were consistent across the two models, that is, the changes in initial conditions had the same effect in the GALG20 and MG1655 models. The results are presented in Figure 3.24 (MG1655) and Figure 3.25 (GALG20). The simulations related to the variation of initial plasmid concentrations

were not represented since they were found to induce very reduced variance in the output of the model, and hence were removed for better visualisation of the remaining simulations.

Figure 3.24: Simulations of **MG1655** model using different initial values. The base conditions of biomass, plasmid and acetate corresponded to 0.1 g/L, 2.0 mg/L, and 0 g/L, and they were tested at different glucose concentrations (S): 10 g/L (pink), 20 g/L (violet), and 30 g/L (black). Two other initial biomass concentrations (X) were tested at 20 g/L of glucose, 0.5 g/L (violet, dash-dot line), and 0.01 g/L (violet, dashed line). Two other initial acetate concentrations (A) were tested at 10 g/L of glucose: 1.0 g/L (pink, dash-dot line) and 0.05 g/L (pink, dashed line). The figure displays time-series data for biomass (top left), glucose (top right), pDNA (bottom left), and acetate (bottom right).

In the MG1655 model, it was observed that despite glucose was consumed at a faster rate than in GALG20, it reached a plateau later in the simulation. This was attributed to the higher amount of acetate produced, which needed to be fully consumed before the system could stabilise. As GALG20 produced very little acetate, the plateau was reached earlier in the simulation. This was also observed in the previous analysis, in which MG1655 and GALG20 had similar biomass and glucose initial concentration (Table 3.8).

This can be explained by the difference in the estimated parameters (Table 3.2) for the MG1655 and GALG20 models. In particular, the value of μ_{maxS} was significantly higher for MG1655 ($1.20 h^{-1}$) compared to GALG20 ($0.38 h^{-1}$). According to the equation describing the consumption rate of the

model (Equation 2.10), this parameter is positively correlated with the consumption rate, while $Y_{X/S}$, lower in MG1655 (0.144 g/g) than GALG20 (0.257 g/g), is negatively correlated with the consumption rate, meaning higher values lead to faster substrate consumption.

Figure 3.25: Simulations of **GALG20** model using different initial values. The base conditions of biomass, plasmid and acetate corresponded to 0.1 g/L, 2.0 mg/L, and 0 g/L, and they were tested at different glucose concentrations (S): 10 g/L (cyan), 20 g/L (teal), and 30 g/L (black). Two other initial biomass concentrations (X) were tested at 20 g/L of glucose, 0.5 g/L (teal, dash-dot line), and 0.01 g/L (teal, dashed line). Two other initial acetate concentrations (A) were tested at 10 g/L of glucose: 1.0 g/L (cyan, dash-dot line) and 0.05 g/L (cyan, dashed line). The figure displays time-series data for biomass (top left), glucose (top right), pDNA (bottom left), and acetate (bottom right).

In the MG1655 simulations, it was possible to observe a positive correlation between initial glucose concentration and higher accumulation of acetate. This is aligned with the mechanism of acetate formation in glucose cultures, where high concentrations of glucose in aerobic conditions inhibit respiration and promote acetate production [27]. On the other hand, GALG20 accumulated similarly reduced amounts of acetate in all simulations. The low accumulation of acetate in GALG20 cultures when compared to MG1655 cultures is also reflected in these simulations, and is in accordance with the characteristics of this strains [44] and literature results (Table 1.1). This is also visible in Table 3.6 and 3.7, where the maximum concentration of acetate for GALG20 was the same, 0.0334 g/L, and MG1655 achieved a

maximum concentration of 2.7 in shake flask (Table 3.7) and 3.1 in batch bioreactor (Table 3.6) g/L . The highest accumulation occurred in the batch bioreactor testing, whose dataset contained a higher initial glucose concentration than the shake flask dataset (Table 3.8).

The difference in acetate accumulation between strains is also reflected through the structure of the model (Equation 2.11) and estimated parameter values. For GALG20, the low value of μ_{maxS} decreases acetate production ($Y_{PA/S}$ is equal), while the low value of $Y_{X/A}$ (0.60 g/g) and high value of μ_{maxA} (2.22 h^{-1}) increase its consumption. For comparison, the values of $Y_{X/A}$ and μ_{maxA} for the MG1655 model were 3.94 g/g and 0.14 h^{-1} , respectively. Interestingly, an increase in the initial acetate concentration did not affect the model negatively, it instead resulted in additional biomass and plasmid being produced, likely as a result of this extra acetate being consumed and used as a CS.

Furthermore, in the datasets used for estimation, the final concentrations of plasmid and biomass were slightly inferior in GALG20 compared to MG1655, despite the first culture initialising at a higher glucose concentration (Table 3.8). While this does not reflect the supposed improved ability for biomass and plasmid growth of GALG20, the estimation data obtained by Lopes et al. (2015) [47] and the testing data obtained by Gonçalves et al. (2014) [24]) are aligned in this. This highlights the impact of using different scales in these cultures, and demonstrates the challenges in scaling up these processes.

Note that this analysis can be valid for small variations, but cannot be used as a reliable prediction of the evolution of variables for wide ranges of initial conditions, even if large variations were used, in the case of glucose. The parameters used in these simulations originated under specific experimental conditions and may not transfer to cultures with significant differences.

4

Conclusions and Future Work

Contents

4.1	Final Conclusions	81
4.2	Limitations and Future Work	84

4.1 Final Conclusions

This work aimed to develop, analyse and test a kinetic model describing plasmid production in the *E. coli* cultures using two common laboratory strains, DH5 α and MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA, and the engineered strain, GALG20, with glucose as a carbon source. To achieve this, experimental data on shake flask cultures of the three strains was obtained. A framework was developed to aid experimentalists in the early phases of process design regarding plasmid production. Plasmids can serve as carriers of genetic materials and be used in vaccine delivery, gene therapies, and the manufacturing of bioproducts [18]. The main bottleneck to achieving large-scale production is the scale-up challenges related to the lack of reproducibility and consequent difficulty in fully complying with GMP standards [74]. Fostering process understanding by developing digital tools, such as mechanistic models, through a DoE framework can aid in monitoring and process control as well as reduction of experimental workload [68].

The cultures for each strain were grown in a chemically defined medium [35] with 20 g/L of glucose, in duplicates. The samples taken throughout the experiment were analysed in order to obtain time-course data on the concentrations of biomass, plasmid, glucose, and acetate. Three datasets, one for each strain in 20 g/L of glucose under batch conditions, were used to obtain the model and the corresponding parameter set describing the evolution of these variables. The kinetic model was adapted from previous work by Lopes et al. (2014) [26], which utilised ten parameters to model the four variables. A modelling and analysis framework was implemented using Python, involving an identifiability analysis using the parameter importance and collinearity index to determine identifiable subsets. By minimising the WRSS value, the parameter values for the identifiable subsets were determined, from which the best subset was selected. The parameter set used in subsequent analysis contained the estimated parameters and the fixed parameters. The IC was determined for the estimated parameters using the covariance matrix, and an uncertainty analysis using the Latin Hypercube Sampling method was performed. By applying the Morris screening method, the effect of each parameter on each output was assessed. Following this analysis, the datasets obtained from the shake flask experiments for the three strains, and datasets from batch experiments for MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA and GALG20 were tested using the respective model for each strain. Lastly, the model was simulated using different initial conditions in order to connect the structure of the model and the obtained parameter sets to the corresponding simulation results. This was also linked to experimental results and explained through known biological phenomena and the differences between strains.

Originally, the data derived from the shake flask experiments were meant to be analysed similarly to the batch data from the three strains. With this, a group of parameter sets that would model the evolution of the shake flask cultures could be obtained. However, due to the fact that not enough data points could be extracted from the experiments, the data was used to test the models obtained from batch data.

Regarding the shake flask experiments, the GALG20 strain produced the most biomass and plasmid, achieving a final concentration of 2.11 g/L and 12.6 mg/L after 24 hours, respectively. This corresponded to a specific plasmid yield of 5.99 mg/g_{DCW}, and a final concentration of glucose and acetate of 5.89 g/L and 7.80 g/L, respectively. Thus, it was observed that indeed this strain produced the most plasmid and biomass, consumed the most glucose and produced the least amount of acetate. DH5 α produced the most acetate, 10.6 g/L, and consumed the least glucose, 6.10 g/L. It produced comparable results to GALG20 regarding biomass, achieving 2.04 g/L, and specific and volumetric plasmid yield, which corresponded to 5.76 mg/g_{DCW} and 11.8 g/L. MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA achieved the least concentration of plasmid, 8.88 g/L, and biomass, 1.66 g/L, as well as lowest specific plasmid yield, 5.35 mg/g_{DCW}. The final acetate and glucose concentrations were 9.41 g/L and 5.05 g/L, respectively. The shake flask experiments yielded reasonable results for DH5 α and MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA, being comparable to literature values [44] [24], considering the lower volume, adaptation period, and use of chemically defined media [122]. On the other hand, GALG20 did not demonstrate the increased plasmid and biomass production capacity reported in literature [44] [24]. However, under these conditions, data extraction through the deployed methods of analysis was limited and hindered the use of this data for modelling purposes.

Through model analyses, identifiable subsets were determined, which all contained a maximum of four parameters. The corresponding parameter set obtained for each (strain) model was compared to the experimental data. The best results were obtained for the DH5 α , in which all R^2 values were over 0.97. Although these results were not deemed reliable due to the reduced number of data points used in the analysis, it is a good indication that the model can estimate parameters that accurately reflect the given data. For GALG20 and MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA, the R^2 values for biomass and plasmid were at or above \sim 0.80, while glucose or acetate did not reach 0.50 in either case. The estimated IC were acceptable, all being at or below 5%. This accuracy is not related to the true biological values of the estimated parameters, it simply reflects the ability of the model to estimate parameters capable of describing the datasets provided. Regarding the uncertainty and global sensitivity analyses, it was observed that while the prediction of acetate had a consistently low robustness associated to it, this variable and the associated parameters were fundamental for understanding plasmid production and its modelling efforts.

For batch testing, the R^2 values for plasmid reached \sim 0.50 in both models (0.67 in GALG20 and 0.49 in MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA), and the GALG20 model also achieved a R^2 value of 0.96 for glucose. The remaining values were below 0.50. The simulated and experimental differences between final concentrations of biomass and plasmid, and maximum concentration of acetate, were calculated. Only the plasmid in MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA and the biomass in GALG20 had errors below 10%, corresponding to 5.6% and 8.6%, respectively. In MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA, the biomass was about 50% higher, while the

simulated maximum concentration of acetate was half the experimental value. In GALG20, the plasmid was simulated about 41% below the experimental value, and the acetate was 67% lower. In shake flask cultures, the simulations were significantly different from the experimental results, resulting in large over-estimations, with biomass errors between 229.5% and 591.3% and plasmid errors between 232.7% and 795.6%. The acetate production was also underestimated in all cases, from 47.2% in DH5 α to 99.6% in GALG20. The significant discrepancies were largely attributed to the difference in operation modes. The results obtained in the analysis through simulating different initial conditions followed the characteristics of the two strains analysed and past experimental results [24]. The increase in glucose demonstrated a positive correlation to increased biomass, plasmid, and acetate production. The biomass and plasmid concentration showed little effect on the final concentrations of the simulation, while acetate showed some positive correlation with higher final concentrations of biomass and plasmid.

In the kinetic model, the model showed an appropriate predictive capacity for MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA and GALG20 regarding plasmid and biomass during estimation, but this was largely not transferred to test the model for other batch experiments. In shake flask cultures, the model demonstrated no predictive ability as a result of the large discrepancy between the batch bioreactors data used for estimating the parameters and the shake flask data tested. Considering the model structure, the parameter sets obtained for MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA and GALG20 reflected the increase of acetate production with glucose concentration in the first strain [27] and the ability of the latter strain to produce significantly less acetate as a result of the *pgi* gene knockout [44]. Considering the model structure, the parameter sets reflected the typical relationships of glucose and acetate in plasmid-producing cultures, but did not reflect the increased production potential of GALG20 compared to MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA, because this is only observed in shake flask conditions, and not in batch bioreactor conditions [24].

As previously mentioned, this work presents a comprehensive kinetic modelling framework for plasmid DNA production in three *E. coli* strains—DH5 α , MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA, and GALG20—cultivated on glucose. Despite limitations in data quantity and predictive accuracy, especially under shake flask conditions, the study successfully established a pipeline for model formulation, parameter identifiability analysis, estimation, and global sensitivity assessment. The models for MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA and GALG20 showed acceptable predictive ability during the fitting phase for biomass and plasmid, and key parameters related to acetate metabolism were shown to influence plasmid production. These results underline the biological relevance of including acetate-related terms in kinetic modelling of plasmid systems. While the models did not generalise well to new datasets, largely due to operational differences and data limitations, they nonetheless enabled a structured exploration of parameter sensitivity and strain-specific differences. This framework contributes a valuable foundation for further refinement and for developing strain-adaptive models during early-stage process design.

This study aimed to develop a modelling and analysis tool that could support experimentalists in

early-stage process development, improving understanding of system dynamics and aiding decision-making. While the models showed limited applicability towards this purpose, particularly under shake flask conditions, the framework successfully established a pipeline for model formulation, parameter identifiability analysis, estimation, and global sensitivity assessment. Within this pipeline, experimentalists can identify sensitive parameters, evaluate model robustness, and simulate process changes, all of which contribute to experimental design and interpretation. Despite limited applicability regarding its use as a tool in early-stage development for experimentalists, it established a pipeline for formulating models, parameter identifiability, estimation, and global sensitivity assessment.

In conclusion, this work demonstrates that even with sparse and heterogeneous data, a well-defined kinetic modelling approach can generate biologically meaningful insights and provide a scalable foundation for future modelling efforts that aim to support digital bioprocess development.

4.2 Limitations and Future Work

The main limitation of this work is the low quality of the predictions, as reflected by the low values of R^2 obtained in most fittings. Although the shake flask fittings were not expected to be accurate, the batch experiments used for testing also resulted in poor fittings. Additionally, not all models could be reliably analysed and tested due to the limited amount of data available.

This main limitation is caused by the data used, both for estimating and testing purposes. The data could be limited according to its quantity or quality. During parameter estimation, the quantity of data posed an issue regarding the DH5 α , as the datasets contained only five data points. For the other strains, the issue lied in fact that the cultures did not reflect the usual advantages associated with GALG20 when compared to MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA. For batch and shake flask testing, all datasets contained eight or fewer data points with all variable measurements. In batch cultures, the deficiency in data can be solved by increasing the number of samples taken, although at the cost of time and resources from experimentalists. Several methods have been developed and implemented in plasmid cultures that can aid in monitoring and controlling the process. Digital methods based on statistical tools that can reduce the experimental workload required for appropriate data extraction, for example, relying on the combination of Partial Least Squares (PLS) regression with NIR [125] [47], or Mid-Infrared (MIR) [48] (or high-throughput MIR [126] [127]) spectroscopy for real-time on-line monitoring and high-throughput analysis, respectively. In shake flask cultures, the low sampling issue often cannot be solved simply by increasing the number of samples, as they typically involve a temporary halt in incubation, and the volume available for sampling is limited. A more immediate solution to this would be to increase the volume of the shake flask or to run parallel experiments and alternate sampling, but this does not address the problem of experimental burden.

However, shake flask experiments, in the context of developing and implementing large-scale manufacturing of pDNA, are mostly used during the early stages of strain and vector development and screening. This means that there is a wide diversity of data from different strains being studied or engineered before being selected for batch or fed-batch cultivations, which will then be scaled up. Additionally, reproducibility studies, which produce larger volumes of similar data, are not the main focus in this stage of process design, and so comprehensive data availability might be scarce. Because of this, models that can incorporate the small differences between strains and reflect them onto kinetic parameters can be a promising approach.

For future work, efforts should be placed towards modelling pDNA production using multiple *E. coli* strains under different operation modes, carbon sources and initial conditions. This approach could rely on the genetic differences between the strains, quantified through metabolic models such as FBA or MFA. By connecting metabolic models with kinetic models, significant insights on the biological workings of the strains and the impacts on the evolution of the main variables can be gained, while creating a model that can be easily adaptable to different strains. As previously mentioned, this would make particular sense when addressing shake flask experiments and early batch or fed-batch experiments, when there is a large variability of strains and conditions. Naturally, this would still require the production of quality data in sufficient amounts. Reliable and reproducible methods should be developed, ideally based on chemically defined mediums, whose composition can be considered in the metabolic model. An approach like this used at the early stages of process development could lead to a solid basis for modelling purposes and process understanding that could facilitate the scale-up process, while diminishing experimental workload.

Bibliography

- [1] J. LEDERBERG, "Cell Genetics and Hereditary Symbiosis," <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.1952.32.4.403>, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 403–430, oct 1952. [Online]. Available: <https://journals.physiology.org/doi/10.1152/physrev.1952.32.4.403>
- [2] D. R. Helinski, "A Brief History of Plasmids," *EcoSal Plus*, vol. 10, no. 1, dec 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://journals.asm.org/journal/ecosalplus>
- [3] W. Hayes, "Introduction: What are episomes and plasmids?" pp. 4–11, 5 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/9780470715345.ch1><https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9780470715345.ch1><https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/9780470715345.ch1>
- [4] T. Watanabe, "Infective heredity of multiple drug resistance in bacteria," *Bacteriological Reviews*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 87–115, 1963. [Online]. Available: <https://journals.asm.org/doi/abs/10.1128/br.27.1.87-115.1963>
- [5] W. Goebel and D. R. Helinski, "Generation of higher multiple circular dna forms in bacteria." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, vol. 61, pp. 1406–1413, 12 1968. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pnas.org/doi/abs/10.1073/pnas.61.4.1406>
- [6] S. N. Cohen, A. C. Chang, H. W. Boyer, and R. B. Helling, "Construction of biologically functional bacterial plasmids in vitro," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 70, pp. 3240–3244, 11 1973. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pnas.org/doi/abs/10.1073/pnas.70.11.3240>
- [7] C. Yanisch-Perron, J. Vieira, and J. Messing, "Improved m13 phage cloning vectors and host strains: nucleotide sequences of the m13mpl8 and puc19 vectors," *Gene*, vol. 33, pp. 103–119, 1 1985.
- [8] "Recombinant dna in the lab — smithsonian institution." [Online]. Available: <https://www.si.edu/spotlight/birth-of-biotech/recombinant-dna-in-the-lab>

- [9] "Process for producing biologically functional molecular chimeras - patent us-4237224-a - pubchem." [Online]. Available: <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/patent/US-4237224-A#section=Abstract>
- [10] S. Jr, "Process for producing biologically functional molecular chimeras," 1 1979.
- [11] E. Harrison and M. A. Brockhurst, "Plasmid-mediated horizontal gene transfer is a coevolutionary process," *Trends in Microbiology*, vol. 20, pp. 262–267, 6 2012.
- [12] S. M. Opal and A. Pop-Vicas, "18 - molecular mechanisms of antibiotic resistance in bacteria," in *Mandell, Douglas, and Bennett's Principles and Practice of Infectious Diseases (Eighth Edition)*, eighth edition ed., J. E. Bennett, R. Dolin, and M. J. Blaser, Eds. Philadelphia: W.B. Saunders, 2015, pp. 235–251.e3. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9781455748013000187>
- [13] S. Chattopadhyay and E. V. Sokurenko, "Evolution of pathogenic escherichia coli," *Escherichia coli: Pathotypes and Principles of Pathogenesis: Second Edition*, pp. 45–71, 1 2013.
- [14] E. Raleigh and K. Low, "Conjugation," in *Brenner's Encyclopedia of Genetics (Second Edition)*, second edition ed., S. Maloy and K. Hughes, Eds. San Diego: Academic Press, 2013, pp. 144–151. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B97801237498400003211>
- [15] D. M. F. Prazeres and G. A. Monteiro, "Plasmid biopharmaceuticals," *Microbiology Spectrum*, vol. 2, 11 2014. [Online]. Available: [/doi/pdf/10.1128/microbiolspec.plas-0022-2014?download=true](https://doi.org/10.1128/microbiolspec.plas-0022-2014?download=true)
- [16] S. Gupta and L. Yel, "Molecular biology and genetic engineering," *Middleton's Allergy: Principles and Practice: Eighth Edition*, vol. 1-2, pp. 162–183, 1 2014.
- [17] M. Schmeer, T. Buchholz, and M. Schleef, "Plasmid dna manufacturing for indirect and direct clinical applications," *Human gene therapy*, vol. 28, pp. 856–861, 10 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28826233/>
- [18] D. Prazeres, "The supporting role of plasmids in gene & cell therapy," *Cell and Gene Therapy Insights*, vol. 09, pp. 755–762, 7 2023.
- [19] M. P. Hirakawa, R. Krishnakumar, J. A. Timlin, J. P. Carney, and K. S. Butler, "Gene editing and crispr in the clinic: current and future perspectives," *Bioscience reports*, vol. 40, 4 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32207531/>

- [20] D. H. Martínez-Puente, J. J. Pérez-Trujillo, L. M. Zavala-Flores, A. García-García, A. Villanueva-Olivo, H. Rodríguez-Rocha, J. Valdés, O. Saucedo-Cárdenas, R. M. de Oca-Luna, and M. de Jesús Loera-Arias, "Plasmid dna for therapeutic applications in cancer," *Pharmaceutics*, vol. 14, p. 1861, 9 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9503848/>
- [21] A. Moretti, M. Ponzio, C. A. Nicolette, I. Y. Tcherepanova, A. Biondi, and C. F. Magnani, "The past, present, and future of non-viral car t cells," *Frontiers in immunology*, vol. 13, 6 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35757746/>
- [22] A. Hamann, A. Nguyen, and A. K. Pannier, "Nucleic acid delivery to mesenchymal stem cells: a review of nonviral methods and applications," *Journal of biological engineering*, vol. 13, 1 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30675180/>
- [23] J. Ohlson, "Plasmid manufacture is the bottleneck of the genetic medicine revolution," *Drug discovery today*, vol. 25, pp. 1891–1893, 11 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33075470/>
- [24] G. A. Gonçalves, K. L. Prather, G. A. Monteiro, A. E. Carnes, and D. M. Prazeres, "Plasmid dna production with escherichia coli galg20, a pgi-gene knockout strain: Fermentation strategies and impact on downstream processing," *Journal of Biotechnology*, vol. 186, p. 119–127, Jul 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168165614002892>
- [25] K. J. Prather, S. Sagar, J. Murphy, and M. Chartrain, "Industrial scale production of plasmid dna for vaccine and gene therapy: plasmid design, production, and purification," *Enzyme and Microbial Technology*, vol. 33, pp. 865–883, 12 2003. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0141022903002059>
- [26] M. B. Lopes, G. Martins, and C. R. Calado, "Kinetic modeling of plasmid bioproduction in escherichia coli dh5a cultures over different carbon-source compositions," *Journal of biotechnology*, vol. 186, pp. 38–48, 9 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24998768/>
- [27] C. P. A. Alves, S. O. D. Duarte, G. A. Monteiro, and D. M. F. Prazeres, "Use of an e. coli pgi knockout strain as a plasmid producer," vol. 28, pp. 38–42–38–42, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.biopharminternational.com/view/use-e-coli-pgi-knockout-strain-plasmid-producer>
- [28] T. Scholz, V. V. Lopes, and C. R. Calado, "High-throughput analysis of the plasmid bioproduction process in escherichia coli by ftir spectroscopy," *Biotechnology and bioengineering*, vol. 109, pp. 2279–2285, 9 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22495516/>

- [29] M. K. Danquah and G. M. Forde, "Development of a pilot-scale bacterial fermentation for plasmid-based biopharmaceutical production using a stoichiometric medium," *Biotechnology and Bioprocess Engineering*, vol. 13, pp. 158–167, 3 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12257-007-0080-2>
- [30] T. Silva, P. Lima, M. Roxo-Rosa, S. Hageman, L. P. Fonseca, and C. R. C. Calado, "Prediction of dynamic plasmid production by recombinant escherichia coli fed-batch cultivations with a generalized regression neural network," *Chemical and Biochemical Engineering Quarterly*, vol. 23, pp. 419–427, 12 2009.
- [31] J. N. Phue, J. L. Sang, L. Trinh, and J. Shiloach, "Modified escherichia coli b (bl21), a superior producer of plasmid dna compared with escherichia coli k (dh5a)," *Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, vol. 101, pp. 831–836, 1 2008. [Online]. Available: [/doi/pdf/10.1002/bit.21973https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/bit.21973https://analyticalsciencejournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/bit.21973](https://doi/pdf/10.1002/bit.21973https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/bit.21973https://analyticalsciencejournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/bit.21973)
- [32] M. Wunderlich, H. Taymaz-Nikerel, G. Gosset, O. T. Ramírez, and A. R. Lara, "Effect of growth rate on plasmid dna production and metabolic performance of engineered escherichia coli strains," *Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering*, vol. 117, pp. 336–342, 3 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389172313003083>
- [33] A. E. Carnes, C. P. Hodgson, and J. A. Williams, "Inducible escherichia coli fermentation for increased plasmid dna production," *Biotechnology and Applied Biochemistry*, vol. 45, pp. 155–166, 11 2006. [Online]. Available: [/doi/pdf/10.1042/BA20050223https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1042/BA20050223https://iubmb.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1042/BA20050223](https://doi/pdf/10.1042/BA20050223https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1042/BA20050223https://iubmb.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1042/BA20050223)
- [34] R. Munguía-Soto, A. García-Rendón, A. Garibay-Escobar, P. Guerrero-Germán, and A. Tejeda-Mansir, "Segregated growth kinetics of escherichia coli dh5a-nh36 in exponential-fed perfusion culture for pdna vaccine production," *Biotechnology and applied biochemistry*, vol. 62, pp. 795–805, 11 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25556882/>
- [35] K. Listner, L. Bentley, J. Okonkowski, C. Kistler, R. Wnek, A. Caparoni, B. Junker, D. Robinson, P. Salmon, and M. Chartrain, "Development of a highly productive and scalable plasmid dna production platform," *Biotechnology progress*, vol. 22, pp. 1335–1345, 9 2006. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17022672/>
- [36] G. M. Borja, E. M. Mora, B. Barrón, G. Gosset, O. T. Ramírez, and A. R. Lara, "Engineering escherichia coli to increase plasmid dna production in high cell-density cultivations in batch mode," *Microbial Cell Factories*, vol. 11, p. 132, 9 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://www.scopus.com/record/display.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84866297923&origin=inward>

- [37] M. Hoare, M. S. Levy, D. G. Bracewell, S. D. Doig, S. Kong, N. Titchener-Hooker, J. M. Ward, and P. Dunnill, "Bioprocess engineering issues that would be faced in producing a dna vaccine at up to 100 m³ fermentation scale for an influenza pandemic," *Biotechnology Progress*, vol. 21, p. 1577, 11 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7161863/>
- [38] P. Almanac, "Overcoming pdna supply challenges for mrna manufacturing," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pharmasalmanac.com/articles/overcoming-pdna-supply-challenges-for-mrna-manufacturing>
- [39] M. Consulting, "Challenges and regulatory requirements in plasmid dna manufacturing: Ensuring safety, quality, and compliance – mmr consulting," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://mmrengineering.com/challenges-and-regulatory-requirements-in-plasmid-dna-manufacturing-ensuring-safety-quality-and-compliance>
- [40] G. V. Research, "Plasmid dna manufacturing market size, share report, 2030," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/plasmid-dna-manufacturing-market-report>
- [41] "U.s. plasmid dna manufacturing market size to hit usd 3,630 mn by 2034," 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/us-plasmid-dna-manufacturing-market>
- [42] "Global cancer burden growing, amidst mounting need for services." [Online]. Available: <https://www.who.int/news/item/01-02-2024-global-cancer-burden-growing--amidst-mounting-need-for-services>
- [43] "Strain information of e. coli k-12 mg1655." [Online]. Available: <https://www.genome.wisc.edu/resources/strains.htm>
- [44] G. A. Gonçalves, D. M. Prazeres, G. A. Monteiro, and K. L. Prather, "De novo creation of mg1655-derived e. coli strains specifically designed for plasmid dna production," *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, vol. 97, pp. 611–620, 1 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00253-012-4308-5>
- [45] G. W. Luli and W. R. Strohl, "Comparison of growth, acetate production, and acetate inhibition of escherichia coli strains in batch and fed-batch fermentations," *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, vol. 56, pp. 1004–1011, 1990. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2187400/>
- [46] R. Pandey, N. Kumar, G. A. Monteiro, V. D. Veeranki, and D. M. Prazeres, "Re-engineering of an escherichia coli k-12 strain for the efficient production of recombinant human interferon gamma," *Enzyme and Microbial Technology*, vol. 117, pp. 23–31, 10 2018.

- [47] M. B. Lopes, G. A. Gonçalves, D. Felício-Silva, K. L. Prather, G. A. Monteiro, D. M. Prazeres, and C. R. Calado, "In situ nir spectroscopy monitoring of plasmid production processes: effect of producing strain, medium composition and the cultivation strategy," *Journal of Chemical Technology & Biotechnology*, vol. 90, pp. 255–261, 2 2015. [Online]. Available: [/doi/pdf/10.1002/jctb.4431](https://doi/pdf/10.1002/jctb.4431)<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/jctb.4431><https://scijournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/jctb.4431>
- [48] K. C. Sales, F. Rosa, P. N. Sampaio, L. P. Fonseca, M. B. Lopes, and C. R. Calado, "In situ near-infrared (nir) versus high-throughput mid-infrared (mir) spectroscopy to monitor biopharmaceutical production," *Applied spectroscopy*, vol. 69, pp. 760–772, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25955848/>
- [49] A. E. Carnes, J. M. Luke, J. M. Vincent, A. Schukar, S. Anderson, C. P. Hodgson, and J. A. Williams, "Plasmid dna fermentation strain and process-specific effects on vector yield, quality, and transgene expression," *Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, vol. 108, pp. 354–363, 2 2011. [Online]. Available: [/doi/pdf/10.1002/bit.22936](https://doi/pdf/10.1002/bit.22936)<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/bit.22936><https://analyticalsciencejournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/bit.22936>
- [50] M. Grieves, "Digital twin: Manufacturing excellence through virtual factory replication," 03 2015.
- [51] "50 years ago: "houston, we've had a problem" - nasa." [Online]. Available: <https://www.nasa.gov/history/50-years-ago-houston-weve-had-a-problem/>
- [52] "Digital twins and living models at nasa - nasa technical reports server (ntrs)." [Online]. Available: <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20210023699>
- [53] "Apollo 13: Facts about nasa's near-disaster moon mission — space." [Online]. Available: <https://www.space.com/17250-apollo-13-facts.html>
- [54] M. Singh, E. Fuenmayor, E. P. Hinchy, Y. Qiao, N. Murray, and D. Devine, "Digital twin: Origin to future," *Applied System Innovation 2021, Vol. 4, Page 36*, vol. 4, p. 36, 5 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2571-5577/4/2/36/html><https://www.mdpi.com/2571-5577/4/2/36>
- [55] "Scopus - document search results." [Online]. Available: <https://www.scopus.com/results/results.uri?st1=Digital+Twin&st2=&s=TITLE-ABS-KEY%28Digital+Twin%29&limit=10&origin=resultslist&sort=plf-f&src=s&sot=b&sdt=cl&sessionSearchId=2252e6bba3c1ebd0fa5b0a9146eb238e&yearFrom=2024&yearTo=2024>
- [56] "Digital twins market by technology, twinning type, cyber-to-physical solutions, use cases and applications in industry verticals 2024 - 2029." [Online]. Available: <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/5308850/digital-twins-market-by-technology-twinning?>

utm_source=dynamic&utm_medium=Ci&utm_code=6q68tb&utm_campaign=1366076+-The+Future+of+the+Digital+Twins+Industry+to+2025+in+Manufacturing%2c+Smart+Cities%2c+Automotive%2c+Healthcare+and+Transport&utm_exec=joca220cid

- [57] G. V. Research, "Digital twin market size, share and growth report, 2030," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/digital-twin-market>
- [58] R. A. R. A. Mouha, "Internet of things (iot)," *Journal of Data Analysis and Information Processing*, vol. 09, pp. 77–101, 4 2021. [Online]. Available: http://file.scirp.org/html/3-2870386_108574.htm
<http://www.scirp.org/journal/Paperabs.aspx?PaperID=108574>
- [59] M. Attaran and B. G. Celik, "Digital twin: Benefits, use cases, challenges, and opportunities," *Decision Analytics Journal*, vol. 6, p. 100165, 3 2023.
- [60] Z. Lv and S. Xie, "Artificial intelligence in the digital twins: State of the art, challenges, and future research topics," *Digital Twin*, vol. 1, p. 12, 11 2022.
- [61] A. Fuller, Z. Fan, C. Day, and C. Barlow, "Digital twin: Enabling technologies, challenges and open research," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 108 952–108 971, 2020.
- [62] W. Kritzinger, M. Karner, G. Traar, J. Henjes, and W. Sihn, "Digital twin in manufacturing: A categorical literature review and classification," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 51, no. 11, pp. 1016–1022, 2018, 16th IFAC Symposium on Information Control Problems in Manufacturing INCOM 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405896318316021>
- [63] Q. Qi, F. Tao, T. Hu, N. Anwer, A. Liu, Y. Wei, L. Wang, and A. Y. Nee, "Enabling technologies and tools for digital twin," *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, vol. 58, pp. 3–21, 1 2021.
- [64] F. Tao, J. Cheng, Q. Qi, M. Zhang, H. Zhang, and F. Sui, "Digital twin-driven product design, manufacturing and service with big data," *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 94, pp. 3563–3576, 2 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00170-017-0233-1>
- [65] Q. Qi and F. Tao, "Digital twin and big data towards smart manufacturing and industry 4.0: 360 degree comparison," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 3585–3593, 1 2018.
- [66] "International conference on harmonisation of technical requirements for registration of pharmaceuticals for human use pharmaceutical development q8(r2)," 2009.
- [67] "Digital twin market size& share, growth analysis 2032." [Online]. Available: <https://www.gminsights.com/industry-analysis/digital-twin-market>

- [68] C. L. Gargalo, I. Udugama, K. Pontius, P. C. Lopez, R. F. Nielsen, A. Hasanzadeh, S. S. Mansouri, C. Bayer, H. Junicke, and K. V. Gernaey, "Towards smart biomanufacturing: a perspective on recent developments in industrial measurement and monitoring technologies for bio-based production processes," *Journal of Industrial Microbiology and Biotechnology*, vol. 47, pp. 947–964, 11 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10295-020-02308-1>
- [69] H. Narayanan, M. F. Luna, M. von Stosch, M. N. C. Bournazou, G. Polotti, M. Morbidelli, A. Butté, and M. Sokolov, "Bioprocessing in the digital age: The role of process models," *Biotechnology Journal*, vol. 15, 1 2020.
- [70] J. M. Juran, "Juran on quality by design: The new steps for planning quality into goods ... - j. m. juran - google livros," 1992. [Online]. Available: https://books.google.pt/books?hl=pt-PT&lr=&id=KPUXbZ2Hw1EC&oi=fnd&pg=PR5&dq=Juran+on+Quality+by+Design:+The+New+Steps+for+Planning+Quality+Into&ots=xNW83EJ1rS&sig=aLvAIBEjHws8F46M6zAvDxDtlyU&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Juran%20on%20Quality%20by%20Design%3A%20The%20New%20Steps%20for%20Planning%20Quality%20Into&f=false
- [71] M. A. Khan, L. X. Yu, G. Amidon, S. W. Hoag, J. Polli, G. K. Raju, and J. Woodcock, "Understanding pharmaceutical quality by design," *The AAPS Journal*, vol. 16, p. 771, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4070262/>
- [72] K. V. Gernaey, A. E. Lantz, P. Tufvesson, J. M. Woodley, and G. Sin, "Application of mechanistic models to fermentation and biocatalysis for next-generation processes," *Trends in Biotechnology*, vol. 28, pp. 346–354, 7 2010. [Online]. Available: [https://www.cell.com/action/showFullText?pii=S0167779910000545https://www.cell.com/action/showAbstract?pii=S0167779910000545https://www.cell.com/trends/biotechnology/abstract/S0167-7799\(10\)00054-5](https://www.cell.com/action/showFullText?pii=S0167779910000545https://www.cell.com/action/showAbstract?pii=S0167779910000545https://www.cell.com/trends/biotechnology/abstract/S0167-7799(10)00054-5)
- [73] P. Sagmeister, "statistical and mechanistic bioprocess model," 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.koerber-pharma.com/blog/statistical-and-mechanistic-bioprocess-model>
- [74] M. Canzoneri, M. Horner, and P. Banerjee, *Digital Twins in Biomanufacturing*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, pp. 59–81. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-61593-1_4
- [75] Y.-H. Du, M.-Y. Wang, L.-H. Yang, L.-L. Tong, D.-S. Guo, and X.-J. Ji, "Optimization and scale-up of fermentation processes driven by models," *Bioengineering*, vol. 9, no. 9, p. 473, Sep 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9495923/>
- [76] S. K. Hahl and A. Kremling, "A comparison of deterministic and stochastic modeling approaches for biochemical reaction systems: On fixed points, means, and modes," *Frontiers in Genetics*, vol. 7, Aug 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27630669/>

- [77] J. Almquist, M. Cvijovic, V. Hatzimanikatis, J. Nielsen, and M. Jirstrand, "Kinetic models in industrial biotechnology – improving cell factory performance," *Metabolic Engineering*, vol. 24, p. 38–60, Apr 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S109671761400041X>
- [78] M. A. Henson, "Dynamic modeling of microbial cell populations," *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 460–467, 2003. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0958166903001046>
- [79] G. Sin, P. Ödman, N. Petersen, A. E. Lantz, and K. V. Gernaey, "Matrix notation for efficient development of first-principles models within pat applications: Integrated modeling of antibiotic production with streptomyces coelicolor," *Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, vol. 101, pp. 153–171, 9 2008. [Online]. Available: [/doi/pdf/10.1002/bit.21869https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/bit.21869https://analyticalsciencejournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/bit.21869](https://doi/pdf/10.1002/bit.21869https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/bit.21869https://analyticalsciencejournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/bit.21869)
- [80] Agger, "Growth and product formation of aspergillus oryzae during submerged cultivations: verification of a morphologically structured model using fluorescent probes," *Biotechnology and bioengineering*, vol. 57, no. 3, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10099209/>
- [81] S. Kyriakopoulos, K. S. Ang, M. Lakshmanan, Z. Huang, S. Yoon, R. Gunawan, and D. Y. Lee, "Kinetic modeling of mammalian cell culture bioprocessing: The quest to advance biomanufacturing," *Biotechnology Journal*, vol. 13, 3 2018. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320385958_Kinetic_Modeling_of_Mammalian_Cell_Culture_Bioprocessing_The_Quest_to_Advance_Biomanufacturing
- [82] J. Nielsen and J. Villadsen, "Modelling of microbial kinetics," *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 47, pp. 4225–4270, 12 1992. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/000925099285104J>
- [83] J. A. Vázquez and M. A. Murado, "Unstructured mathematical model for biomass, lactic acid and bacteriocin production by lactic acid bacteria in batch fermentation," *Journal of Chemical Technology & Biotechnology*, vol. 83, no. 1, p. 91–96, Oct 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://scijournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/jctb.1789>
- [84] C. González-Figueroa, R. A. Flores-Estrella, and Ó. A. Rojas-Rejón, "Fermentation: Metabolism, kinetic models, and bioprocessing," *Current Topics in Biochemical Engineering*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:92835961>

- [85] A. K. Gombert and J. Nielsen, "Mathematical modelling of metabolism," *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*, vol. 11, no. 2, p. 180–186, Apr 2000. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10753761/>
- [86] D. S. Cunningham, R. R. Koepsel, M. M. Ataii, and M. M. Domach, "Factors affecting plasmid production in escherichia coli from a resource allocation standpoint," *Microbial Cell Factories*, vol. 8, pp. 1–17, 5 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://microbialcellfactories.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1475-2859-8-27>
- [87] J. D. Orth, I. Thiele, and B. Palsson, "What is flux balance analysis?" *Nature Biotechnology*, vol. 28, no. 3, p. 245–248, Mar 2010. [Online]. Available: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3108565/>
- [88] M. Gotsmy, F. Strobl, F. Weiß, P. Gruber, B. Kraus, J. Mairhofer, and J. Zanghellini, "Sulfate limitation increases specific plasmid dna yield and productivity in e. coli fed-batch processes," *Microbial cell factories*, vol. 22, 12 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38017439/>
- [89] R. Schuetz, L. Kuepfer, and U. Sauer, "Systematic evaluation of objective functions for predicting intracellular fluxes in escherichia coli," *Molecular Systems Biology*, vol. 3, no. 1, Jan 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1949037/>
- [90] P. Çalik and N. İleri, "ph influences intracellular reaction network of -lactamase producing bacillus licheniformis," *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 62, no. 18-20, p. 5206–5211, Sep 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0009250907001376?via%3Dihub>
- [91] X. J. Xiong and Y. F. Li, "Study on temperature regulation of lactic acid bacteria using metabolic flux analysis," *Advanced materials research*, vol. 356-360, p. 127–132, Oct 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://www.scientific.net/AMR.356-360.127>
- [92] C. P. Long, J. E. Gonzalez, N. R. Sandoval, and M. R. Antoniewicz, "Characterization of physiological responses to 22 gene knockouts in escherichia coli central carbon metabolism," *Metabolic Engineering*, vol. 37, p. 102–113, Sep 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1096717616300179?via%3Dihub>
- [93] H. Shimizu, N. Shimizu, and S. Shioya, "Roles of glucose and acetate as carbon sources inl-histidine production withbrevibacterium flavum ferm1564 revealed by metabolic flux analysis," *Biotechnology and Bioprocess Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 3, p. 171–177, Jun 2002. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/BF02932915>

- [94] T. Shirai, A. Nakato, N. Izutani, K. Nagahisa, S. Shioya, E. Kimura, Y. Kawarabayasi, A. Yamagishi, T. Gojobori, and H. Shimizu, "Comparative study of flux redistribution of metabolic pathway in glutamate production by two coryneform bacteria," *Metabolic Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 2, p. 59–69, Mar 2005. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15781416/>
- [95] R. Mahadevan and C. Schilling, "The effects of alternate optimal solutions in constraint-based genome-scale metabolic models," *Metabolic Engineering*, vol. 5, no. 4, p. 264–276, Oct 2003. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1096717603000582?via%3Dihub>
- [96] L. Heirendt, S. Arreckx, T. Pfau, S. N. Mendoza, A. Richelle, A. Heinken, H. S. Haraldsdóttir, J. Wachowiak, S. M. Keating, V. Vlasov, S. Magnúsdóttir, C. Y. Ng, G. Preciat, A. Žagare, S. H. J. Chan, M. K. Aurich, C. M. Clancy, J. Modamio, J. T. Sauls, and A. Noronha, "Creation and analysis of biochemical constraint-based models using the cobra toolbox v.3.0," *Nature Protocols*, vol. 14, no. 3, p. 639–702, Feb 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41596-018-0098-2>
- [97] M. A. Henson and T. J. Hanly, "Dynamic flux balance analysis for synthetic microbial communities," *IET Systems Biology*, vol. 8, no. 5, p. 214–229, Oct 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://ietresearch.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1049/iet-syb.2013.0021>
- [98] K. Bohle and A. Ross, "Plasmid dna production for pharmaceutical use: role of specific growth rate and impact on process design," *Biotechnology and bioengineering*, vol. 108, pp. 2099–2106, 9 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21437880/>
- [99] A. García-Rendón, R. Munguía-Soto, R. M. Montesinos-Cisneros, R. Guzman, and A. Tejeda-Mansir, "Performance analysis of exponential-fed perfusion cultures for pdna vaccines production," *Journal of Chemical Technology and Biotechnology*, vol. 92, pp. 342–349, 2 2017. [Online]. Available: [/doi/pdf/10.1002/jctb.5011](https://doi/pdf/10.1002/jctb.5011)<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/jctb.5011><https://scijournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/jctb.5011>
- [100] A. García-Rendón, A. García-Rendón, R. Guzmán, and A. Tejeda-Mansir, "Substrate-source flexibility of an exponential-fed perfusion process to produce plasmid dna for use as leishmaniasis vaccine," *Biotechnology and Biotechnological Equipment*, vol. 33, pp. 195–203, 1 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/13102818.2018.1560232>
- [101] F. Grijalva-Hernández, V. P. Caballero, P. A. López-Pérez, and R. Aguilar-López, "Estimation of plasmid concentration in batch culture of escherichia coli dh5a via simple state observer," *Chemical Papers*, vol. 72, pp. 2589–2598, 10 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11696-018-0478-7>

- [102] O. Roeva, "Parameter estimation of a monod-type model based on genetic algorithms and sensitivity analysis," *Lecture notes in computer science*, p. 601–608, Jan 2008. [Online]. Available: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-540-78827-0_69?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- [103] G. Jia, G. N. Stephanopoulos, and R. Gunawan, "Parameter estimation of kinetic models from metabolic profiles: two-phase dynamic decoupling method," *Bioinformatics*, vol. 27, no. 14, p. 1964–1970, May 2011. [Online]. Available: https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6281308/?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- [104] V. Rajamanickam, H. Babel, L. Montano-Herrera, A. Ehsani, F. Stiefel, S. Haider, B. Presser, and B. Knapp, "About model validation in bioprocessing," *Processes*, vol. 9, no. 6, p. 961, May 2021. [Online]. Available: https://www.mdpi.com/2227-9717/9/6/961?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- [105] K. Ramanathan and C. S. Sharma, "Kinetic parameters estimation for three way catalyst modeling," *Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 50, pp. 9960–9979, 9 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/ie200726j>
- [106] P. Kroll, A. Hofer, I. V. Stelzer, and C. Herwig, "Workflow to set up substantial target-oriented mechanistic process models in bioprocess engineering," *Process Biochemistry*, vol. 62, pp. 24–36, 11 2017.
- [107] R. L. Fernandes, V. K. Bodla, M. Carlquist, A. L. Heins, A. E. Lantz, G. Sin, and K. V. Gernaey, "Applying mechanistic models in bioprocess development." *Advances in Biochemical Engineering/Biotechnology*, vol. 132, pp. 137–166, 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://orbit.dtu.dk/en/publications/applying-mechanistic-models-in-bioprocess-development>
- [108] B. Petersen, K. Gernaey, M. Devisscher, D. Dochain, and P. A. Vanrolleghem, "A simplified method to assess structurally identifiable parameters in monod-based activated sludge models," *Water Research*, vol. 37, no. 12, p. 2893–2904, Jul 2003. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0043135403001143>
- [109] B. Petersen, K. Gernaey, and P. A. Vanrolleghem, "Practical identifiability of model parameters by combined respirometric-titrimetric measurements," *Water Science and Technology*, vol. 43, pp. 347–355, 2001. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/11953030_Practical_Identifiability_of_Model_Parameters_by_Combined_Respirometric-Titrimetric_Measurements
- [110] A. C. Daly, D. Gavaghan, J. Cooper, and S. Tavener, "Inference-based assessment of parameter identifiability in nonlinear biological models," *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*, vol. 15, 7 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/10.1098/rsif.2018.0318>

- [111] G. Sin and K. Gernaey, "Data handling and parameter estimation," *Welcome to DTU Research Database*, p. 201–234, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://orbit.dtu.dk/en/publications/data-handling-and-parameter-estimation>
- [112] A. Gábor, A. F. Villaverde, and J. R. Banga, "Parameter identifiability analysis and visualization in large-scale kinetic models of biosystems," *BMC Systems Biology*, vol. 11, pp. 1–16, 5 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/articles/10.1186/s12918-017-0428-yhttps://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s12918-017-0428-y>
- [113] A. F. Villaverde, F. Fröhlich, D. Weindl, J. Hasenauer, and J. R. Banga, "Benchmarking optimization methods for parameter estimation in large kinetic models," *Bioinformatics*, vol. 35, pp. 830–838, 3 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty736>
- [114] D. M. Prazeres, G. N. Ferreira, G. A. Monteiro, C. L. Cooney, and J. M. Cabral, "Large-scale production of pharmaceutical-grade plasmid dna for gene therapy: Problems and bottlenecks," *Trends in Biotechnology*, vol. 17, pp. 169–174, 4 1999. [Online]. Available: [https://www.cell.com/action/showFullText?pii=S0167779998012918https://www.cell.com/action/showAbstract?pii=S0167779998012918https://www.cell.com/trends/biotechnology/abstract/S0167-7799\(98\)01291-8](https://www.cell.com/action/showFullText?pii=S0167779998012918https://www.cell.com/action/showAbstract?pii=S0167779998012918https://www.cell.com/trends/biotechnology/abstract/S0167-7799(98)01291-8)
- [115] K. A. Datsenko and B. L. Wanner, "One-step inactivation of chromosomal genes in escherichia coli k-12 using pcr products," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, vol. 97, pp. 6640–6645, 6 2000. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10829079/>
- [116] A. R. Azzoni, S. C. Ribeiro, G. A. Monteiro, and D. M. Prazeres, "The impact of polyadenylation signals on plasmid nuclease-resistance and transgene expression," *The Journal of Gene Medicine*, vol. 9, no. 5, p. 392–402, Apr 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/jgm.1031>
- [117] J. Monod, "The growth of bacterial cultures," *Annual Review of Microbiology*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 371–394, Oct 1949. [Online]. Available: <https://www.annualreviews.org/content/journals/10.1146/annurev.mi.03.100149.002103>
- [118] R. Brun, M. Kühni, H. Siegrist, W. Gujer, and P. Reichert, "Practical identifiability of asm2d parameters - systematic selection and tuning of parameter subsets," *Water Research*, vol. 36, pp. 4113–4127, 2002.
- [119] M. D. Morris, "Factorial sampling plans for preliminary computational experiments," *Technometrics*, vol. 33, p. 161, 5 1991.

- [120] G. Sin, K. V. Gernaey, and A. E. Lantz, "Good modeling practice for pat applications: Propagation of input uncertainty and sensitivity analysis," *Biotechnology Progress*, vol. 25, pp. 1043–1053, 7 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19569187/>
- [121] K. A. Presser, D. A. Ratkowsky, and T. Ross, "Modelling the growth rate of escherichia coli as a function of ph and lactic acid concentration," *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, vol. 63, p. 2355, 1997. [Online]. Available: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC168528/>
- [122] M. K. Danquah and G. M. Forde, "Growth medium selection and its economic impact on plasmid dna production," *Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering*, vol. 104, pp. 490–497, 12 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1389172308700082>
- [123] W. V. Gonzales, A. T. Mobashsher, and A. Abbosh, "The progress of glucose monitoring—a review of invasive to minimally and non-invasive techniques, devices and sensors," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 19, 2 2019.
- [124] C. Kilkenny, W. J. Browne, I. C. Cuthill, M. Emerson, and D. G. Altman, "Improving bioscience research reporting: The arrive guidelines for reporting animal research," *PLoS Biology*, vol. 8, 6 2010.
- [125] M. B. Lopes, K. C. Sales, V. V. Lopes, and C. R. Calado, "Real-time plasmid monitoring of batch and fed-batch escherichia coli cultures by nir spectroscopy," *3rd Portuguese Bioengineering Meeting, ENBENG 2013 - Book of Proceedings*, 2013.
- [126] F. Rosa, K. C. Sales, B. R. Cunha, A. Couto, M. B. Lopes, and C. R. Calado, "A comprehensive high-throughput ftir spectroscopy-based method for evaluating the transfection event: estimating the transfection efficiency and extracting associated metabolic responses," *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry*, vol. 407, 9 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26329279/>
- [127] K. C. Sales, F. Rosa, B. R. Cunha, P. N. Sampaio, M. B. Lopes, and C. R. Calado, "Metabolic profiling of recombinant escherichia coli cultivations based on high-throughput ft-mir spectroscopic analysis," *Biotechnology Progress*, vol. 33, pp. 285–298, 3 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27696721/>

Experimental data

Sequence of pVAX1-GFP plasmid (3697 bp):

```
1 GACTCTTCGC GATGTACGGG CCAGATATAC GCGTTGACAT TGATTATTGA CTAGTTATTA
61 ATAGTAATCA ATTACGGGGT CATTAGTTCA TAGCCCATAT ATGGAGTTCC GCGTTACATA
121 ACTTACGGTA AATGGCCCGC CTGGCTGACC GCCCAACGAC CCCCGCCCAT TGACGTCAAT
181 AATGACGTAT GTTCCCATAG TAACGCCAAT AGGGACTTTC CATTGACGTC AATGGGTGGA
241 CTATTTACGG TAAACTGCCC ACTTGCCAGT ACATCAAGTG TATCATATGC CAAGTACGCC
301 CCCTATTGAC GTCAATGACG GTAAATGGCC CGCCTGGCAT TATGCCCAGT ACATGACCTT
361 ATGGGACTTT CCTACTTGGC AGTACATCTA CGTATTAGTC ATCGCTATTA CCATGGTGAT
421 GCGGTTTTGG CAGTACATCA ATGGGCGTGG ATAGCGGTTT GACTCACGGG GATTTCCAAG
481 TCTCCACCCC ATTGACGTCA ATGGGAGTTT GTTTTGGCAC CAAAATCAAC GGGACTTTCC
541 AAAATGTCGT AACAACTCCG CCCATTGAC GCAAATGGGC GGTAGGCGTG TACGGTGGGA
601 GGTCTATATA AGCAGAGCTC TCTGGCTAAC TAGAGAACCC ACTGCTTACT GGCTTATCGA
661 AATTAATACG ACTCACTATA GGGAGACCCA AGCTGGCTAG CGTTTAAACT TAAGCTTGGT
721 ACCGAGCTCG GATCCACTAG TCCAGTGTGG TGGAATTCGC ATATGGTGAG CAAGGGCGAG
781 GAGCTGTTCA CCGGGGTGGT GCCCATCCTG GTCGAGCTGG ACGGCGACGT AAACGGCCAC
841 AAGTTCAGCG TGTCCGGCGA GGGCGAGGGC GATGCCACCT ACGGCAAGCT GACCCTGAAG
901 TTCATCTGCA CCACCGGCAA GCTGCCCGTG CCCTGGCCCA CCCTCGTGAC CACCCTGACC
961 TACGGCGTGC AGTGCTTCAG CCGTACCCC GACCACATGA AGCAGCACGA CTTCTTCAAG
1021 TCCGCCATGC CCGAAGGCTA CGTCCAGGAG CGCACCATCT TCTTCAAGGA CGACGGCAAC
1081 TACAAGACCC GCGCCGAGGT GAAGTTCGAG GGCGACACCC TGGTGAACCG CATCGAGCTG
1141 AAGGGCATCG ACTTCAAGGA GGACGGCAAC ATCCTGGGGC ACAAGCTGGA GTACAACACT
1201 AACAGCCACA ACGTCTATAT CATGGCCGAC AAGCAGAAGA ACGGCATCAA GGTGAACTTC
1261 AAGATCCGCC ACAACATCGA GGACGGCAGC GTGCAGCTCG CCGACCACTA CCAGCAGAAC
1321 ACCCCATCG GCGACGGCCC CGTGCTGCTG CCCGACAACC ACTACCTGAG CACCAGTCC
1381 GCCCTGAGCA AAGACCCCAA CGAGAAGCGC GATCACATGG TCCTGCTGGA GTTCGTGACC
1441 GCCGCCGGGA TCACTCTCGG CATGGACGAG CTGTACAAGT AATGGATCCT CTAGAGGGCC
```

1501 CGTTTAAACC CGCTGATCAG CCTCGACTGT GCCTTCTAGT TGCCAGCCAT CTGTTGTTTTG
1561 CCCCTCCCC GTGCCCTTCT TGACCCTGGA AGGTGCCACT CCCACTGTCC TTTCTAATA
1621 AAATGAGGAA ATTGCATCGC ATTGTCTGAG TAGGTGTCAT TCTATTCTGG GGGGTGGGGT
1681 GGGGCAGGAC AGCAAGGGGG AGGATTGGGA AGACAATAGC AGGCATGCTG GGGATGCGGT
1741 GGGCTCTATG GCTTCTACTG GGCGGTTTTA TGGACAGCAA GCGAACCGGA ATTGCCAGCT
1801 GGGGCGCCCT CTGGTAAGGT TGGGAAGCCC TGCAAAGTAA ACTGGATGGC TTTCTCGCCG
1861 CCAAGGATCT GATGGCGCAG GGGATCAAGC TCTGATCAAG AGACAGGATG AGGATCGTTT
1921 CGCATGATTG AACAAGATGG ATTGCACGCA GGTTCTCCGG CCGCTTGGGT GGAGAGGCTA
1981 TTCGGCTATG ACTGGGCACA ACAGACAATC GGCTGCTCTG ATGCCGCCGT GTTCCGGCTG
2041 TCAGCGCAGG GGCGCCCGGT TCTTTTTGTC AAGACCGACC TGTCCGGTGC CCTGAATGAA
2101 CTGCAAGACG AGGCAGCGCG GCTATCGTGG CTGGCCACGA CGGGCGTTCC TTGCGCAGCT
2161 GTGCTCGACG TTGCTACTGA AGCGGGAAGG GACTGGCTGC TATTGGGCGA AGTGCCGGGG
2221 CAGGATCTCC TGTCATCTCA CCTTGCTCCT GCCGAGAAAG TATCCATCAT GGCTGATGCA
2281 ATGCGGCGGC TGCATACGCT TGATCCGGCT ACCTGCCCAT TCGACCACCA AGCGAAACAT
2341 CGCATCGAGC GAGCACGTAC TCGGATGGAA GCCGGTCTTG TCGATCAGGA TGATCTGGAC
2401 GAAGAGCATC AGGGGCTCGC GCCAGCCGAA CTGTTCCGCC GGCTCAAGGC GAGCATGCCC
2461 GACGGCGAGG ATCTCGTCGT GACCCATGGC GATGCCTGCT TGCCGAATAT CATGGTGGAA
2521 AATGGCCGCT TTTCTGGATT CATCGACTGT GGCCGGCTGG GTGTGCGCGA CCGTATCAG
2581 GACATAGCGT TGGCTACCCG TGATATTGCT GAAGAGCTTG GCGGCGAATG GGCTGACCGC
2641 TTCCTCGTGC TTTACGGTAT CGCCGCTCCC GATTGCGAGC GCATCGCCTT CTATCGCCTT
2701 CTTGACGAGT TCTTCTGAAT TATTAACGCT TACAATTTCC TGATGCGGTA TTTTCTCCTT
2761 ACGCATCTGT GCGGTATTTT ACACCGCATA CAGGTGGCAC TTTTCGGGGA AATGTGCGCG
2821 GAACCCCTAT TTGTTTATTT TTCTAAATAC ATTCAAATAT GTATCCGCTC ATGAGACAAT
2881 AACCCGTATA AATGCTTCAA TAATAGCACG TGCTAAAAC TCAATTTTAA TTTAAAAGGA
2941 TCTAGGTGAA GATCCTTTTT GATAATCTCA TGACCAAAAT CCCTAACGT GAGTTTTCGT
3001 TCCACTGAGC GTCAGACCCC GTAGAAAAGA TCAAAGGATC TTCTTGAGAT CCTTTTTTTC
3061 TGCGCGTAAT CTGCTGCTTG CAAACAAAAA AACCACCGCT ACCAGCGGTG GTTTGTTTGC
3121 CGGATCAAGA GCTACCAACT CTTTTTCCGA AGGTAACGGT CTTGAGCAGA GCGCAGATAC
3181 CAAATACTGT CCTTCTAGTG TAGCCGTAGT TAGGCCACCA CTTCAAGAAC TCTGTAGCAC
3241 CGCTACATA CCTCGCTCTG CTAATCCTGT TACCAGTGGC TGCTGCCAGT GCGGATAAGT
3301 CGTGTCTTAC CGGGTTGGAC TCAAGACGAT AGTTACCGGA TAAGGCGCAG CGGTGCGGCT
3361 GAACGGGGGG TTCGTGCACA CAGCCAGCT TGGAGCGAAC GACCTACACC GAAGTGAAT
3421 ACCTACAGCG TGAGCTATGA GAAAGCGCCA CGCTTCCCGA AGGGAGAAAG GCGGACAGGT
3481 ATCCGGTAAG CGGCAGGGTC GGAACAGGAG AGCGCACGAG GGAGCTTCCA GGGGAAACG
3541 CCTGGTATCT TTATAGTCTC GTCGGGTTTC GCCACCTCTG ACTTGAGCGT CGATTTTTGT
3601 GATGCTCGTC AGGGGGGCGG AGCCTATGGA AAAACGCCAG CAACGCGGCC TTTTACGGT
3661 TCCTGGGCTT TTGCTGGCCT TTTGCTCACA TGTTCTT

t	P (g/L)	X (g/L)	S (g/L)	A (g/L)	SD P	SD X	SD S	SD A
0	1,00E-03	7,40E-02	1,61E+01	0,00E+00	0,00E+00	2,10E-02	3,10E-01	0,00E+00
1		4,88E-01				9,20E-02		
2		7,80E-02				7,00E-03		
3		1,24E-01				2,80E-02		
4		1,50E-01				2,10E-02		
5		1,90E-01	1,50E+01	0,00E+00		3,50E-02	5,00E-01	0,00E+00
6		2,64E-01				2,80E-02		
7		3,42E-01	1,54E+01	1,20E-01		7,00E-03	4,30E-01	0,00E+00
8		4,68E-01				2,80E-02		
9	3,98E-03	6,60E-01	1,47E+01	3,00E-01	6,95E-04	1,27E-01	3,00E-01	2,00E-02
24	1,18E-02	2,04E+00	6,10E+00	1,06E+01	8,64E-04	2,83E-01	6,00E-02	5,00E-02

Figure A.1: Experimental values of plasmid (P), biomass (X), glucose (S), and acetate (A), and respective standard deviations (SD) for each time point, for shake flask culture of **DH5 α** .

t	P (g/L)	X (g/L)	S (g/L)	A (g/L)	SD P	SD X	SD S	SD A
0	1,00E-03	8,40E-02	1,59E+01	0,00E+00	0,00E+00	0,00E+00	8,70E-01	0,00E+00
1		2,60E-02				2,10E-02		
2		5,40E-02				3,50E-02		
3		6,40E-02				2,80E-02		
4		7,80E-02				7,00E-03		
5		8,20E-02	1,61E+01	0,00E+00		7,00E-03	3,00E-02	0,00E+00
6		1,08E-01				2,80E-02		
7		1,38E-01	1,56E+01	2,00E-02		7,00E-03	1,60E-01	0,00E+00
8		1,82E-01				3,50E-02		
9	4,31E-03	2,58E-01	1,52E+01	1,10E-01	3,81E-03	4,90E-02	3,60E-01	0,00E+00
24	8,88E-03	1,66E+00	5,05E+00	9,41E+00	1,30E-03	1,70E-01	3,30E-01	3,20E-01

Figure A.2: Experimental values of plasmid (P), biomass (X), glucose (S), and acetate (A), and respective standard deviations (SD) for each time point, for shake flask culture of **MG1655**.

t	P (g/L)	X (g/L)	S (g/L)	A (g/L)	SD P	SD X	SD S	SD A
0	1,00E-03	9,40E-02	1,62E+01	0,00E+00	0,00E+00	4,90E-02	3,10E-01	0,00E+00
1		6,60E-02				6,40E-02		
2		1,28E-01				0,00E+00		
3		1,78E-01				2,10E-02		
4		2,98E-01				2,10E-02		
5		3,92E-01	1,55E+01	1,60E-01		1,40E-02	2,60E-01	1,00E-02
6		5,22E-01				2,10E-02		
7		7,70E-01	1,44E+01	3,80E-01		7,80E-02	3,70E-01	1,00E-02
8		1,04E+00				1,40E-02		
9	5,68E-03	1,50E+00	1,13E+01	8,10E-01	1,04E-03	1,34E-01	7,00E-01	2,00E-02
24	1,26E-02	2,11E+00	4,89E+00	7,80E+00	8,99E-03	3,50E-02	6,00E-02	5,00E-02

Figure A.3: Experimental values of plasmid (P), biomass (X), glucose (S), and acetate (A), and respective standard deviations (SD) for each time point, for shake flask culture of **GALG20**.

B

Model Analysis

Table B.1: Sensitivity matrix for DH5 α according to the outputs biomass (X), glucose (S), plasmid (P), and acetate (A).

Output	umaxS	umaxA	Yx_s	Yx_a	Yp_xs	Yp_xa	Ypa_s	Ks	Ka	Kix_a
X	0.5488	0.1533	0.6164	0.1412	0.000	0.0000	0.1278	-0.0038	-0.0397	0.0339
S	-0.1389	-0.0151	0.0244	0.0003	0.000	0.0000	-0.0002	0.0006	0.0036	-0.0021
P	0.2185	0.0546	0.2453	0.0463	0.2255	0.1064	0.0.0421	-0.0014	-0.0141	0.0117
A	0.2405	-0.1508	0.2649	0.2620	0.000	0.0000	0.4805	0.0018	0.0419	-0.0442

Table B.2: Sensitivity matrix for MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA (MG1655) according to the outputs biomass (X), glucose (S), plasmid (P), and acetate (A).

Output	umaxS	umaxA	Yx_s	Yx_a	Yp_xs	Yp_xa	Ypa_s	Ks	Ka	Kix_a
X	0.4259	0.1331	0.2133	0.0565	0.0000	0.0000	0.0523	-0.0029	-0.0259	0.0184
S	-0.5143	-0.0940	0.1344	0.0056	0.0000	0.0000	0.0060	0.0038	0.0248	-0.0180
P	0.1425	0.0415	0.0715	0.0156	0.0862	0.0352	0.0144	-0.0010	-0.0084	0.0060
A	0.2524	-0.2045	0.1436	0.2207	0.0000	0.0000	0.5095	-0.0027	0.0121	-0.0072

Table B.3: Sensitivity matrix for GALG20 according to the outputs biomass (X), glucose (S), plasmid (P), and acetate (A).

Output	umaxS	umaxA	Yx_s	Yx_a	Yp_xs	Yp_xa	Ypa_s	Ks	Ka	Kix_a
X	0.6857	0.2083	0.1829	0.0353	0.0000	0.0000	0.0278	-0.0033	-0.0380	0.0287
S	-0.2346	-0.0420	0.0546	0.0025	0.0000	0.0000	0.0040	0.0011	0.0098	-0.0074
P	0.2066	0.0585	0.0557	0.0085	0.0889	0.0328	0.0064	-0.0010	-0.0110	0.0083
A	11.0299	-6.1282	4.2821	6.2538	0.0000	0.0000	14.5851	-0.0520	0.4170	-0.3251

DH5 α

MG1655

GALG20

Figure B.1: Ranked importance of parameters (δ_j) according to output using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right). The figures display the outputs of biomass (top left), glucose (top right), pDNA (bottom left), and acetate (bottom right).

DH5 α

MG1655

GALG20

Figure B.2: Fitting of estimation data to the simulation according to output using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right). The figure displays time-series data for biomass (top left), glucose (top right), pDNA (bottom left), and acetate (bottom right) concentrations for each strain. The experimental points are represented by dots, while the fitting obtained for each output is represented by a dashed line.

	umaxS	umaxA	Yx_s	Yp_xa
umaxS	1.000	0.053	0.252	-0.183
umaxA	0.053	1.000	0.653	-0.879
Yx_s	0.252	0.653	1.000	-0.755
Yp_xa	-0.183	-0.879	-0.755	1.000

DH5 α

	umaxS	Yx_s	Yx_a	Yp_xa
umaxS	1.000	0.681	-0.299	-0.316
Yx_s	0.681	1.000	-0.506	-0.394
Yx_a	-0.299	-0.506	1.000	-0.175
Yp_xa	-0.316	-0.394	-0.175	1.000

MG1655

	umaxA	Yx_s	Yp_xa
umaxA	1.000	0.227	-0.189
Yx_s	0.227	1.000	-0.719
Yp_xa	-0.189	-0.719	1.000

GALG20

Figure B.3: Correlation between estimated parameters using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right).

Figure B.4: Simulation vs experimental results according to output for testing model using **batch** cultures using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right). The figure displays time-series data for biomass (top left), glucose (top right), pDNA (bottom left), and acetate (bottom right) concentrations for each strain. The experimental points are represented by dots, while the fitting obtained for each output is represented by a dashed line.

DH5 α

MG1655

GALG20

Figure B.5: Simulation vs experimental results according to output for testing model using **shale flask** cultures using DH5 α (top), MG1655 (bottom left), and GALG20 (bottom right). The figure displays time-series data for biomass (top left), glucose (top right), pDNA (bottom left), and acetate (bottom right) concentrations for each strain. The experimental points are represented by dots, while the fitting obtained for each output is represented by a dashed line.

